

Understanding the role of the Advanced Paediatric Nurse Practitioner from the perspectives of service users and service providers within NHS Scotland: a Gadamerian hermeneutic approach.

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Abstract

Introduction:

The Scottish Government prioritises improving capacity and capability in child health (Scottish Government, 2006; 2008; 2017) and aims to develop a skilled workforce capable of adapting to changing health and social care needs (Scottish Government, 2010). Advanced paediatric nurse practitioners (APNPs) are central to the Scottish Government's (2017) strategy to address the evolving health and care demands of children, young people, and their families in Scotland.

Aim of study: This research aims to develop an understanding and meaning of the APNP role from a whole Systems perspective of service providers and service users.

Method: Using a Gadamerian philosophical hermeneutic (Gadamer, 2012) lens, a purposeful sample of 8 APNPs, 8 'others', members of the multidisciplinary team who work alongside APNPs, and 5 parents participated in conversational interviews with the researcher about their experience, understanding and meaning of the advanced paediatric nurse practitioner role (n = 21 conversations) in NHS Scotland. The research process was guided by using the research method of Fleming *et al.*, (2003).

Results: The findings from the conversations are presented in three chapters and constitute a hermeneutic narrative that represents emergent themes from each participant group. The emergent themes for APNPs were Taking a chance, Professional Identity, Communication and Family Centredness; For 'Others' were Professional Identity, Bridging the gap, and Inconsistency; And finally for Parents were Bridging the gap, Communication skills and Clinical Competence, and Caring Behaviour. A fusion of horizon chapter offers a critical discussion on these emergent themes within the context of contemporary literature.

Conclusion: This thesis makes a unique contribution to knowledge as the first study in Scotland, and the wider UK, to explore the APNP role from these three perspectives: APNPs, 'others' as professional colleagues, and parents. By integrating these voices, the research demonstrates that relational essence embodied in communication, empathy, and caring behaviours is as vital as clinical competence in shaping new role development. The study provides narrative evidence from multiple stakeholders, offering a holistic understanding of how APNPs are perceived and legitimised in practice. Most significantly, it illuminates the parent perspective for the first time, revealing their appreciation of APNPs' ability to bridge the gap between nursing and medicine, their clinical expertise, and the caring behaviours rooted in prior nursing experience. These insights extend existing conceptualisations of the APNP role and provide a foundation for supporting future workforce planning, education, and policy development in advanced paediatric nursing practice.

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My family is foremost in my gratitude for their support while I studied, worked, and balanced family life during both the joyful and challenging times. Both of my parents passed away during this period, and I faced an illness that led me to take a break, initially stepping away from my studies. However, my sheer determination and awareness that there were still gaps in this field motivated me to return, and personally, I was resolved to complete what I had begun. I hope that my display of perseverance and resilience will inspire my children as they navigate life, and I hope that everyone, including my parents, feels proud of me.

I would like to thank my current supervisors, Dr Beverley Young and Dr Clair Graham, for their determination, support, and facilitation in helping me reach my final goal. I know I wasn't the easiest student to support, but both of you have always been optimistic and encouraging, believing in me even when I did not believe in myself. I also wish to acknowledge the influence of my first supervisory team, as I began this doctoral journey at another university—Dr Yvonne Robb and Dr Marion Welsh. They helped shape my knowledge and the development of this thesis at the start of my journey, and I am grateful to them for that.

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Author's Declaration

I declare that this thesis is original and has been composed entirely through my own efforts.

It has not been submitted for another comparable academic award.

Date: 11 December 2025.

Signature:

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Glossary: Abbreviations and Terminology

ANP	<i>Advanced nurse practitioner</i> An experienced nurse with post-graduate education at Masters Level in clinical practice, and who is competent undertaking complete management of a patient journey.
ACP/AP	<i>Advanced clinical practitioner/ Advanced practitioner</i> Experienced practitioners from a range of professional backgrounds who are educated to Masters Level and are able to take on expanded roles due to highly developed skills and knowledge.
APNP	<i>Advanced paediatric nurse practitioner</i> An experienced paediatric nurse practitioner educated to Masters Level who is able to work independently to manage the complete care of patients and their family using expert knowledge base and clinical competence. (*Please see note below)
ANNP	<i>Advanced neonatal nurse practitioner</i> An experienced neonatal nurse educated to Masters Level who manages acute and chronic illness in neonates by formulating complex treatment plans, and who is able to support parents to make clinical decisions.
NP	<i>Nurse Practitioner</i> A term used for an advanced practice registered nurse, particularly noted in American/Canadian based literature.
HEE	<i>Health Education England</i> Public body organisation which is part of the NHS and works with partners to educate, train and develop healthcare professionals.
RCN	<i>Royal College of Nursing</i> A registered professional and trade union body supporting nurses.
NMC	<i>Nursing and Midwifery Council</i> Regulator for nursing and midwifery professions in UK. Maintains registers for eligible nurses and nursing associates able to practice. Sets and reviews standards for education, training, conduct and performance.
GP	<i>General Practice/Practitioner</i> A doctor/family practitioner in general practice, working in local communities providing comprehensive care for everyone, as part of multi-disciplinary teams.
NES	<i>NHS Education for Scotland</i> An education and training body, and an independent national health board. They develop and deliver healthcare education and training across Scotland at undergraduate, postgraduate and continuing professional development levels.
HEI	<i>Higher Education Institution</i> Provider of education after school, usually in college or university providing a variety of courses at undergraduate and postgraduate study level.
SAPEN	<i>Scottish Advanced Practice Education Network</i> Collaborative network taking a multidisciplinary, inclusive approach to enable UK wide collaboration on key areas of

	educational practice and research, provides a co-ordinated approach to AP education in Scotland.
NMAHP	<i>Nursing, midwifery and allied health professionals</i> Offers a development and education framework aligned to the Career Framework for Health
Hermeneutics	The act of understanding text
Dasein	Being in the world
Horizon	A way of viewing the world and conceptualising understanding
Aristotle's phronesis	Practical wisdom
Text	Written dialogue or conversation
Ontology	Theory of existence and nature of reality
Epistemology	Theory of knowledge
Temporality	Of or relating to time
Hermeneutic circle	Understanding of text as a whole is based on understanding of each individual part, and how this refers back to the whole.
Erfahrung	Experience of meaning
Logos	Vehicle for communicating with others
Die Sache	The subject matter about which people converse
Circulus vitiosus	Vicious cycle/circle
Temporal distance	Distance in time

*Please note: this thesis emphasises the importance of understanding the terminology used throughout. 'Advanced practice nursing' is frequently associated with titles such as nurse practitioner, consultant nurse, advanced practitioner, and clinical nurse specialist, all of which are widely recognised. However, there's often little consensus or distinction made between these roles and their titles (Jokiniemi et al, 2012). The latest Transforming Roles Paper (Paper 8, Scottish Government, 2021) aims to clarify the differences between advanced practitioners and Clinical Nurse Specialist roles. Nonetheless, in much of the literature, the term 'advanced nurse practitioner' is still broadly applied to encompass the wide range of advanced practice roles (Ketefian et al., 2001). All these roles and titles are grouped under the advanced practice umbrella, with each role practised within its specific clinical context or speciality. The literature referenced in this thesis relates to advanced practice roles across various settings, as reflected in the writing undertaken. For instance, advanced practitioners in paediatric settings are known as Advanced Paediatric Nurse Practitioners (APNPs).

CHAPTER ONE – Introduction and Overview of The Thesis

1 Introduction

This thesis highlights and contextualises a pivotal work-based clinical practice issue within the National Health Service (NHS) in Scotland, one that resonates with my own professional interests as an educationalist. The study offers a critical examination of the evolving understanding of the Advanced Paediatric Nurse Practitioner (APNP) role within NHS Scotland. Initially established to address a shortage of mid-grade medical staff in paediatrics, the APNP role has continued to develop, becoming increasingly embedded in clinical practice. Importantly, a growing body of evidence now demonstrates the positive impact of APNPs on both patient and service outcomes, as well as on the overall quality of care delivered (Newhouse *et al.*, 2011; Swan *et al.*, 2015; Ridgeway *et al.*, 2021). This study offers a critical appraisal of the methodological approaches employed and thoughtfully situates the philosophical principles that underpin the research. It proceeds to analyse the research conversations undertaken as part of this inquiry, illuminating the understandings that have emerged and illustrating how these insights contribute to a deeper comprehension of the subject matter.

This thesis was originally initiated in 2013, with research conversations conducted between 2015 and 2016. In 2018, unforeseen personal circumstances necessitated a pause in my studies, prompting a period of absence from the programme. By 2020, I began exploring the possibility of resuming my research, engaging in discussions with the Doctoral College. Following a thorough review of the literature in 2021, it became evident that a significant gap in the evidence base persisted within this area of practice. In consultation with my supervisory team, I resolved to recommence and ultimately complete this research journey. Advanced Paediatric practice remains a particular passion of mine, and I hope this work will make a meaningful contribution to the ongoing development of the field, which remains of critical importance.

With this in mind, the literature underpinning this study is organised into two distinct timelines. Chapters 1 to 4 predominantly draw upon my initial literature search, conducted between 1990 and 2017, a period during which scholarship on advanced practice began to emerge in the UK and also marks the timeframe leading up to the research interviews with participants, completed between 2015 and 2016. The development of this thesis continued during that period. However, following a period away from my studies and my return to study in 2021, I undertook a further literature search spanning 2016 to 2025 to ensure the research remained current and comprehensive.

From the outset, Gadamer's philosophical hermeneutic (Gadamer, 2012) concepts have guided this study, a methodological commitment explicitly identified in my IRAS ethics

application prior to commencing any research conversations. Gadamer's hermeneutics supports the reflective integration of existing knowledge with new insights gained from research conversations, enabling the emergence of new understandings that can be meaningfully presented.

1.1 Background to the study and on the use of Gadamer's work

This section provides the background of the study within the context of Advanced Practice and outlines the theoretical foundations used. It is followed by some information about myself as the researcher and my personal motivation for undertaking this study.

1.1.1 Advanced Practice

Healthcare organisations across the globe, including those in the United Kingdom, face challenges in providing high-quality care to those in need with fewer resources (Lowe *et al.*, 2012). The debate surrounding the difficulties in delivering adequate, efficient, and cost-effective healthcare under the current economic climate characterised by financial austerity is evident both in practice and in the literature (Mantzoukas and Watkinson, 2007; Barton *et al.*, 2012; Barnes, 2015; Britton and Blackwood, 2023; Miller *et al.*, 2024). Healthcare provision has been shaped by shifting societal expectations and beliefs, new perceptions of health and illness, the introduction of various technologies, and, more recently, the formal recognition of specific groups through education and regulation (Scottish Government, 2017; Nursing and Midwifery Council, 2024). Advanced practice has also been influenced by other factors, such as discussions of professional identity and interprofessional or cross-boundary relationships that have developed over time (Kilpatrick *et al.*, 2012; Academy of Medical Royal Colleges, 2020).

Several factors have combined to create new pressures on workforce development. These include unmet healthcare needs due to public service cutbacks, workforce reductions, reorganised services, emerging technologies, shifting population demographics, and difficulties in sustaining workforces amid changing workforce profiles. All these factors impact how healthcare needs are addressed (Scottish Government, 2006; Scottish Government, 2008; Mantzoukas and Watkinson, 2007; DOH, 2010; Currie and Grundy, 2011; Leary and MacLaine, 2019). Consequently, a new and innovative workforce is needed, one capable of responding effectively and flexibly to emerging opportunities and evolving care models (Scottish Government, 2006; Scottish Government, 2007; Scottish Government, 2017; Scottish Government, 2021). Roles in advanced nursing practice have adapted in response to these changing health and service care requirements (Por 2008; Miller *et al.*, 2024). From 2012 to 2014, the Scottish Government provided funding to develop a paediatric and neonatal advanced nurse practitioner programme, as no such course existed in Scotland at that time

(Curry and Grundy, 2011). NHS Education for Scotland (NHS) asked Scottish universities to collaborate on establishing an advanced practice programme for both specialisms. I was fortunate to be involved in this effort and served as the programme lead for the advanced paediatric and neonatal nurse practitioner programme at one Scottish university.

The literature demonstrates the emergent value of the advanced practitioner (AP) role in terms of clinical outcomes and as an efficient strategy for patient care (Hodson, 1998; Newhouse *et al.*, 2011; Kilpatrick *et al.*, 2024; Miller *et al.*, 2024). The role started in a haphazard way with a range of titles internationally, with the role being introduced in the 1990's in Scotland (De Geest *et al.*, 2008; Curry and Grundy, 2011; Miller *et al.*, 2024). The role continues to evolve as services adapt to shifting healthcare needs and advanced practice becomes integrated into daily practice. Nevertheless, in some regions, role development remains limited due to vague role definitions and systemic barriers, which often lead to inadequate funding for sustainable growth and competing clinical priorities (Boase *et al.*, 2017). The fast-paced development of these roles has created confusion about their scope, resulting in role ambiguity or unclear boundaries (Ormond-Walsh and Newham, 2001; Daly and Carnwell, 2003; Lankshear *et al.*, 2005; Newhouse *et al.*, 2011; Evans *et al.*, 2020; Evans *et al.*, 2020a; Miller *et al.*, 2024). Additionally, there is a noticeable gap in research exploring the softer aspects of understanding these roles.

Gadamer's philosophical hermeneutics (Gadamer, 2012) have shaped this study. Gadamer (2012) believes that understanding our surrounding world can be achieved by recognising the language, tradition, and culture that are uniquely embedded in each conversation we encounter, and by understanding how the comprehension of a conversation evolves, influenced by each person's distinctive background. Gadamer does not claim that everyone would interpret a conversation in the same way, which is an important point to note in the writing of this thesis.

To read and understand Gadamer's philosophical hermeneutics, *Truth and Method (Wahrheit und Methode)*, his magnum opus, was read. This is a translation of Gadamer's main work, originally written in German, his native language, along with other interpretations of his writings (Palmer 1969; Lawn 2006; Thistleton 2009; Simms 2015; and Dostal 2021). Hence, all sources used are translations, but many scholars have engaged with these translations, which have been revised over time. Through discussions with my doctoral peers and supervisors, I have ensured fidelity to Gadamer's ideas and philosophy. Any differences in his philosophical hermeneutics will be recognised and discussed openly.

Gadamer acknowledged that 'the inevitable mistakes reflect the limits of erudition or understanding' and noted that 'a translation must transpose a work from one time and cultural situation to another' (Gadamer, 1989, p.xi). Consequently, this study employs Gadamer's philosophical hermeneutics and its key concepts to explore the understanding of

the APNP role among NHS Scotland's service providers and service users. The research aims to provide a unique perspective and understanding of how three different groups perceive this role, potentially shaping future developments through narrative text, which offers an insight into how knowledge and understanding evolve.

1.1.2 Personal motivation

As a nurse, educator, and reflective practitioner involved in an advanced practice programme at a higher education institution in Scotland, I regularly interact with students pursuing an MSc in advanced clinical practice. Through conversations with them and engagement with pedagogical literature, I became interested in gaining a deeper understanding of the role of the advanced paediatric nurse practitioner (APNP) by examining the perspectives of service providers and service users.

As a researcher grounded in real-world experiences, I recognise that my prior exposure to literature on advanced practice and paediatric nursing has shaped my thinking in this area. Choosing to guide this study by using Gadamer's Philosophical Hermeneutics (Gadamer, 2012), underpinned by Gadamer's emphasis on historicity, language and culture, helps me challenge my previous knowledge and understanding of this role before beginning this study, which is crucial. By applying Gadamer's core concepts of Philosophical Hermeneutics to interpret the world around me, I can gain an understanding and meaning of the advanced paediatric nurse practitioner role in NHS Scotland, thus remaining open to new insights into this role.

This study will allow for my role as an educator to develop and, in the writing of this thesis, form a contribution to new nursing knowledge.

1.2 Aim of the research study

This study aims to gain understanding and meaning of the Advanced Paediatric Nurse Practitioner (APNP) role from a whole systems perspective of service providers and service users perspectives. This involves three groups of research participants: APNPs, 'others' (colleagues) who work alongside APNPs, and, finally, parents whose child was looked after by an APNP.

The research utilises a Gadamerian philosophical hermeneutic approach, with key concepts identified and applied to guide the study. The three groups of people were identified for this study to capture their experiences and understandings of this role, thereby encapsulating a whole systems perspective that is meaningful to understanding the APNP role.

1. Study Aim:

- To gain understanding and meaning of the APNP role from a whole systems perspective of service providers and service users.

2. Objectives

- To explore APNPs' perspectives on their role
- To investigate multidisciplinary colleagues' perspectives on the APNP role
- To explore parent user perspectives on the APNP service delivery

1.3 Structure of this thesis

Chapter 1 introduces this thesis, giving a background to the study, my personal motivation for doing this study, and outlining the research study aims and objectives.

Chapter 2 introduces the concept and evolution of advanced practice. The background, history, and policy context of advanced practice are explored globally, within the UK, and in Scotland. The latter part of this chapter highlights the development of a researchable topic and includes a narrative literature review.

Chapter 3 presents the theoretical framework guiding this study and examines the interpretivist paradigm. It introduces the origins of hermeneutics and discusses Gadamer's philosophical hermeneutics in relation to its application in this study.

Chapter 4 describes the method undertaken to carry out this research and reasoning for using a Gadamerian-based research approach previously undertaken by Fleming, Gaidys, and Robb (2003). The research process undertaken and considerations are also critically identified and discussed here.

Chapter 5 is the first of three Chapters discussing the research itself. This chapter focuses on the APNPs. Eight APNPs from across NHS Scotland agreed to participate in this study, and this chapter presents the conversations I had with the research participants. Conversations in the context of this study represent research interviews as they are situated within a Gadamerian philosophical hermeneutic context.

Chapter 6 is the second of three chapters that explore and focus on discussions held with eight 'Others'. These 'others' include various colleagues working alongside APNPs, such as Consultant paediatricians, Nurse Managers, a Nurse Director and a Staff Nurse. All have experience working with APNPs within their units or teams, and therefore hold opinions about the APNP role.

Chapter 7 is the third of three chapters that focus on conversations with five parents whose child received care from an APNP within the three months prior to the study's commencement. This timeframe was chosen so that parents would have a clear recollection of the care provided by an APNP to their child when unwell.

Chapter 8 is titled 'Fusion of Horizon', a Gadamerian term that signifies the discussion and analysis chapter based on conversations with all three groups of participants. This chapter provides an analysis of the findings from the researcher's perspective, placing this discussion in the context of current practice.

Chapter 9 presents the concluding remarks from this study and outlines the study's contribution to new knowledge. The chapter highlights that the findings carry implications for APNPs and inform recommendations for workforce planning, education, and policy. Limitations have been acknowledged and situate the study within its scope, while reflection on the research process underscores the importance of revisiting the original aim. The study highlights its theoretical and practical significance, offering a foundation for future inquiry and professional development.

1.4 Chapter Summary

This opening chapter has introduced the study and established its intellectual foundations. It has outlined the background to advanced practice, situating the research within the broader theoretical framework that informs its design. Specifically, the study is guided by a Gadamerian Philosophical Hermeneutic approach, which provides the interpretive lens through which advanced practice will be explored. Within this context, the study's aims and objectives have been articulated, thereby clarifying its scope and scholarly intent.

Chapter two will extend this groundwork by offering a more detailed examination of the historical development of advanced practice across Global, UK, and Scottish contexts. It will critically examine the conceptualisation of advanced practice and the policy drivers that have shaped its evolution, highlighting the interplay between professional practice and national health strategies. In addition, key dimensions central to advanced practice will be reviewed, including the Four Pillars of Advanced Practice, the education and training requirements underpinning advanced roles, and the regulatory frameworks that govern professional standards. The latter part of chapter two will conclude by presenting the search strategy and a narrative literature review, which together provide the evidential base for this study and situate it within the existing body of scholarship.

CHAPTER TWO Background to Advanced Practice

2.1 Introduction

This chapter offers a comprehensive exploration of the background and conceptual evolution of advanced practice across global, UK, and Scottish contexts. Recognising that an informed vision for the future of advanced practice must be grounded in a critical reflection on its past (Lewis, 2022), the chapter examines the development of advanced practice through the lens of policy, frameworks, and regional variations. To support this analysis, a table is provided that outlines the conceptual framework tracing the evolution of advanced practice from the early 1990s to the present day, alongside a second table detailing key policies that have shaped advanced practice in the UK. These frameworks and policies are discussed and integrated throughout the first half of the chapter, providing both context and continuity. The latter part of the chapter is devoted to outlining the comprehensive search strategy undertaken in two phases (1990 – 2015 Phase 1, and 2016 – 2025 Phase 2) due to suspension of my studies (see page 12), and presenting a narrative review of the relevant literature that underpins this study, thereby establishing a robust foundation for the research that follows.

Healthcare organisations globally, including within the UK, continue to struggle with the persistent challenge of delivering high-quality care amid constrained resources and escalating demand (Lowe et al., 2013). The literature identifies tensions surrounding the pursuit of efficient, effective, and economically sustainable healthcare provision amid prolonged financial austerity (Mantzoukas and Watkinson, 2007; Newhouse *et al.*, 2011). Within this landscape, the emergence and expansion of advanced practice roles reflect a strategic response to systemic pressures and evolving workforce needs.

The concept of advanced practice is generally considered to have originated in the US in the 1960s, focusing on paediatric roles in primary care due to the limited access to medical services (Ford, 1997; Pearson and Peels, 2002; Marsden *et al.*, 2003). Advanced practice was introduced to the UK early in the 1990s (Newhouse *et al.*, 2011; Lowe *et al.*, 2012), with Barbara Stilwell recognised as a pioneer for establishing the first advanced nursing practice programme at the Royal College of Nursing Institute in 1990 (Leary and MacLaine, 2019).

The advanced practice movement has been expanding in the UK for over 30 years, partly in response to longstanding issues in UK healthcare (Lewis, 2022). Hamric and Hanson (2003) suggest that nursing often evolves spontaneously to meet unmet healthcare needs, ‘filling the vacuum’ and taking on healthcare tasks to address gaps in patient care. As far back as 25 years ago, Barton *et al.*, (1999) also observed that advanced practice development was prompting significant discussion on the definitive nature and implications of this developing healthcare role. Morgan (2010) found that unclear role definitions, scope of practice issues, and the absence of title protection in the UK hindered progress in this area. While the current

landscape demonstrates positive outcomes for advanced practice, ongoing debate and considerable confusion persist about the advanced practice role and the misuse of the title (Nadaf, 2018; Mann *et al.*, 2023).

The drivers underpinning this evolution are multifaceted and interdependent. Shifting demographic profiles, rising public expectations, the proliferation of health information via digital platforms, and rapid technological and pharmacological innovation have collectively redefined the contours of healthcare delivery (Lowe *et al.*, 2013; Scottish Government, 2006; 2008; DOH, 2010; Currie and Grundy, 2011). These dynamics necessitate a workforce capable of agile adaptation, operational efficiency, and sustainable service transformation (Scottish Government, 2006; 2006a; 2007; 2017). In this context, advanced practice roles have been positioned, not as an extension of nursing practice, but to realise their potential for professional autonomy and enhanced clinical impact (Government of Health, N.I. 2001/2003; Scottish Government, 2017; Nuffield Trust, 2023; NMC, 2024).

In this context, advanced practice is considered a pathway for professional growth (Leary and MacLaine, 2019). Nevertheless, critics have raised concerns that advanced practice roles, particularly in high-pressure environments such as emergency departments, risk being seen as cost-saving substitutes for medical practitioners (Leary *et al.*, 2017; Leary and MacLaine, 2019). The role has been described as having developed in a disorganised manner both nationally and internationally, leading to confusion and a lack of role clarity (Lowe *et al.*, 2012; Jokiniemi *et al.*, 2012; Oxtoby, 2020). This highlights the potential for further erosion of role clarity and professional boundaries, especially where AP training is shaped by cost-efficiency savings and medically orientated curricula (Leary and MacLaine, 2019; Health Education England [HEE], 2017/2025; NMC, 2025).

2.2 What is advanced practice?

Over the past thirty years, the definition of advanced practice has evolved from role-based descriptions to frameworks emphasising competencies such as autonomy, complexity, and systemic influence. However, there remains ambiguity about the precise definition of advanced practice, leading to a wide range of practices and roles globally (Woods 1999; Ormande-Walsh and Newham 2001; Pearson and Peels 2002; Daly and Carnwell, 2003; Marsden *et al.*, 2003). Additionally, changing definitions and role titles now span multiple professional fields, all linked to regulatory, educational, and service improvement goals (HEE, 2017/2025; Royal College of Emergency Medicine [RECM], 2015; NMC, 2024). In 2010, Pulcini *et al.*, found, through a survey of 32 countries, that 13 titles were used under the advanced practice umbrella. More recently, Evans *et al.*, (2020), in a scoping review of papers describing outcomes, impacts, and challenges of implementing advanced practice roles in the UK, identified over 63 different titles across 169 research papers, further highlighting role confusion.

Advanced Paediatric Nurse Practitioners (APNPs) are advanced practice nurses with additional paediatric qualifications working within paediatric contexts. They are highly skilled professionals who can support the development of child health services, offering a skillset that extends beyond traditional nursing boundaries to address systemic gaps in healthcare delivery. Empirical evidence consistently demonstrates that APNPs can improve patient outcomes, achieve comparable or superior results to physicians, and foster high levels of patient satisfaction (Lambing *et al.*, 2004; Mundinger *et al.*, 2000; Newhouse *et al.*, 2011; Hyde *et al.*, 2020; Thibodeau *et al.*, 2022). These findings underscore the potential of advanced practice to mitigate workforce shortages and enhance service accessibility.

However, the expansion of advanced practice roles has not been without contention. Early critics warned that advanced practice risked becoming an alternative for junior medical posts, thereby undermining nursing's distinctive epistemological and patient-centred orientation (Manley, 1997; Bryant-Lukosius *et al.*, 2004; Evans *et al.*, 2020; Evans *et al.*, 2020a). This tension reflects a deeper professional struggle about whether advanced practice is genuinely transformative in meeting evolving patient and service needs, or whether it is subsumed into a medically dominated model of care (Manley, 1997; Bryant-Lukosius *et al.*, 2004; Lewis, 2022). Such concerns highlight the importance of safeguarding nursing's holistic ethos within advanced practice frameworks.

The literature identifies substantive benefits of APNPs in child health, including expedited diagnostics, anticipatory and preventative care, and family-centred approaches that align with contemporary policy imperatives (Jones, 2005; Barton *et al.*, 2012; Thompson *et al.*, 2016; Hyde *et al.*, 2020). These contributions resonate with government priorities to reduce health inequalities and improve child health outcomes (Scottish Government, 2006a; 2007). Nevertheless, the ad hoc evolution of advanced practice roles continues to generate uncertainty. The debate persists that, without strong regulatory frameworks, achieving role clarity and consistency will be hard. Even with regulation in place, cultural and organisational changes might take years to fully develop (Por, 2008; Wilkinson, 2008; Barton *et al.*, 2012; Mann *et al.*, 2023).

Other evidence also demonstrates broader improvements in patient care through improved access, reduced waiting times, and expanded outreach in underserved areas. The advanced practice role in chronic disease management is particularly well-documented, with studies reporting reductions in hospital admissions, readmissions, and lengths of stay (Bryant-Lukosius *et al.*, 2004; Gardner *et al.*, 2012; Hall, 2016; Fothergill *et al.*, 2022; Kilpatrick *et al.*, 2024). These outcomes suggest that advanced practitioners are not merely filling gaps but actively reshaping service delivery models.

2.3 Historical Context of Advanced Practice Policy and Frameworks

This section is structured around two distinct temporal frameworks. The first traces the historical trajectory of advanced practice up to 2015, culminating in the period during which I conducted the research interviews (2015–2016), before my studies were temporarily suspended. The second framework extends from 2016 to 2025, encompassing the phase following my return to study. Within this latter period, I critically examine developments in practice, policy, and prevailing trends in advanced practice through a systematic engagement with the literature. These insights are subsequently subjected to interpretive reflection through a Gadamerian hermeneutic lens, enabling a deeper exploration of continuity and transformation across the two timelines.

2.3.1 Advanced Practice Policy up until 2015

This section of the discussion situates advanced practice policy within the broader UK context, acknowledging the overarching developments articulated at the national level. However, the reality of devolved governance across the four nations necessitates recognition of the differentiated trajectories through which such policies were interpreted, operationalised, and enacted. While the policy frameworks signalled collective advancement in the conceptualisation of advanced practice, their translation into practice was contingent upon the political, professional, and organisational priorities specific to each devolved administration. Later in the chapter, an overview of the principal policy influences and substantive developments within England, Scotland, Wales, and Northern Ireland is provided, thereby illuminating both convergences and divergences in the evolution of advanced practice across the UK.

The evolution of advanced practice in the United Kingdom has been shaped by a series of policy milestones and professional debates that reflect both the ambition and ambiguity surrounding role expansion in nursing. A pivotal moment occurred in 1992 with the publication of the *Scope of Professional Practice* by the United Kingdom Central Council for Nursing, Midwifery and Health Visiting (UKCC, 1992). This document redefined the boundaries of nursing practice, shifting the focus from task-based limitations to competence-based autonomy. It empowered nurses to extend their roles contingent upon demonstrable competence, thereby foregrounding professional accountability and self-regulation (Rushforth and Singleton, 2004). This shift laid the groundwork for expanded responsibilities in prescribing, clinical decision-making, and leadership, domains traditionally reserved for medical practitioners.

In 1994, the UKCC formally introduced the concept of advanced practice, building upon its earlier 1992 framework. Rather than anchoring advanced practice to specific job titles, the UKCC defined it by the level of practice, emphasising autonomy, complexity, and boundary adjustment for future role development (UKCC, 1994). This conceptual shift acknowledged that many nurses were already functioning at advanced levels, albeit without formal recognition or regulatory clarity. While this marked a significant step toward legitimising advanced practice, regulation remained under the UKCC's auspices, and the absence of statutory protection continued to hinder standardisation of roles.

As advanced practice roles gained recognition by the mid-1990s, albeit in a fragmented manner, there was increasing concern about the regulatory vacuum surrounding these developing roles. Early discussions on scope of practice, accountability, and legitimacy were influenced by workforce shortages and role cost-effectiveness (Bryant-Lukosius *et al.*, 2004; Brooke and Rushforth, 2011). In 2002, Pearson and Peels highlighted the difficulty of gaining professional recognition without formal regulation, while Thompson and Watson (2003) criticised regulatory bodies for their reluctance to define advanced practice levels, noting the inconsistent, often ad hoc, nature of educational provision. Later, Leary and MacLaine (2019) reported the continuing lack of dedicated regulatory mechanisms to protect the public interest amid the proliferation of advanced practice titles, observing that little had changed. These critiques reflect a broader tension between innovation and oversight, a recurring theme in the development of advanced practice roles.

The Royal College of Nursing's (RCN) 1997 definition of the Nurse Practitioner further crystallised the emerging discourse around advanced roles. Describing the Nurse Practitioner as a clinician capable of autonomous decision-making, differential diagnosis, disease screening, and patient discharge, the RCN's articulation marked one of the earliest formal recognitions of advanced practice in the UK. However, its emphasis on undergraduate preparation reveals the emerging and somewhat limited conceptualisation of advanced practice at the time (RCN, 1997). This early framing arguably conflated extended roles with advanced practice, failing to distinguish between role complexity and educational depth (Bryant-Lukosius *et al.*, 2004).

By the 2000s, policy momentum had shifted towards formalising advanced practice through the expansion of prescribing rights and the development of competency frameworks. The Careers Framework for Health in 2006 (Skills for Health, 2006; updated 2012) represented a strategic effort to address workforce planning and career progression across the UK. The framework delineated nine levels of practice, stratified by complexity, responsibility, and knowledge. advanced practice roles were situated at level 7, denoting practitioners with highly specialised expertise, leadership capacity, and advanced decision-making skills. This alignment provided a structural reference point for advanced practice development, although its implementation varied across sectors and regions (Skills for Health, 2006; 2012).

Over time, the conceptualisation of Advanced Practice Nursing (APN) has undergone refinement, reflecting broader shifts in professional expectations, educational standards, and UK policy. A pivotal contribution to this debate came from the International Council of Nurses (ICN) in 2008, which defined the Advanced Practice Nurse as a registered nurse who, through graduate-level education, typically at least a master's degree, acquires expert knowledge, advanced clinical competencies, and complex decision-making capabilities shaped within the specific practice environment (ICN, 2008), by emphasising the contextual and regional variability inherent in advanced practice. This definition marked a departure from earlier, more limited interpretations, such as those offered by the Royal College of Nursing (RCN, 1997), by explicitly embedding postgraduate education as a requirement and expanding the scope of the role.

In addition, in 2008, both the Council for Healthcare Regulatory Excellence (CHRE, 2009) and the Nursing and Midwifery Council (NMC, 2008) undertook consultations to determine whether advanced practice warranted separate regulatory mechanisms. They concluded that there was no need for additional or separate regulation of advanced practice, reflecting the view that existing professional frameworks provided sufficient safeguards for public protection, accountability, and competence (NMC, 2008). This decision acknowledged that advanced practice was an extension of registered nursing practice rather than a distinct profession, thus avoiding regulatory fragmentation and maintaining coherence across the nursing profession (NMC, 2008; CHRE, 2009).

In 2010, the Department of Health issued a position statement that established a clear distinction between entry-level and advanced-level nursing. This pivotal development brought much-needed clarity and consistency to the definition of advanced practice, introducing a nationally recognised framework for evaluating roles, competencies, and career pathways, and integrating advanced practice into national workforce strategies. By positioning advanced practice as a higher standard within the nursing profession, the statement conferred validation and legitimacy upon these roles (DOH, 2010). Furthermore, it addressed longstanding ambiguities by embedding advanced practice within a structured career model, thereby enhancing both the credibility and sustainability of these roles across the UK. The Scottish Government's NMAHP Development Framework (NES, 2010) adopted a more detailed approach to career progression for nurses, midwives, and allied health professionals, utilising tools such as development needs analysis, reflective practice documentation, and benchmarking against knowledge, skills, and behaviours. This framework operationalised advanced practice through four interconnected pillars: Clinical Practice, Facilitating Learning, Leadership, and Evidence, Research and Development (NHS Education for Scotland (NES), 2008).

This multidimensional model emphasised the breadth of knowledge and professional agility required at level 7, reaffirming that advanced practice is not simply an extension of existing tasks, but rather a distinct and sophisticated mode of professional engagement. Throughout

the remainder of the 2010s, policy increasingly emphasised the integration of advanced practice roles into multidisciplinary teams and leadership structures, with a focus on care coordination and the development of more flexible workforce models across the UK. Nevertheless, challenges persisted, particularly regarding title protection, regulatory disparities, and the evolution of roles across professional boundaries.

2.3.2 Advanced Practice Policy 2016 – 2025 (current)

In 2016, the Scottish Government set out its Health and Social Care Delivery Plan, outlining Scotland's ambition to transform health and social care services so that people could live longer, healthier lives at home. Central to this vision was a stronger focus on prevention and self-management, and on accelerating day case treatment to minimise hospital stays (Scottish Government, 2016). Addressing rising health demands, demographic shifts, and persistent geographical health inequalities became an urgent priority. These challenges closely aligned with the evolving competencies and contributions of advanced practitioners, whose roles were increasingly designed to deliver anticipatory care, expedite diagnostics, and provide holistic, person-centred support for patients and families. By shifting the focus of care into community and primary care settings, the plan required practitioners to have the autonomy and expertise to manage complex cases independently.

Compelling evidence demonstrated that advanced practitioners improved access to care, reduced admissions, shortened hospital stays, ensured continuity of care, and ultimately enhanced patient satisfaction. In recognition of these contributions, the Scottish Government allocated funding to train an additional 500 advanced practitioners over three years, in partnership with several universities (SEND, 2017).

In 2017, Scottish policy was notably shaped by the introduction of the Transforming Roles agenda (Scottish Government, 2017), which initially set out a series of briefing papers articulating the broader transformational change required across health and social care in Scotland. This agenda called for innovative models of care to meet evolving service needs. The inaugural policy on Transforming Nursing Roles, introduced in the same year, established a strategic framework for national policy development (Scottish Government, 2017). Through this agenda, between 2017 – 2021, eight papers were produced that provided Scotland with strategic oversight and clear direction for the ongoing transformation of the roles of nursing, midwifery, and allied health professions (NMAHP), as well as the development of progressive career pathways (Scottish Government, 2017; Scottish Government 2021). These efforts are closely aligned with the NES Post-registration Career Development Framework (2018, 2024), ensuring a cohesive, future-focused approach to workforce development.

In 2017, Health Education England (HEE) released a multiprofessional framework for advanced clinical practice in England, introducing the term 'Advanced Clinical

Practitioner' (ACP). This framework describes advanced practice as a practice level marked by autonomy, complex decision-making, and expertise across four key areas: clinical practice, leadership and management, education, and research. Based on a master's level qualification or equivalent, it clarified the skills expected of advanced practitioners and outlined principles for role implementation, including workforce planning, supporting practitioners and employers, accountability standards, and pathways for professional development. There is limited guidance on how to implement these within current resource limitations. Other ongoing challenges include role confusion, lack of standardisation, inconsistent organisational support, unclear career pathways, and difficulties in balancing the four pillars of advanced practice. These issues are compounded by regional variations and interpretations, which suggest that the framework may be more aspirational than practically achievable (HEE, 2017; Fothergill *et al.*, 2022).

During the early 2020s, the COVID-19 pandemic served as a catalyst for the recognition of advanced practitioners, elevating their leadership in rapidly driving innovation to meet evolving healthcare demands (Ziegler *et al.*, 2024). Advanced practitioners played a pivotal role in spearheading the rapid development and implementation of telehealth and digital health solutions, reshaping care models, and providing essential education, mentorship, and mental health support to colleagues.

In the lead-up to 2024, following extensive professional debate, the Nursing and Midwifery Council (NMC) commissioned the Nuffield Trust (2023) to produce an independent report on advanced practice, offering recommendations for its future development (NMC, 2024). In response, the NMC introduced a definition of advanced practice designed to clarify the role for the public and to establish standards of best practice that employers can implement to safeguard the public and ensure safe, effective care (NMC, 2024).

The most recent NMC guidance (2025) marks a significant conceptual shift. Advanced practice is now defined as a distinct level of professional practice to be attained through formal postgraduate education rather than solely through experiential accumulation. This new definition aligns closely with Health Education England's (HEE) 2017 framework, positioning advanced practice as a level of practice rather than a job title, and reaffirming the four pillars: clinical practice, leadership, education, and research as foundational. The guidance emphasises the necessity of postgraduate education and the ability to manage uncertainty and risk in complex clinical environments (NMC, 2025).

This broader framework moves beyond clinical expertise alone, supporting professional identity and consistency across nursing, midwifery, and allied health professions (HEE, 2017). Once implemented, regulation is expected to reinforce the identity of advanced practitioners and align them with wider healthcare standards. However, the framework currently offers limited guidance on operationalising these principles within resource-constrained organisations, and there is already evidence of variation in implementation across England.

Table 1: A Conceptual Map of Advanced Practice Policy Milestones

Period	Key Policy Milestones	Drivers and context	Implications
Mid 1990's	Early recognition of Advanced practice roles – NPs, CNSs, ANPs. Initial debates around Scope of Practice and Regulation	Workforce shortages Need for cost-effective care Changing professional boundaries	Fragmentation of Policy frameworks across UK Uneven role adoption across regions
2000's	Formalisation of advanced practice competencies and standards Development of NES Toolkits and NHMAP	Patient safety and access concern Regulatory harmonization efforts	Greater legitimacy of advanced practice Enhanced autonomy in clinical decision-making
2010's	Consolidation of advanced practice into national workforce strategies Emphasis shifting away from nursing to multidisciplinary integration More development of postgraduate education pathways to support role development	Concentration on ageing populations and chronic disease burden Health system reforms to reflect shift in policy	Advanced practice roles being embedded in service redesign Policy endorsement of advanced practice as a workforce solution
2020's	Focus on advanced practice leadership and governance Innovations such as digital and telehealth integration into services Global policy convergence on advanced practice regulation	COVID 19 pandemic pressures Equity and access agendas International collaboration	Advanced practice framed as essential to innovation and workforce resilience Ongoing debates on consistency of regulation and title protection Future trajectories – regulation NMC in 2029.

The policy context, summarised in Table 2 below, outlines the specific Policy context that has evolved and influenced AP within the UK 1990 – 2025, and as discussed during the period covered by this study.

Table 2: All Policy Context within Scotland and the UK

Year	Policy	Comment/rationale
1992	Scope of Professional Practice Document published	UKCC as nurses professional regulator at time.
1994	Concept of Advanced Practice first defined in UK	By UKCC
1997	RCN published definition of an Advanced Nurse Practitioner	Key milestone in defining AP role

2006/2012	Skills for Health	Career framework for health – positioning of AP roles. Updated 2012.
2008	ICN definition of Advanced Practice Nurse	Key milestone in defining APPN
2008	Scotland’s advanced practice toolkit (NES)	Outline level of practice, NMAHP development framework, 4 pillars of practice and Developmental needs assessment toolkit (DNAT)
2008	Council for healthcare regulatory excellence	Is advanced practice a regulatory issue – report to 4 UK health departments – No change to AP
2010	Advanced level nursing: A position statement	Benchmarking – recognition of 2 levels of nursing practice – entry level and advanced level
2010	Framework for advanced nursing, midwifery & allied health professional practice in Wales	Reviewed 2012
2010	CEL 42 National uniform policy	Direction set for wearing of uniform – cornflower blue (same as staff nurses) – implemented 2012
2014	Setting the direction	CNO review of education
2014	Advanced nursing practice framework – Northern Ireland	
2016	Scottish Government Vision for health and social care integration (Scottish Government Health & Social Care Delivery Plan, December, 2016)	National clinical strategy for sustainable health services over next 10-20 years which lead to funding & training of 500 extra ACPs in Scotland over 3 years. Identified metrics (Safe, effective & Person centred) should be aligned to the Nursing Assurance Framework: Excellence in Care (2015/updated 2022)
2018	Multi-professional framework for advanced practice in England published and coined the term ‘Advanced Clinical Practitioner’	HEE milestone for England
2017	Credentialing introduced by RCN	Key milestone by RCN to try and introduce some form of standardisation for AP and education
2017 - 2021	Scottish Government (SEND) - Transforming nursing roles Papers 1 - 8	2017 Paper 1 focus on AP & Paper 2 (Transforming roles programme) 2021 Advanced nursing practice (Phase 2) 2021 CNS and NP
2017 - 2018	Introduction of advanced practice academies in Scotland	West 2017

		East & North Scotland 2018 to provide support and information across Scotland
2019	The NHS Long Term Plan	A 10 year strategic plan for NHS England to improve patient care and health outcomes, and integrate care more effectively.
2023	RCN Advanced practice standards	
2023	Nuffield Trust – Independent report on the regulation of advanced practice in nursing and midwifery	
2023	NMC independent report on the regulation of advanced practice	Regulatory implications with consultation ongoing
2024	NES Post registration framework	Builds on previous skills for health, levels 5 – 8 practice, 4 pillars of practice, SCQF framework
2023/4	NMC Review of advanced practice options appraisal	Range of regulatory options mapped and consultation ongoing

2.2.3 Global Advanced Practice

The global proliferation of advanced practice roles represents a shift in healthcare workforce development in the 21st century. These roles, particularly for advanced practice nurses have emerged as strategic responses to escalating healthcare demands, physician shortages, and systemic inequities in access to care. Empirical evidence increasingly affirms the capacity of advanced practitioners to deliver high-quality, cost-effective services, particularly in underserved, rural, and complex care environments (Miller *et al.*, 2024; Thomas *et al.*, 2025).

The US and Canada have traditionally been at the forefront of developing advanced practice roles. Since the 1960s, Nurse Practitioners have played a vital role in primary, acute, and speciality care, with numerous states granting them full practice authority. In parallel, Canada’s provincial regulatory frameworks similarly support the integration of Nurse Practitioners and Clinical Nurse Specialists across diverse healthcare settings (Miller *et al.*, 2024). These jurisdictions exemplify mature advanced practice systems characterised by statutory regulation, postgraduate education, and policy alignment.

In contrast, European implementation is marked by heterogeneity. Countries such as Ireland, the Netherlands, and Scandinavian nations have established advanced practice roles, yet regulatory protections and title protections remain inconsistent. While the European Union encourages cross-border recognition of qualifications, full harmonisation is impeded by national-level regulatory divergence (Mackavey *et al.*, 2024).

Australia and New Zealand offer well-established advanced practice integration, underpinned by national regulation and structured postgraduate pathways. Conversely, countries like Japan, South Korea, and China are in earlier stages of advanced practice role development, driven by demographic challenges and rural healthcare disparities. These systems face challenges in establishing regulatory and educational infrastructure (Miller *et al.*, 2024).

In South America, advanced practice roles are emergent, often supported by international collaborations and pilot initiatives. South Africa has piloted advanced practice roles in primary care, while Brazil and Chile are exploring advanced nursing education and practice. However, regulatory fragmentation and limited educational capacity constrain scalability (Miller *et al.*, 2024).

2.2.3.1 Global Regulation and Governance

Globally, a master's degree is increasingly recognised as the minimum educational threshold for advanced practice roles. Many countries have adopted competency frameworks aligned with the International Council of Nurses (ICN) guidelines (2020). Regulatory approaches vary widely, from comprehensive statutory oversight [i.e. US, Canada] to employer-led credentialing systems. The presence of clear role definitions, title protection, and regulatory oversight is positively correlated with enhanced role clarity, system integration and public trust (Kilpatrick *et al.*, 2021; Maier, 2015; Heale and Reike Buckley, 2015).

A growing body of research demonstrates that APNs significantly improve clinical and systemic contributions to patient outcomes (Kilpatrick *et al.*, 2021; Miller *et al.*, 2024). These include reduced hospital admissions, enhanced access to care, particularly in chronic disease management, care coordination, and service delivery to vulnerable populations. Their impact is especially pronounced in health systems with physician shortages or rural disparities (Kilpatrick *et al.*, 2021; Miller *et al.*, 2024).

2.2.3.2. Global Future Directions

Despite global momentum, several structural and policy challenges persist. Many countries, including the UK, lack standardised role definitions and protections for advanced practice titles, leading to ambiguity and role dilution (Mackavey *et al.*, 2024). Regulatory fragmentation and differing credentialing standards hinder role development, international mobility and professional recognition. As advanced practice expands beyond nursing into other disciplines, the absence of interprofessional regulatory coherence becomes increasingly problematic. Structural barriers also limit the influence of advanced practice in health policy and leadership domains (Miller *et al.*, 2024). Future policy trajectories must prioritise harmonising regulatory standards, expanding AP roles across professional boundaries, and elevating advanced practitioners into leadership and system redesign roles (Miller *et al.*,

2024). These efforts are essential to ensure the transformative potential of advanced practice in addressing global health challenges.

The global expansion of advanced practice illustrates a flexible, evolving approach to addressing health system challenges. Despite differing models, the core principles of advanced practice are increasingly viewed as essential to modern healthcare. Continued investment in education, regulation, and policy will be vital to sustain and expand these roles worldwide.

Having considered the global context of advanced practice, it is now important to examine how advanced practice policy has developed across the four nations of Wales, England, Ireland, and Scotland.

2.2.4 Advanced Practice Policy within the rest of the United Kingdom

In the UK, advanced practice development has been shaped by the broader tensions between national coherence and devolved autonomy in health policy. Unlike advanced practice models seen in other countries, the UK's landscape is shaped by distinct priorities, governance structures, and the health system configurations of its four nations: Wales, England, Northern Ireland and Scotland (Department of Health - Wales, 2010; Department of Health - Ireland, 2014; Scottish Government, 2017; HEE, 2017). This fragmentation has produced differing frameworks that, while sharing foundational principles, diverge in implementation, regulatory emphasis, and strategic integration (Department of Health - Wales, 2010; Department of Health – N.I. 2014 HEE, 2017).

2.2.4.1 Scotland's Policy Framework

With Scotland very much at the forefront of advanced practice development in the UK, the trajectory of advanced practice policy reflects a dynamic interaction between professional aspirations, regulatory frameworks, and systemic pressures within healthcare. Originating in Scotland, various initiatives supported by succession planning frameworks (Currie and Grundy, 2011) and the Transforming Roles agenda (Scottish Government, 2017) demonstrate how government investment, organisational infrastructure, and educational innovation can underpin advanced practice.

The Scottish Government's early key priorities for child health focused on building capacity and capability to address the shortage of skilled senior and middle-ranking paediatric medical staff within the Scottish National Health Service (Scottish Government, 2006; Scottish Government, 2006a; Scottish Government, 2007; Scottish Government, 2008). Significant changes to how the medical workforce are prepared for practice and the European working time directive reducing junior doctors' working hours have influenced service delivery

(Scottish Government, 2009), opening doors to innovative development opportunities and serving as one of the original reasons for the push to implement advanced roles within Scotland to fill this gap (Scottish Government, 2006a; Scottish Government, 2011; SEND, 2016).

Policy drivers had led to a reduction in the healthcare workforce, including staff in medical, nursing, and allied health professions (Scottish Government, 2006a; Scottish Government, 2007; Scottish Government, 2009; Department of Health, 2008). The decrease in junior doctors' hours required significant changes in service delivery (Scottish Government, 2007; Wilkinson, 2008a). An increase in service user involvement raised expectations for better choice, accessibility, and service quality (Scottish Government, 2006; Scottish Government, 2007). Recognition of the evolving patterns of care for children and their families, along with the growing complexity of care needs, underscored the necessity for service redesign and role development (Scottish Government, 2006; Scottish Government, 2007).

Current Scottish policy presents opportunities and challenges for the development of advanced practice roles in rapidly evolving environments (Por, 2008). However, policy drivers often overlook the limited evidence supporting the value of some roles, especially when their implementation is inconsistent, leading to accusations of reactive policy making (Wilkinson, 2008). Policy must be viewed within the political climate, which often involves hidden agendas. It is politically motivated, with promises of a better healthcare system that raise public expectations. Changes in political parties can influence services, and roles are adjusted to align with different government strategies (Barton *et al.*, 2012). Consequently, advanced practice exemplifies a vulnerable form of sustainable development without a robust supporting evidence base.

Scottish policy has been supported and guided by the introduction of the Transforming Roles agenda (Scottish Government, 2017). The first policy on Transforming Nursing Roles was introduced in 2017 (Scottish Government, 2017) and sets the framework for current policy development in Scotland, providing strategic oversight and evolving direction for transforming nursing, midwifery, and allied health professions (NMAHP) roles within the health and social care system. The aim of Transforming Roles (Scottish Government, 2017; Scottish Government, 2021) is to ensure a consistent, nationally adopted, and sustainable approach that supports career pathways and clarity around levels of practice within Scotland. To date, eight reports have been published, with Papers 1 and 2 (Scottish Government, 2017 & 2017a, Paper 7 (Scottish Government, 2021), and Paper 8 (Scottish Government, 2021a) being the most significant for advanced practice. Core area-specific competencies have been identified as an addendum to the initial papers, outlining the vision for advanced practice in Scotland. The latest paper clarifies the roles of the CNS and nurse practitioner to differentiate them clearly. This work focuses on developing the research base for measuring outcomes, discussing supervision, and establishing three advanced practice academies across Scotland

to support education, practitioners, and the dissemination of information across all professions (NES 2017-2018; Scottish Government, 2021a).

Here, Table 3 outlines the Transforming Roles Policy Agenda Papers between 2017 and 2021 and identifies the focus for each individual Policy. Papers 1,2,7, and 8 are the main drivers for advanced practice roles referred to in this thesis.

Table 3: Transforming Roles Policy

Paper	Title	Year and Focus
1	Transforming Nursing, Midwifery and Health Professions Roles: Introduction	2017 Sets out the overall vision for transforming nursing, midwifery, and allied health professional roles in Scotland.
2	Transforming Nursing, Midwifery and Health Professions Roles: Advanced Nursing Practice	2017 Defines advanced practice, outlines core competencies, and provides a framework for implementation across NHS Scotland.
3	Transforming Nursing, Midwifery and Health Professions Roles: The District Nursing Role in Integrated Community Nursing Teams	2017 Clarifies the evolving role of district nurses in community-based, integrated care models.
4	Transforming Nursing, Midwifery and Health Professions Roles: The School Nursing Role in Integrated Community Nursing Teams	2018 Establishes the scope of school nursing, focusing on public health, prevention, and child wellbeing.
5	Transforming Nursing, Midwifery and Health Professions Roles: Education and Career Development	2018 Provides pathways for education, training, and career progression to support role transformation.
6	Transforming Nursing, Midwifery and Health Professions Roles: Developing the General Practice Nursing Role in Integrated Community Nursing Teams	2018 Defines the role of general practice nurses, emphasising multidisciplinary working and patient-centred care.
7	Transforming Nursing Roles: Advanced Nursing Practice – Phase II	2021 Builds on Paper 2, refining advanced practice frameworks and addressing implementation challenges.
8	Transforming Nursing, Midwifery and Health Professions Roles: Review of Clinical Nurse Specialist and Nurse Practitioner Roles within Scotland	2021 Reviews specialist and practitioner roles, aligning them with advanced practice standards and workforce needs.

Advanced practice roles should be evidence-based and aim to achieve the best outcomes for children and their families (Thompson *et al.*, 2016; Winter *et al.*, 2021; Thibodeau *et al.*, 2022). The expansion of practice should not be driven solely by the need to replace medical care, even if this appears necessary, as Wilkinson (2008) suggests. Healthcare professionals must uphold their professional integrity and generate evidence to support the development of such roles. Wilkinson (2008) strongly argues that there is currently limited evidence demonstrating the impact, effectiveness, and value of nurse practitioners within the health service. This is not an isolated stance, and more recently, the Scottish Government has acknowledged through the Transforming Roles agenda (Scottish Government, 2021; Scottish Government 2021a), the need for more evidence on the value of advanced practice roles. However, some critics argue that the existing evidence already demonstrates that Advanced practitioners are effective and efficient in many areas (Kilpatrick *et al.*, 2013; Evans *et al.*, 2020a; Fothergill *et al.*, 2022; Britton and Blackwood, 2023). There are, however, still gaps in the literature surrounding people's understanding and meaning of advanced practice from different perspectives (Kilpatrick *et al.*, 2024).

2.2.4.2 England's Policy Framework

England's trajectory has been marked by initial inconsistency and conceptual ambiguity. Before 2017, advanced practice development lacked unified standards, resulting in disparate interpretations of advanced practice across sectors and employers. However, in 2017, a multi-professional framework (HEE, 2017) was published, representing guidance for role development and establishing the four pillars of advanced practice and promoting cross-disciplinary applicability (HEE, 2017). The introduction of apprenticeship schemes for trainee Advanced Clinical Practitioners (ACPs) further reflected England's commitment to widening access and embedding advanced practice roles within workforce planning. However, these apprenticeship schemes do not come without criticism, as the assessments differ from a standard MSc degree pathway, and introduce more opportunity for inequity between advanced practice students, with additional assessment processes required (Evans *et al.*, 2020; Fothergill *et al.*, 2022).

The HEE 2017 report was revised in 2025 (HEE, 2025) and further informed by stakeholder feedback, with the report harmonised with frameworks from the other UK nations. The updated report enhances clarity; its decision to retain the original framework's core purpose may be viewed as conservative, potentially missing an opportunity for more transformative reform. It is currently early days, but the persistence of employer-led variation in role interpretation and support continues to offer challenges in the coherence of advanced practice implementation in England.

The NHS Long Term Plan (NHS England, 2019) highlights the vital role of advanced practice roles in workforce transformation, service delivery, and the addressing of local health needs.

This plan aims to expand AP roles to boost capacity, productivity, and efficiency by integrating advanced practitioners into multidisciplinary teams and networks, ultimately improving patient care. It is supported by the HEE (2017) framework above. The NHS Long Term Plan (NHS England, 2019) set out a ten-year strategy to enhance care across six key areas in England: preventing illness, improving cancer services, advancing digital technology, expanding mental health support, shifting care focus to out-of-hospital settings, and increasing the number of community rapid response teams to reduce unnecessary hospital admissions with many of these services being enhanced through the development of AP roles (NHS England, 2019).

2.2.4.3 Wales Policy Framework

Wales was among the first UK nations to formalise advanced practice roles through its 2010 Framework for advanced nursing, midwifery, and allied health professional practice (Department of Health, Wales, 2010; NLIAH [National Leadership and Innovation Agency for Healthcare], 2010). Drawing on the principles from Scotland's 2008 Advanced Practice Toolkit for nursing (NES, 2008), retaining the four domains of advanced practice, while adapting them to its own workforce and policy context. The framework was mapped against the Knowledge and Skills Framework (Skills for Health, 2006), aligning these to local employer agreements, reflecting a pragmatic approach to integration within existing structures.

Critically, while local guidance identified holding a master's degree as the preferred qualification for advanced practice, this was framed as 'desirable' rather than mandatory, suggesting a tension between aspirational professionalisation and workforce pragmatism. Since then, guidance has been revised to offer clarity through a Professional Framework for Enhanced, Advanced, and Consulting Clinical Practice in Wales (Health Education and Improvement, Wales, 2023), which introduced a more pronounced stratification of practice levels – Enhanced, Advanced, and Consulting, which suggests a shift towards more precise role delineation and progression pathways. However, reliance on health boards operationalising support introduced variability and inequity in implementation, raising concerns about the consistency of approach and accountability across the country.

2.2.4.4 Northern Ireland Policy Framework

Northern Ireland developed its own advanced nursing practice framework in 2014 (Department of Health, N.I., 2014), which closely aligns with those of other UK nations. It also adopted the four pillars, although with minor terminological differences. What distinguishes Northern Ireland is its strategic embedding of advanced practice roles within broader health reform efforts, which emphasise universal, integrated care. This policy alignment has enabled advanced practice roles to evolve and become integral to services for chronic disease

management, elderly care, and community-based care in particular, areas of high system demand and strategic priority.

The framework's emphasis on leadership and collaborative practice reflects a deliberate effort to position advanced practitioners not only as clinical experts but also as transformative agents. Further expansion of advanced practice is anticipated, especially in primary care, mental health, and digital health specialisms (Department of Health, N.I., 2018). However, the success of expansion will depend on sustained investment in education, regulatory support, and interprofessional collaboration.

2.2.4.5 Summary of Policy Context

The United Kingdom's devolved approach to the development of advanced practice presents both significant opportunities and notable challenges. While regional autonomy enables tailored frameworks to address local health needs and policy priorities, the absence of a unified regulatory system risks ongoing fragmentation, role ambiguity, and inequitable access to advanced practice career pathways (Nuffield Trust, 2023; NMC, 2024).

The adoption of the four pillars across all nations suggests consensus, yet their operationalisation varies significantly. Wales and Northern Ireland had demonstrated greater alignment with workforce planning and service reform, while England's modelling remains more employer-driven and variable in practice (Evans *et al.*, 2020). Scotland's Transforming Roles agenda (Scottish Government, 2017) adopts a national approach to better align with workforce and service reform. The ongoing absence of statutory protection for advanced practice titles further worsens role confusion and weakens professional identity. A comparative analysis across the UK nations shows that policy consistency, regulatory transparency, and strategic alignment are vital to unlocking the full potential of advanced practice (Nuffield Trust, 2023; NMC, 2024).

The concept of the four pillars of advanced practice forms the cornerstone of advanced practitioner roles in the United Kingdom, providing a comprehensive framework that defines the breadth and depth of expertise required for advanced clinical practice. UK policy frameworks articulate the strategic vision for advanced practice, emphasising workforce transformation, patient-centred care, and sustainability (DOH, Wales, 2010; Department of Health, N.I., 2018; Scottish Government, 2017; HEE, 2018). However, realising these ambitions necessitates a structured mechanism for implementation. The four pillars of clinical practice, leadership, education, and research, represent the operational domains through which policy goals are converted into professional practice. Each pillar is aligned with policy drivers, ensuring that advanced practice is more than just a theoretical idea; it becomes an integral part of daily healthcare delivery.

2.2.5 The Four Pillars of Advanced Practice

The concept of the four pillars of advanced practice was first introduced in the UK in 1997, building on and expanding Hamric's earlier work on the role of the clinical nurse specialist (Hamric and Sprouse, 1989), in which these four elements of practice were first discussed. The four pillars of advanced practice are now integral to advanced practice education and are embedded as a key component of advanced practice roles across the UK (Manley, 1997). These four pillars: clinical practice, research, education, and leadership are crucial for advanced practitioners and are underpinned by the skills and capabilities required for the role (NES, 2008, HEE, 2017, Scottish Government, 2017, Scottish Government, 2021).

The RCN initially adopted and integrated these four pillars into its professional development frameworks, aligning them with levels of nursing practice [enhanced, advanced, consultant] to maintain consistency across diverse roles and settings (RCN, 2018) building on previous work undertaken by Hamric and Sprouse (1989) and Manley (1997) which identified the four pillars meaning that advanced practice roles were no longer just a response to workforce needs but were now grounded in scholarly models rooted in professional knowledge and inquiry (Manley, 1997; NES 2008; HEE 2017; Scottish Government 2017, 2021; NMC, 2024). In 2008, NES introduced the advanced practice toolkit, which was subsequently incorporated into workforce planning to support Scotland's developing standards for advanced practitioners (NES, 2008). By 2018, HEE had adopted the four pillars into its Multiprofessional Framework for Advanced Clinical Practice (HEE, 2018), ensuring that all practitioners in England are assessed against the same core competencies.

These four pillars form the basis of advanced practice nursing roles, which are developed and recognised within modern healthcare systems. Each pillar not only defines a specific area of professional competence but also reflects and implements national policy goals aimed at improving the quality, accessibility, and sustainability of healthcare services (Thomas *et al.*, 2025).

Clinical practice is the foundation of advanced practice, demanding that practitioners provide expert, autonomous care to a wide range of complex patient groups. Their ability to make independent decisions and apply advanced clinical reasoning aligns with national policies aimed at decreasing hospital admissions, enhancing access to timely treatments, and maintaining safe, high-quality care. In this context, advanced practitioners support the policy goal of bringing care closer to home and reducing stress on acute healthcare services (Mann *et al.*, 2023; MacKavey *et al.*, 2024).

The leadership pillar positions advanced practitioners as catalysts for organisational change, enabling them to influence service redesign, contribute to governance, and lead multidisciplinary teams (Thomas *et al.*, 2025). These roles align with national strategies to promote integrated care systems and workforce transformation, ensuring services are both

efficient and patient-centred. Thus, leadership in advanced practice serves as a means to translate policy goals for collaborative, system-wide reform into action at the clinical level (MacKavey *et al.*, 2024).

Education, as an additional pillar, highlights the importance of advanced practitioners in promoting a culture of lifelong learning. By supporting the development of colleagues, students, and patients, advanced practitioners help disseminate knowledge and improve professional skills across the workforce (Mann *et al.*, 2023; MacKavey *et al.*, 2024). This aligns with national strategies on continuous professional development (CPD) and the growth of advanced roles within the NHS, ensuring that the workforce remains flexible, resilient, and able to meet changing healthcare needs (Thomas *et al.*, 2024).

Finally, the research pillar views advanced practitioners as both users and creators of evidence, developing and applying knowledge to enhance patient outcomes and service quality. This aligns with national policies that prioritise integrating evidence-based decision-making into routine practice and promoting population health through research-driven improvements (Thomas *et al.*, 2025). By embedding research into daily practice, advanced practitioners support the wider policy goals of fostering innovation, improving clinical effectiveness, and reducing health disparities (Mann *et al.*, 2023; MacKavey *et al.*, 2024).

Finally, the historical context of advanced practice situates the four pillars within broader debates about professional autonomy, workforce transformation, and evidence-based healthcare. It reflects the profession's response to systemic challenges, that of rising healthcare demand, resource constraints, and the provision of cost-effective and efficient care (DOH, 2010; ICN, 2020). The four pillars support the shift toward a holistic, scholarly, and leadership-oriented identity (HEE, 2017; Scottish Government, 2021).

Together, the four pillars of advanced practice: clinical practice, leadership, education, and research, demonstrate how UK policy ambitions are translated into tangible professional domains and serve as a structural bridge between professional practice and national policy. Each pillar aligns with national policy and directives, ensuring that advanced practice is not merely a theoretical construct but a structured framework embedded in everyday healthcare delivery. By operationalising policy priorities through these domains, advanced practitioners contribute to workforce sustainability, service transformation, and evidence-based improvement. Yet, the relationship between policy and practice is not without tension; regional variation, resource constraints, and differing interpretations of the pillars highlight the complexity of implementation.

2.2.6 Education and Training

Educational standards and preparation vary across the UK and globally, with programmes being independently validated within higher education institutions (Griffin and Melby, 2006; Heale and Rieck Buckley, 2015; Kuczawki *et al.*, 2024). This is directly related to criticism of the NMC's lack of professional regulation (Brooke and Rushforth, 2011; MacKavey *et al.*, 2024). Consequently, a broad range of advanced practice courses, qualifications, and expectations for preparing for the advanced practice role has existed, leading to further criticism from some employers about variations in standards and practitioners' knowledge (Hill and Mitchell, 2021; Mann *et al.*, 2023). More countries are now recognising minimum standards, and preparation for this role, with most aligning with Master's level education, given the skills and knowledge needed for such a complex role.

In the UK, although the four countries' Health Departments agree with recommendations stating that Master's level education is desirable (RCN, 2012; ICN, 2020; NMC, 2024), this is not yet universally implemented (Pulcini *et al.*, 2010; Scottish Government, 2017; HEE, 2018; NMC, 2018; and RCN, 2018). Currently, in Scotland, demonstrating Master's level study is a requirement for a post, but completing a full Master's degree is not yet mandatory, with a postgraduate certificate being the minimum standard for employment in an advanced practice role (NES, 2012; Scottish Government, 2017). For example, a UK survey in 2011 found that fewer than one-third of advanced practitioners held a full Master's degree (Gerrish *et al.*, 2011). A later study (Fothergill *et al.*, 2022) demonstrated that most advanced practitioners were trained to at least degree level, with 56% trained to a Master's level, although the subjects studied varied significantly. This highlights ongoing criticism of variation in qualification standards among practitioners in different clinical roles and regions.

After setting the policy context, outlining the Four Pillars of Advanced Practice, and identifying the educational needs for advanced practitioners, it is essential to review the regulatory mechanisms that maintain professional standards. Regulation provides the formal frameworks that define, legitimise, and oversee advanced practice, ensuring it aligns with national policy objectives, protects the public, and maintains the integrity of the nursing profession.

2.2.7 The Regulation of Advanced Practice

There has been extensive debate and a broad consensus that regulating advanced practice is necessary to establish a more consistent, systematic approach for defining these roles and supporting coherent development, thereby reducing confusion around the role (Leary and MacLaine, 2019). It has been noted that advanced practice roles in the UK are not regulated

separately, raising concerns about public safety (Lewis, 2022). However, plans with the NMC aim to change this by 2029 (Nuffield Trust, 2023; NMC, 2024).

The previous lack of specific regulation for advanced practice was due to the nursing profession being overseen by the NMC, which has traditionally been seen as sufficient in defining nursing roles and protecting the public. The NMC holds various regulatory and statutory powers (Thomas *et al.*, 2025), enabling it to set professional standards, regulate education, maintain a register of qualified nurses, and investigate fitness-to-practise issues. Nurses are governed by standards outlined in The Code of Conduct (NMC, 2018), which is regularly updated. All registered nurses must adhere to this Code to maintain their practice and demonstrate their competence through revalidation.

Due to the lack of statutory regulation for advanced practice, voluntary regulation began to develop across the UK. From 2008, advanced practice frameworks showed disparities in approaches among the four UK nations (Thomas *et al.*, 2025). Educational standards differed by country and employer, with employers able to appoint individuals without ensuring they possessed specific qualifications, competencies, or experience. Brook and Rushforth (2011) were among the first to call for a regulatory framework for nurse practitioners, aiming to standardise education and clinical practice to safeguard public safety (Gardner *et al.*, 2012).

A 2009 report by the Council for Healthcare Regulatory Excellence (CHRE, 2009), in collaboration with the NMC (2010), argued against introducing national regulation for advanced practice, viewing these evolving roles as extensions of skills beyond those assessed at initial registration. Additionally, within the UK, the NMC (2005) regarded advanced practice as consistent with Benner's (1982) concept of the novice to expert trajectory and believed that the risks associated with advanced practice are minimal, as advanced practitioners possess expertise and operate within the NMC scope of practice. Since then, roles have evolved, and some argue that advanced practice roles often cross professional boundaries due to their autonomous, complex clinical decision-making, diagnosis, and treatment responsibilities. This challenges the notion that regulation is unnecessary, especially when prioritising public safety (Brook and Rushforth, 2011; Mann *et al.*, 2023).

As formal regulation of advanced practice had not changed, the Royal College of Nursing introduced one of the earliest forms of voluntary regulation (RCN, 2012). The RCN established a credentialing process for educational institutions to assure practitioners and the public that the education programmes offered equitable opportunities for advanced practice knowledge and skill development, which many considered essential (Thompson and Watson, 2003; Brook and Rushforth, 2011). The RCN (2012) set standards and competencies that institutions adhered to, meaning that graduates from those institutions received an additional RCN certificate at the end of their course, recognising their experience, skills, and qualifications, and signifying the quality of their training. Nevertheless, an informal scoping exercise across

the UK revealed that only a few HEIs used this process because it was costly for institutions to obtain accreditation and for individual students who also had to pay a fee. In Scotland, competency frameworks were addressed through regional discussions as part of the Transforming Nursing Roles initiative (Scottish Government, 2017). Some of these competencies are currently being incorporated into practice, alongside ongoing efforts to establish a national approach to advanced practice (Scottish Government, 2017)

2.2.8. Summary of first part of chapter

This first part of the chapter has critically discussed the evolving advanced practice role from global, UK, and Scottish perspectives.

The complexity behind developing diverse advanced practice roles must be recognised. Ketefian *et al.*, (2001) highlight essential factors which impact on the development of advanced practice roles, such as the socio-political environment, societal health needs, workforce availability, supply and demand, government policy, interprofessional collaboration, and nursing education, and this continues to be the case (Thomas *et al.*, 2025). Lewis (2022) also identified alternative factors which impact upon role development through a sociological lens, and links the challenges and opportunities for advancement of advanced nursing practice to gender (more women, who often take on caring roles), identity (social expectations and control over women, and the social capital where medicine typically holds more value than nursing), power (the dominance of medicine in healthcare), and patriarchy (where medicine's cultural authority and societal value reinforce its dominance).

The evolution of advanced practice (AP) in the UK reflects a growing professionalisation, marked by increased regulatory attention, academic rigour, and alignment with health system priorities. While various frameworks have contributed to the conceptual and structural development of advanced practice in the UK, ongoing challenges persist. Frameworks from Health Education England (HEE, 2017) and the Nursing and Midwifery Council (NMC, 2024) have helped define advanced practice as a level of practice characterised by autonomy, complex decision-making, and postgraduate education, rather than a job title. The adoption of the four pillars (clinical practice, leadership, education, and research) has provided clear structural coherence (HEE, 2018). However, significant gaps still exist. The lack of statutory regulation, inconsistent educational standards, and fragmented role definitions continue to obstruct the full realisation of advanced practice potential, and the absence of statutory title protection, inconsistent educational standards, and varying employer interpretations continue to undermine coherence and public understanding (Kilpatrick *et al.*, 2024; Nuffield Trust, 2023; NMC, 2024). Moreover, the historical reluctance of regulatory bodies to define AP precisely has left a legacy of ambiguity, complicating efforts to integrate AP roles into broader health system reform. As advanced practice continues to evolve, future policy must

balance the need for flexibility with the necessity for clarity, ensuring that innovation is supported by strong governance and equitable access to professional development.

The next section of this chapter identifies and situates a search strategy for a narrative literature review on the APNP, the focus of this thesis.

2.3 Development of a researchable topic

In adopting Gadamer's philosophical hermeneutics, the literature review was initially halted at the point of beginning the conversations (interviews). This decision reflected the hermeneutic principle that understanding develops through dialogue and that participants' voices must be heard without being overshadowed by a fixed interpretive framework. These hermeneutic concepts will be further explored in Chapter Three of this thesis. Gadamer's (2012) notion of the fusion of horizons requires that the researcher's pre-understandings, informed by prior experience, be brought into conversation with participants' experience, knowledge, and understanding. By pausing the literature review at this juncture, the study safeguarded against the risk of prioritising textual interpretations over participants' accounts, thereby allowing the data to speak authentically into the hermeneutic circle.

However, the dynamic nature of advanced practice nursing, coupled with the researcher's period of interruption from doctoral study, necessitated a return to the literature following data collection. This later engagement is not construed as a methodological deviation but as a continuation of the hermeneutic process (Gadamer, 2012). Gadamer emphasises that understanding is iterative, and horizons are continually reshaped through new encounters. Revisiting the literature after conversations enabled the study to situate participants' perspectives within the most contemporary developments in policy, regulation, and workforce transformation. In this way, the later literature review became part of the interpretive dialogue, enriching analysis by ensuring that findings were contextualised against current practice realities (Gadamer, 2012).

Transparency in reporting this process is critical. The thesis therefore acknowledges that the literature review was conducted in two phases: an initial review to establish pre-understandings prior to the participant conversations, and a subsequent review to incorporate contemporary evidence following data collection. This dual-phase approach demonstrates reflexivity, methodological integrity, and responsiveness to the evolving context of advanced practice nursing. It ensures that the study remains both faithful to hermeneutic principles and relevant to the present landscape of healthcare practice (Van Manen, 1997; Vandermause and Fleming, 2011; Gadamer, 2012).

The next section explains the search strategy used to find literature related to the development of this area of practice. A search strategy provides a structured, comprehensive, and systematic way to locate relevant information, enhancing the quality of the results. It also

ensures that the search is replicable, transparent, and that the findings can be justified (Parahoo, 2006).

2.3.1 Search Strategy

This study aims to gain an understanding and meaning of the APNP role from a whole systems perspective of service providers and service users; therefore, it is crucial to develop a thorough and transparent search strategy that systematically identifies, evaluates, and synthesises relevant literature. By clearly outlining the search parameters, databases used, inclusion and exclusion criteria, and the rationale for these decisions, the study maintains methodological integrity and provides a solid evidence base for the subsequent narrative review.

Therefore, an extensive literature review was conducted to include advanced practice developments influenced by workforce changes in the UK and internationally. The following databases were searched: Cumulative Index to Nursing and Allied Health Literature (CINAHL), Medline/PubMed, Emcare, British Nursing Index, and the Cochrane Library using key search terms (see Table 4 below). The selected databases captured essential nursing and medical literature, providing a balanced, comprehensive range and both UK and international perspectives. The searches were initially limited to English-language, peer-reviewed research articles published between 1990 and 2015 (Phase 1). This period was chosen because advanced practice nursing roles began to evolve rapidly from the early 1990s, particularly in the UK. Literature before 1990 was considered less relevant due to limited applicability and the absence of formalised advanced practice frameworks. Then, from 2016 to 2025 (Phase 2), a second search was conducted to capture contemporary developments, reflecting ongoing workforce changes, policy reforms, and the expansion of advanced practice roles in the UK and internationally.

Dividing the search into two phases was necessary due to a period of interruption from doctoral study (see Chapter 1), therefore ensuring historical coverage while also incorporating the most recent evidence, since the research conversations were carried out in 2015 and 2016, thereby situating the study within both its developmental trajectory and current practice landscape. Boolean operators, including truncation and MeSH terms, were used to support the search strategy by ensuring precision, comprehensiveness, and transparency (Aveyard, 2023). Additional articles were identified by reviewing the reference lists of sources not found during the initial search, and duplicates were subsequently removed. For articles initially deemed relevant, abstracts were reviewed, and articles were excluded if they were not evidence-based, such as discussion or editorial articles, or if they did not meet the study inclusion or exclusion criteria (Table 5 below). Having such a study criteria ensures that the review remains focused on professional policy and workforce dimensions of advanced practice and avoids loss of focus (for example, articles related to education or curriculum

issues concerning AP, or disease-specific articles) (Aveyard, 2014). Relevant grey literature was also examined (Parahoo, 2014) to ensure that all comprehensive evidence that might not have been published was identified from the NMC, RCN, Department of Health, NHS England, and NHS Scotland websites, as well as theses. This approach mitigates publication bias and strengthens the comprehensiveness of the review process (Parahoo, 2014). All unrelated articles were excluded; complete copies of each paper were obtained and read, and the papers were appraised. All papers were evaluated using an appropriate critical appraisal tool (CASP - Critical Appraisal Skills Programme, no date). A second search was conducted in the same manner between 2015 and 2025 (Phase 2).

Table 4: Key Search Terms Used

<p>Key Search Terms Used: Advanced nursing practice or advanced nurse practitioner or nurse practitioner or clinical nurse specialist, paediatric or pediatric, parent* view of APNP/ANP/AP, parent*perspective, or parent understanding of APNP role, AHP and/or doctors view of APNP/ANP/AP, doctor*perspective, AHP*perspective of ... nurse view of or nurse*perspective of APNP/ANP/AP, qualitative research, children and young people, nursing.</p>

Table 5: Study Inclusion/Exclusion Criteria

Study Inclusion Criteria:
Articles published in English Language
Phase 1 search Articles published 1990-2015
Phase 2 search Articles published 2016-2024
Articles relating to advanced practice, in terms of role development and understanding of the role – advanced practitioners, people who work alongside advanced practitioners in a healthcare related field, parents of children
Articles which related to nursing, advanced nursing and hermeneutic related methodology
Study Exclusion Criteria:
Articles published in languages other than English
Articles published before 1990
Articles relating to advanced practice but which were not relevant to role development or opinions about AP
Articles which did not relate to AP nursing and/or included other forms of methodology which were not relevant to this study

Two Prisma flow charts (2009) below demonstrate the results obtained within two timelines of 1990 – 2015 (phase 1), and the second from 2016 – 2025 (phase 2) of this study.

Figure 1: PRISMA flowchart Phase 1

Figure 2: PRISMA flowchart Phase 2

Literature search dates 2016 – 2025 (phase 2)

2.4 Literature review

This section offers a critical review of the literature presenting various perspectives on the Advanced Paediatric Nurse Practitioner (APNP) role, from service providers or service users. Over the past 25 years, there has been a substantial increase in published work on advanced practice, with more than 117 systematic reviews examining different facets of the field (Kilpatrick *et al.*, 2023). Notably, these reviews reveal that most research has focused on advanced practice roles in adult populations, with most studies employing quantitative methods measuring efficiency and effectiveness. To date, only one systematic review has specifically addressed advanced paediatric practitioners working with children and young people (Hyde *et al.*, 2020), making it challenging to reach consensus on the unique contributions of APNPs.

Within this context, relevant studies are outlined and situated in relation to the existing literature available in this part of the chapter. There remains a paucity of research in several key areas pertinent to this study: first-hand narratives from advanced paediatric nurse practitioners about their own roles; accounts from multidisciplinary team members regarding their perspectives on the APNP role; and parental perspectives on advanced paediatric nurse practitioners. The structure of this part of the chapter mirrors the framework of my study, which will be discussed in greater detail later in this thesis.

The second half of the chapter is organised into the following five main sections:

- Systematic review relating to paediatric advanced practice
- APNP or APN perspectives on their own role
- 'Others' perspectives of APNPs
- Parental perspectives of APNPs
- Other systematic reviews

This approach provides a comprehensive foundation for understanding the current evidence base and highlights the gaps that this research seeks to address.

2.4.1 Systematic review of APNPs

To date, only one systematic review has been conducted based on advanced paediatric practice. Although it is not directly focused on this study's aim, it provides useful insights into advanced paediatric practice roles. As it stands, it demonstrates the paucity of literature examining a holistic perspective on interpretative data in the context of new role development.

In 2020, Hyde, MacVicar, and Humphrey conducted a systematic review of existing literature on advanced practice nurses working with children and young people (CYP) in healthcare environments. This addressed a significant gap, as most previous research focused on adult

populations. So far, no other review of APN roles in CYP settings has been published, which hampers efforts to understand their contribution.

The review (Hyde *et al.*, 2020) identified nine studies, all of which indicated that advanced practice nurses working with CYP provide care comparable to that of medical colleagues while also adding value through enhanced patient satisfaction, role modelling, and efforts to enhance health literacy. These findings show that advanced practice nurses working with CYP are not only clinically competent practitioners but also serve as educators and clinical leaders, capable of influencing both patient outcomes and professional culture.

Patient and/or family experience of care is a key aspect compared across many of the studies. Six studies examined satisfaction with care provided by advanced practice nurses, including Borgmeyer *et al.*, (2006), Evangelista *et al.*, (2012), Fanta *et al.*, (2006), Kinder (2016), Martin (1999), and Schuttelaar *et al.*, (2010). Borgmeyer *et al.*, (2006) found that families felt they received high-quality care from APNs. Kinder (2016) echoed this, noting that parents viewed advanced practice nurses as equivalent to physicians in delivering care. Parents also reported that advanced practice nurses enhanced their knowledge and influenced decisions about their child's condition. Additionally, Kinder (2016) reported a strong correlation between APN clinical competence and parents' willingness to adhere to treatment, though the method of measuring competence was not specified. Fanta *et al.* (2006) found APNs scored significantly higher than medical colleagues in listening to parental concerns.

Staff perspectives were similarly varied. Physicians generally reported that advanced practice nurses reduced workload and managed care effectively, with high levels of satisfaction concerning communication and collaboration (Fanta *et al.*, 2006; Martin, 1999; Schuttelaar *et al.*, 2010). Only one study (Evangelista *et al.*, 1) found no difference in satisfaction levels between APN and physician-led care. However, nursing staff responses were more critical. Martin (1999) documented concerns about the continuity of care and the appropriateness of advanced practice nursing, with most nurses expressing dissatisfaction, but the author did not adequately address these findings. Rejtar *et al.*, (2017) provided a more balanced view, noting both satisfaction with advanced practice nurse contributions and concerns regarding variability in knowledge and experience. These concerns indicate tensions in interprofessional relationships and suggest that role integration may be experienced unevenly across professional groups.

Despite these promising conclusions, the evidence base remains limited. Seven of the nine studies were rated as weak by the study team, who used the Effective Public Health Practice Project (1998) tool, with only two achieving a moderate rating. The authors' reliance on this tool, chosen for familiarity, raises questions about methodological rigour and whether alternative appraisal frameworks might have provided different assessments. The lack of high-quality evidence they identified emphasises the fragility of claims regarding the

effectiveness of advanced practice nurses in children and young people settings. It highlights the necessity for more robust, contextually grounded research.

Therefore, Hyde et al., (2020) systematic review provides an important starting point for understanding the roles of advanced practice nurses working with children and young people. Still, its contribution is limited by the low quality and heterogeneity of the evidence base. The findings align with other systematic reviews based on adult advanced practice role development (Newhouse et al., 2011; Kilpatrick et al., 2023), suggesting that advanced practitioners can deliver care comparable to that of physicians; however, methodological weaknesses and conflicting staff perspectives warrant caution.

This study shows that while clinical outcomes are important, a more in-depth interpretative exploration of the advanced practitioner role for those working with CYP would be beneficial.

2.4.2 APNP perspective of role

Only two studies specifically focused on advanced paediatric practice roles were identified, both from the perspective of advanced paediatric practice nurses themselves, and both predating 2015. Other studies conducted since then may have explored the perspectives of adult-based advanced practice nurses in clinical roles or focused on quantitative outcomes related to the development of advanced paediatric nurse roles.

Davies *et al.*, (2010) conducted one of the earliest service evaluation studies in the UK to examine attitudes towards the emerging role of the paediatric nurse practitioner within retrieval services in critical care. Their work is set against a background of limited research on advanced nursing roles in paediatrics, positioning the study as both exploratory and foundational. By surveying 15 paediatric intensive care nurses across the UK, the authors aimed to define the scope of practice and gather perceptions of role development at a time when such positions were still developing.

Davies et al., (2010) findings highlight a range of themes: fear, communication, trust, teamwork, role conflict, role division, and role boundaries, which collectively reveal the tensions present in professional role transition, similarly reported by Brisson-Banks (2010) in a study exploring managing change and transitions with adult advanced practitioners. Significantly, Davies *et al.*, (2010) emphasise the dynamic nature of these perceptions: initial anxieties and uncertainties seemed to diminish as the retrieval role became established, leading to improved interprofessional collaboration and communication. This pattern underscores the adaptive ability of nursing teams when faced with role innovation, while also indicating the relational and organisational factors that influence acceptance of advanced practice.

Methodologically, Davies *et al.*, (2010) adopted a descriptive statistical approach, yielding a reasonable 67% response rate (10 out of 15 nurses) (Parahoo, 2006). While this lends some credibility to the data's representativeness, the authors acknowledge significant limitations. The small sample size may underestimate the diversity of advanced nurse practitioners involved in retrieval work, especially considering the variability in their role titles and responsibilities across the UK. Furthermore, reliance on self-assessment introduces the risk of bias, as respondents may overestimate or underestimate their competencies or experiences (Flanagan and Tatano, 2024). These methodological limitations limit the generalisability of the findings, positioning the study more as a preliminary exploration than a definitive account (Parahoo, 2006).

Nevertheless, the study's contribution lies in its originality: it is the first self-evaluation of paediatric retrieval nurse practitioners in the UK, providing a baseline overview of their scope and role development. The lack of significant regional differences in responses suggests some consistency in how the role was viewed across the country, although this uniformity might also be due to the sample's limited size rather than true nationwide consistency (Davies *et al.*, 2010).

This study highlights the importance of conducting more comprehensive, long-term, and theory-driven research to better understand the complexities of role development from nurses' perspectives, how they perceive changes in interprofessional relationships, and the wider impact on advanced paediatric nursing practice.

A year later, in 2011, Currie and Grundy made a significant contribution to advancing paediatric practice development in Scotland by evaluating a pilot national succession pathway and producing a research report funded and supported by the Scottish Government (Curry and Grundy, 2011). The succession planning pathway initiative was aligned explicitly with policy drivers (Scottish Government 2006a; 2007) designed to enhance the capacity and capability of the advanced practice workforce. Their mixed-methods approach gathered insights from 15 pathway participants, which is valuable for this thesis. It provides perspectives from managers and critical companions, offering a comprehensive view of the programme's outcomes in Scotland and its evolution over time.

The participant cohort was heterogeneous: six were already established in advanced practice roles, three were preparing for new roles, and six anticipated further development. This diversity allowed the evaluation to explore both consolidation and expansion of advanced practice. Thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006) revealed broad satisfaction with the acquisition of new knowledge and skills. However, a critical tension emerged: participants not yet in advanced roles expressed frustration at their inability to apply newly acquired competencies in practice. This disjuncture, at this point in time, underscored a theme in the literature (Por, 20008), advanced practice pathways often serve staff development purposes rather than being strategically embedded to meet service needs. The absence of

organisational foresight and planning, highlighted by Por (2008), manifests here as a structural weakness, with roles implemented in an ad hoc and inconsistent manner.

Currie and Grundy also highlighted concerns about sustainability, especially regarding funding for new roles and succession planning. Although national and regional support for succession planning was evident (Scottish Government 2006a; 2007), the absence of a unified national model left advanced practice development open to fragmentation. This uncertainty has serious consequences: practitioners and managers may see advanced roles as undervalued or marginal, leading to feelings of isolation, demotivation, and reduced role legitimacy. These findings align with broader critiques of advanced practice implementation, in which policy rhetoric often outpaces organisational readiness and resource planning (Bryant-Lukosius *et al.*, 2004; Bonsall and Cheater, 2008; Brisson-Banks, 2010).

The study's methodology is enhanced by its mixed-methods approach, capturing perspectives from both individuals and managers (Flanagan and Tatano, 2024). However, the small sample size and the pathway's pilot status limit the ability to generalise the findings (Parahoo, 2006). Overall, the evaluation was exploratory, providing insights into participants' experiences and offering suggestions rather than conclusive evidence on national succession planning.

Currie and Grundy (2011) highlighted both the potential and the fragility of advanced practice succession planning in Scotland. Their findings emphasised the tension between policy ambitions and organisational realities, highlighting the risks posed by underdeveloped strategic frameworks and insufficient funding models. The study and report demonstrated the usefulness of service provider experiences in informing the need for broader, system-wide research that explores a wider range of practitioner experiences, alongside service user experiences and other structural factors necessary for the sustainable development of advanced practice roles.

2.4.3 'Others' perspectives of APNPs

As in the previous section, only one study was identified that offered a perspective on the role of advanced paediatric nurses from a multidisciplinary team viewpoint. Other relevant studies, which are not the main focus of this thesis, discuss the development of the advanced paediatric nurses' role in relation to clinical outcomes, efficiency, and effectiveness.

Thus, Inwood *et al.*, (2021) explore clinicians' experiences and perceptions of paediatric complex care nurse practitioners within a tertiary hospital and associated health services. Their study is set within the broader context of integrating advanced practice roles into multidisciplinary teams (MDTs), with a particular emphasis on acceptance, role clarity, and perceived impact on service delivery. By using a validated survey instrument distributed to MDT members working alongside both established and trainee nurse practitioners, Inwood

et al., (2021) aimed to assess how well nurse practitioner roles were understood, valued, and trusted within complex paediatric care.

Inwood *et al.*, (2021) revealed a generally positive attitude towards the integration of advanced nurse practitioners, with most respondents recognising that the roles were effective and aligned with service needs. However, the data also revealed ongoing scepticism regarding the scope of nursing expertise. Notably, 9% of respondents expressed concerns about prescribing errors, 7% questioned diagnostic accuracy, and 15% doubted prescribing knowledge. Although these figures represent minority views, they are significant because they highlight ongoing anxieties about expertise in advanced nursing practice. This study identifies gaps in awareness among healthcare providers who are unsure of the capabilities of advanced nurse practitioners or the added value of these roles. This lack of clarity emphasises the importance of communication and role definition in fostering acceptance. Such doubts echo broader debates in the literature concerning professional boundaries, medical dominance, and the contested nature of nurse practitioner authority in specialised contexts (Nancarrow and Borthwick, 2005; Jokiniemi *et al.*, 2012; Kilpatrick *et al.*, 2012; Torrens *et al.*, 2020; Kilpatrick *et al.*, 2013; Lewis, 2022). Inwood *et al.*, (2021) suggest that more deliberate strategies are needed to clearly articulate the scope, purpose, and benefits of this role across organisational levels.

Methodologically, this study is limited by its modest 44% response rate (Parahoo, 2006), raising questions about its representativeness and the potential for non-response bias (Flanagan and Tatano, 2024). Additionally, although using a validated survey instrument can strengthen reliability, there is no discussion of the instrument's validity and reliability to make an informed judgement.

However, Inwood *et al.*, (2021) make a valuable contribution to understanding the acceptance of paediatric complex care nurse practitioners' roles. Their findings show that, although generally welcomed, nurse practitioners still face some scepticism, highlighting underlying structural and cultural tensions in healthcare. While studying clinical outcomes of nursing practice remains important, exploring perceptions of these roles can further inform the broader discussions on professional identity and interprofessional relationships as these roles evolve.

2.4.4 Parental perspectives of APNPs

Numerous studies examine parental perspectives of paediatric nurses, primarily focusing on palliative care or neonatal settings. However, few specifically address advanced paediatric nurse roles in children and young people's services. This review critically discusses three studies, two published before 2015 and one in 2022.

Forgeron and Martin-Misener (2005) conducted a mixed-methods study in a Canadian emergency department to explore parental intentions to utilise paediatric nurse practitioner services. This work is significant in that it moves beyond a focus on patient satisfaction with advanced practice roles to examine behavioural factors that shape public uptake of such services. Using a self-report questionnaire and achieving a good response rate of 78% (Flanagan and Tatano, 2024) among parents presenting their child for non-urgent emergency care, the study aimed to capture attitudes towards nurse practitioner services in a context where medical dominance typically shapes expectations of care.

Forgeron and Martin-Misener (2005) based their analysis on Rogers' (1995) innovation diffusion theory, a behavioural change model explaining how new practices are adopted or rejected over time within populations. This highlights that parental acceptance of nurse practitioners is not just about clinical equivalence to doctors but also part of a wider sociocultural process of adopting and accepting new roles. Most parents in this study felt comfortable with nurse practitioner tasks, though they showed varying levels of comfort with other aspects, such as chest x-ray interpretation, which some found uncomfortable. The authors recommended that, to better meet parental needs, physicians and nurse practitioners should interpret x-ray findings together to boost parental confidence.

However, Forgeron and Martin-Misener (2005) study's methodological limitations weaken its conclusions. The authors recognised concerns about the reliability of the questionnaire tools and scales, noting the risk of parents misinterpreting questions, but they did not offer a detailed critique of how this might affect validity. This gap is concerning, especially given the dependence on self-report data and the lack of triangulation with other methods. Although they justified their approach by citing similar instruments from previous studies (Chang *et al.*, 1999; Mitchell *et al.*, 2001), the lack of a critical discussion of measurement issues undermines confidence in the robustness of the results.

Forgeron and Martin-Misener (2005) also raised important questions regarding public awareness of nursing roles and their scope of practice. Although parents felt comfortable with nurse practitioner care, confusion remained about the limits of nursing expertise and knowledge. This challenge persists in developing advanced practice roles, where acceptance depends not only on demonstrated competence but also on public understanding and recognition of professional authority (Inwood *et al.*, 2021; Lewis, 2022). This issue persists, worsened by inconsistent implementation, unclear role definitions, and the variety of role titles (Evans *et al.*, 2020; Nuffield Trust, 2023; NMC, 2024).

A study by Dickens *et al.*, (2010) investigated parents' and service users' perspectives on family-centred care for children with disabilities. Conducted at a large Australian children's hospital, it aimed to collect both qualitative and quantitative data using the Measure of Processes of Care (MPOC) survey (King *et al.*, 1996). The research compared parents'

perceptions with staff views on the understanding of family-centred care and assessed how well parents recognise behaviours associated with high-quality family-centred care, as described in literature as a best practice model (King *et al.*, 2004).

The findings, derived from descriptive analysis, one-way ANOVA, and thematic analysis, suggested generally positive views of family-centred care among both parents and staff, with no significant differences between metropolitan and rural parent groups. This outcome is notable because it diverges from Dyke *et al.*, (2006), who reported more favourable perceptions among rural parents than their metropolitan counterparts. Dickens *et al.*'s, (2010) results therefore challenge assumptions about geographic disparities in service satisfaction, though the limited sample size and response rate complicate the strength of this conclusion.

Methodologically, this study faced some limitations that affect its interpretation. The parent response rate was low at 34% (Flanagan and Tatano, 2024), suggesting that many parents found the survey irrelevant. This could be due to the significant time pressures experienced by parents caring for children with disabilities, but it may also suggest a mismatch between the research tool (King *et al.*, 1995) and the real-world experiences of participants. Although the MPOC is a validated tool for evaluating family-centred care (King *et al.*, 1995), its application here is problematic. The study aimed to explore perceptions of care broadly, but the instrument focuses narrowly on family-centred constructs. This mismatch may have limited the depth and scope of the data, restricting the study's ability to capture wider parental experiences. The thematic analysis offered some qualitative insights, but because the survey was the main data source, qualitative findings were secondary rather than integral, reducing their interpretive power, especially in understanding how family-centred care is implemented and experienced in practice. Overall, the study emphasises the need for methodological alignment with research goals and transparent reporting throughout (Flanagan and Tatano, 2024).

Thibodeau *et al.*, (2022) conducted a study examining parent satisfaction with care provided by Paediatric Nurse Practitioners (PNPs) in different speciality areas at a tertiary paediatric hospital. A convenience sample of parents caring for children treated by 19 paediatric nurse practitioners completed a confidential survey, which included demographic information and the Parents' Perception of Satisfaction with Care from the Paediatric Nurse Practitioners Instrument (PPSC-PNP) previously developed by Kinder and Allen (2014), measuring communication skills, clinical competence, caring behaviour, and decisional control. The study found high levels of satisfaction scores in all areas and aligns with other researchers who have studied parent satisfaction (Martin-Misener, 2005), and the study found no significant differences in parental satisfaction related to child age, parent participant, or patient setting.

The study by Thibodeau *et al.*, (2022) emphasises the advanced skills, knowledge, and caring approach of paediatric nurse practitioners. Parents perceived paediatric nurse practitioners as providing expert-level care within a compassionate environment, illustrating these positive outcomes. The findings highlight the ongoing importance of these roles within children's healthcare teams and suggest that further research is needed to explore and evaluate how parents perceive the care provided by paediatric nurse practitioners and how this perception influences care across different healthcare settings. The future sustainability and growth of these roles will depend on confirming parents' experiences of the expert care their children receive and on the continued generation of evidence.

2.4.5. Other systematic reviews

This section concludes with a critical review of two additional systematic reviews. Although these reviews are not specific to advanced paediatric practice, they highlight that, despite a 12-year gap, there is still a notable lack of qualitative research exploring the experiences and perceptions of emerging advanced practice roles. This gap persists across various perspectives and limits insights that could enhance workforce planning and deepen our understanding of professional identity and interdisciplinary working relationships.

Newhouse *et al.*, (2011) examined 37 American studies (14 RCTs and 23 observational studies) to evaluate outcomes associated with advanced practice nurses compared with other healthcare providers, including physicians. Unlike some systematic reviews that restrict their scope to a narrow set of outcomes, this review captured the full range of advanced practice nurse outcomes reported in the literature, identifying 11 categories in total, not all of which were related to paediatric care.

The findings of the review were strikingly consistent. Across multiple studies, patient outcomes associated with advanced practice nurse care were shown to be equivalent to, and in some cases superior to, those achieved by physicians working alone (Lenz *et al.*, 2004; Mundinger *et al.*, 2000; Fanta *et al.*, 2006). Collaborative models of care, where Advanced practice nurses worked with a physician, were particularly effective, with evidence of improved patient outcomes and with some reductions in hospitalisation length and overall costs of care (Mundinger *et al.*, 2004). These results reinforce earlier American outcome-focused studies (Mundinger *et al.*, 2000; Lenz *et al.*, 2004), but also challenge assumptions about the physician's role as the lone gatekeeper of patient care (Lowe *et al.*, 2013). Thus, this review contributed to the growing body of evidence at that point in time that positioned advanced practice nurses as leaders in delivering high-quality, cost-effective healthcare.

Newhouse *et al.*, (2011) systematic review was not without limitations. The diversity of study designs and outcome measures complicated synthesis, and an absence of statistical data sufficient to calculate effect sizes weakened the strength of the conclusions (Parahoo, 2006).

In addition, the study literature was situated within the US healthcare system, raising questions about their transferability to other contexts, such as NHS Scotland, where organisational structures and professional hierarchies differ.

The Newhouse *et al.*, (2011) study highlights an epistemological gap in the literature that persists today. By emphasising quantitative, outcome-based measures of efficiency and effectiveness, it overlooks interpretive perspectives such as the hermeneutic lens, which could shed light on how advanced practice nurse roles are experienced and embedded in clinical practice. There remains a scarcity of qualitative research exploring the lived realities of advanced practice nurses, particularly in specialisms such as the APNP role, leaving a significant gap in understanding these roles from multiple perspectives.

Kilpatrick *et al.*, (2023) conducted a meta-review of systematic reviews to provide a global perspective on advanced practice nursing. Drawing on 5,840 articles, including 117 systematic reviews spanning 38 countries over 15 years, the study represents one of the most comprehensive syntheses of advanced practice nursing outcomes to date. The findings offer robust evidence that care delivered by advanced practice nurses, nurse practitioners, and clinical nurse specialists is broadly equivalent to, and in many cases superior to, physician-led care across 29 indicators encompassing diverse clinical settings, various patient populations, and acuity levels. This study reinforces the international legitimacy of these roles as safe and effective providers of healthcare.

However, some important distinctions were noted (Kilpatrick *et al.*, 2023). While many of the outcome measures demonstrated equity or superiority, results relating to quality of life, consultation patterns, healthcare costs, emergency visits, and broader delivery metrics were inconsistent, with some studies favouring physician-led control groups. These variations demonstrate the complexity of evaluating advanced practice nurse effectiveness across heterogeneous systems and highlight the limitations of relying solely on outcome-based indicators without accounting for contextual and systemic differences.

Critically, Kilpatrick *et al.*, (2023) identified significant gaps in the global evidence base. Despite the breadth of included studies, several WHO regions remain underrepresented, raising questions about the universality of the conclusions. The review also points to neglected areas of enquiry, including the functioning of interprofessional teams, workload implications, strategies for engaging patients and families as active partners in care, and the role of advanced practice nurses in addressing the needs of vulnerable populations, particularly in children and young people. Similar to the results of Newhouse *et al.*, (2011), from nearly 15 years ago, the results suggest that while quantitative evidence for advanced practice nurse effectiveness is strong, the literature remains underdeveloped in some respects. There remains a paucity of qualitative research exploring the experiences or

understanding of advanced practice roles, particularly in specialisms such as the APNP role, leaving a significant gap in knowledge of these roles from different perspectives.

2.5 Summary

This chapter has provided a critical examination of advanced practice and the evolution of advanced practice roles from global, UK, and Scottish perspectives. It has explored the policies that have shaped the development of advanced practice, alongside key factors such as regulation, education, and training. Additionally, the chapter outlined the literature search strategy and reviewed literature relevant to this study.

In summary, the studies discussed reveal a paucity of robust evidence and a fragmented, inconsistent evidence base for paediatric advanced practice. While existing research offers broad insights into the development of advanced paediatric practice roles, many studies are constrained by methodological limitations. This underscores the need for future research that combines methodological rigour with theoretical depth. Such research should not only evaluate the health outcomes associated with the advanced paediatric nurse practitioner role for children and families, but also incorporate perspectives from practitioners, multidisciplinary team members, and parents regarding the value and impact of these roles. A more comprehensive, holistic understanding of advanced practice in all its forms and complexities is essential. These insights can inform practice development, strengthen professional identity, and enhance educational training- an imperative that is especially relevant for NHS Scotland, where no comparable studies have yet been conducted.

The next chapter discusses and develops the theoretical framework which underpins this thesis and aligns with the study's aim and objectives.

CHAPTER THREE – Theoretical Framework

3.1 Introduction

This study intends to develop the understanding and meaning of the APNP role from a whole systems perspective of service providers and service users, and to contribute new knowledge where there is currently a paucity of evidence in the literature. Using Gadamer's philosophical hermeneutics to guide this study will make a new contribution to the current literature and to knowledge and understanding of the development of the APNP role within NHS Scotland. The theoretical framework provides the philosophical and methodological foundation for this study. It situates the research within broader epistemological debates, clarifies the assumptions underpinning the inquiry, and guides the interpretive process. To justify the adoption of Gadamer's philosophical hermeneutics, it is necessary first to outline the contrasting traditions of positivism and interpretivism, trace the origins of hermeneutics, and then consider the development of Gadamer's philosophical hermeneutics (Gadamer, 2012) and his key concepts.

3.1.1 Positivism

Positivism-based research theories are typically employed for scientific discoveries, operating within a set of assumptions and beliefs aligned with the hypothetico-deductive method of science (Parahoo, 2014; Park *et al.*, 2020). These theories are based on testing hypotheses and experiments that rely on reasoning and the measurement of quantifiable data, where actions, activities, or reactions can be observed. Using these assumptions, researchers can assess the quality of their findings and identify knowledge gaps, providing evidence that advances scientific understanding (Park *et al.*, 2020).

This paradigm and its associated theories generally hold that if something cannot be observed and measured, it is of little or no significance. This perspective often favours various quantitative data collection methods (Gray and Grove, 2020), which rely on large sample sizes to derive empirically based conclusions through controlled experiments, replication of findings, or aiming for generalizable inferences. These studies mainly aim to establish causal relationships or associations that enable predictions. Therefore, empirical research conducted within this framework typically helps develop theories and advance scientific knowledge (Gray and Grove, 2020). However, this study does not aim to find an empirical answer or contribute to scientific knowledge, but rather to gain a new understanding of nursing knowledge regarding the role of the APNP. Therefore, using a positivist paradigm does not align with the aim of this study.

3.1.2 Interpretivism

The Interpretivist paradigm holds that beliefs are loosely based on the idea that all reality is subjective and socially constructed in some manner. Interpretivist perspectives argue that an individual’s reality can only be understood through their experiences, which are shaped by their historical and social context. This can be achieved through various questioning techniques and observations, allowing for the development of rich, in-depth data that demonstrates an understanding of the phenomenon being studied (Parahoo, 2014, De Chesnay, 2015). This aligns with Gadamer’s philosophical hermeneutics (Gadamer, 2012).

In interpretative research, research methods tend to emphasise individual beliefs, motivations, and reasoning rather than quantitative data, facilitating an understanding of social interactions. Subjectivity is regarded as important due to the interaction between researcher and participant and recognises that meanings and understanding are constructed in different ways depending on the circumstances, context, and points of reference within the world being interpreted (Crotty 1998).

A review of the different interpretivist approaches was undertaken prior to the start of this study (Table 6/Appendix 1). Following an additional literature review at the beginning of this study, nine research papers claiming to utilise hermeneutics were critically examined. This analysis highlighted how other researchers had employed hermeneutics (Table 7/Appendix 2) to identify the most suitable approach for this study. It was ultimately concluded that Gadamer’s philosophical hermeneutics (Gadamer, 2012) was the right approach (Table 7 is available in Appendix 2 with a broader critique of each of the papers read).

Table 6: Different Methodologies within Interpretivism

Method	Consideration	Rationale for use/not using
Phenomenology	Focus on lived experience of a particular phenomenon	Lived experience is descriptive and can be ambiguous, doesn’t require the application of deeper understanding.
Grounded theory	Developing theories from data on a phenomenon or action	Developing a theory is not the aim of this thesis.
Ethnography	Understanding cultures by describing behaviours, beliefs and values – researchers situate themselves within a cultural group to observe its functioning	As there are three different groups under study in this thesis, the aim is not to describe cultural behaviours, beliefs or values.

Narrative Inquiry	Exploring life stories of individuals through complex stories of personal journeys	Exploring life stories and personal journeys explicitly was not the aim of this thesis.
Case study	Involves intensive investigation of a single case to provide contextualised understanding of an issue	A case study methodology does not align to the aims of this thesis.
Discourse analysis	Uses language and communication to understand how identity and roles are constructed and maintained within a specific context	This methodology examines how language is used as a social practice to construct meanings, power dynamics and social reality instead of developing a deeper understanding of text.
IPA	Focuses on how people make sense of personal experience. An account of lived experience but not prescribed by any pre-existing theoretical concepts.	Although IPA uses hermeneutics as a core analytical component, it fails to recognise that the hermeneutic circle starts with one's own pre-conceptions which is part of Gadamer's philosophical hermeneutic framework.

Table 7: Papers critically reviewed

Authors	Title	Aim	Claims & limitations
Howlin 2008	Understanding advocacy in children's nursing.	To illuminate and interpret experience of children's nurses' advocacy	Philosophical hermeneutic inspired by Gadamer - lack of detail in relation to application of Gadamerian concepts and used Benner for data analysis but Benner's methodology is driven by Heideggerian philosophy which does not align to Gadamerian philosophy.
Ryde, Strang & Friedrichsen (2008)	Crying in Solitude or With Someone for Support and Consolidation: Experiences from Family	To explore deeper understanding of family members' experience of crying within hospital based palliative care units.	Qualitative hermeneutic approach. Lack of application of concepts fully i.e. lack of reflection on historical background of researcher. Acknowledged by authors in terms of limitations.

	Members in Palliative Home Care.		Discussed data saturation rather than fusion of horizon.
Grassley & Nelms (2008)	Understanding maternal breastfeeding confidence: a Gadamerian hermeneutic analysis of women's stories.	To gain understanding of maternal breast-feeding confidence and its meaning.	Gadamerian hermeneutic study faithfully described using Fleming et al, but lacked detail in places, and did not account for pre-understandings which is a requirement to enter hermeneutic circle.
Wiriya, Hatthakit, Wiroonpanich and Smith-Battle (2009)	Buddhist Mothers' Experience of Suffering and Healing After the Accidental Death of a Child.	To explore what suffering means to Buddhist mothers who had experienced an accidental death of a child.	Gadamerian hermeneutic phenomenological approach. The study demonstrates inconsistencies and misconceptions in the boundaries between phenomenology and hermeneutics.
Skar (2009)	How nurses experience their work as a learning environment.	To illuminate the meaning of nurses' experiences of autonomy in work.	Hermeneutic approach where method of Fleming et al described faithfully but a lack of application noted between concepts and method and potential difficulty in use of focus groups which may be biased towards one person's opinion when applying preunderstanding to a situation and as a means to enter the hermeneutic circle.
Lindberg, Persson & Bondas (2012)	The responsibility of someone else: a focus group study of collaboration between a university and a hospital regarding the integration of	To develop an understanding of collaboration between a hospital and university regarding the integration of caring science in practice.	Hermeneutical interpretative approach inspired by Fleming et al. No main focus on concepts to underpin study identified and therefore leads to a lack of clarity about influence and development of understanding of the phenomenon.

	caring science in practice.		
Soderhamn, Dale & Soderhamn (2013)	The meaning of actualization of self-care resources among a group of older home-dwelling people: A hermeneutic study.	To re-analyse narratives to describe self-care activities of older people.	Gadamerian based research. Method clearly articulated and faithful to Fleming et al method but no central concepts were discussed within paper leading to a lack of clarity.
Weiland (2013)	Understanding nurse practitioner autonomy.	To understand the meaning of autonomy to nurse practitioners	Gadamerian hermeneutics using Fleming et al. No Gadamerian concepts are identified and no reflection on preunderstanding and other influences.
Austgard (2013)	Doing it the Gadamerian way using philosophical hermeneutics as a methodological approach in nursing science.	Review of basic key concepts of Gadamer's hermeneutics into a methodological approach to the interpretation of texts	Gadamerian philosophical hermeneutic method identifies key concepts used. 1 major difference noted, with use of 'fore-understanding' which emerges from different opinions of the researchers. There are differences to preunderstanding which gives historical awareness.

Hermeneutics is the branch of knowledge dealing with interpretation (Oxford English Dictionary 2010). Historically, hermeneutics was seen as the art of correctly reading and interpreting ancient texts, particularly the Bible (Palmer 1969).

Gadamer (2012) defines hermeneutics as the 'art of understanding texts' (p 164) and states that hermeneutics enables us to uncover and interpret meaning in texts. This includes written dialogue or any conversation within Gadamer's definition of 'text'. Gadamer emphasises that all understanding is shaped by an individual's tradition and historicity in relation to the phenomenon being examined. He points out that each person is influenced differently, making it crucial to recognise that everyone's understanding is different. Gadamer

distinguishes the subtleties of understanding drawn on through individuals' unique experiences and understanding that each person brings to their comprehension.

As the aim of my study is to gain an understanding and meaning of the APNP role from a whole-systems perspective of service providers and service users, the application of Gadamer's hermeneutic philosophy was deemed to be the most appropriate methodological approach to align with these study aims allowing for the discovery of new knowledge through conversations and exploring individuals unique experiences and perspectives of the phenomenon, which is congruent with Gadamer's' philosophical hermeneutics (Gadamer, 2012). The following section identifies the origins of hermeneutics before linking to Gadamer's philosophical hermeneutics (2012).

3.2 Origins of Hermeneutics

Hermeneutics is a term derived from the Greek 'hermeneutikos', meaning to interpret (Palmer 1969), and can be traced back to the time of Aristotle and Hermes. 'Hermes' is associated with the discovery of language and writing, which humans use to convey meaning and that enables interpretation (Palmer, 1969). Hermeneutics encourages human potential for understanding the meaning of language to expand the infinite possibilities of human thought (Palmer, 1969). Based on theological interpretations of the Christian Bible, hermeneutics aimed to affirm God's authority over the thinking process (Palmer, 1969) so that divine revelations could be understood and applied to real-life situations (Silverman, 1994). Hermeneutics is now generally regarded as a philosophical discipline focused on questioning, interpreting, and understanding (Agrey, 2014). It is widely applied in human science subjects, such as nursing, in contrast to the strict procedures and methods of positivism. Smith (2002, p. 183) explains that 'engaging in hermeneutic activity is simply the ordinary work of trying to make sense of things we don't understand, things that fall outside our taken for granted assumptions about the nature of experience'.

Hermeneutic enquiry is distinctive and prioritises questioning that ultimately leads to meaning. The questions asked do not necessarily have simple answers, but genuine enquiry remains open-ended and vague, emphasising the process over finding definitive answers (Gadamer, 2012).

3.3 Origins of Philosophical Hermeneutics

Edmund Husserl (1859-1938) is widely regarded as the founder of the modern phenomenological movement. He outlined a method of thinking and inquiry focused on studying experience within the life-world (Dahlberg and Dahlberg, 2002; Crist and Tanner, 2003; McConnell-Henry *et al.*, 2009). Husserl proposed an epistemological perspective where the mind and body are viewed as mutually exclusive (Benner, 1984; Cohen *et al.*, 2000;

McConnell *et al.*, 2009), emphasising the importance of uncovering truth through a systematic understanding of human (lived) experiences and exploring them through rigorous inquiry.

For Husserl, the aim of phenomenology was the rigorous and unbiased descriptive study of things as they appear to understand human consciousness and lived experience. Husserl achieved this by considering the immediate pre-reflective consciousness of life (Dilthey, 1985; Husserl, 2012), attempting to understand the phenomenon as independently of cultural context as possible through phenomenological reduction. He supported phenomenological 'bracketing', where researchers set aside their preconceptions and beliefs to reveal the true essence of another's lived experience (Cohen *et al.*, 2000; McConnell *et al.*, 2009).

Building on Husserl's work, Heidegger (1889-1976)(2010) expanded ideas related to phenomenology. His seminal work, *Being and Time* (1927/1962), introduced the concept of the nature of being, questioning and challenging conventional thinking. Heidegger rejected Husserl's epistemological 'bracketing' and wrote about *being-in-the-world* as an integral, temporal, and dynamic activity that comprises what it means 'to be'. He regarded interpretation as involving a pre-existing understanding of 'being-in-the-world' and the integration of human experience with meaning (Vandermause and Fleming, 2011). Heidegger identified intentionality as the core concept for understanding and categorising conscious acts (Moustakas 1994; Dowling 2012), which pertains to the internal experience of being aware of something. Husserl's aims were primarily epistemological, considering experience as the essential source of all knowledge (Dowling and Cooney, 2012). Heidegger's work emphasised the human ability to make interpretations based on prior knowledge, in which what might be is interpreted. Humans are self-interpretative beings, and interpretation occurs in an all-encompassing circular process, which could be described as the hermeneutic circle, allowing for understanding by considering the past, present, and future (Diekelmann and Ironside, 2006). For Heidegger (2003), this process is essential, but he opposes Husserl's view on the significance of describing this experience rather than understanding it (Racher, and Robinson, 2003). Heidegger promoted the use of hermeneutics, grounded in the ontological view that lived experience is an interpretive process. Heidegger uses the phrase 'Being in the world', referred to as 'Dasein', and introduced the concept of the hermeneutic circle to illustrate his ideas. Heidegger's exploration of Dasein recognises that something must exist before it can be studied (Heidegger from Regan, 2012). The concepts of historicity and the hermeneutic circle are seen as a revision of phenomenological reduction, rather than its rejection (Racher and Robinson, 2003).

Hans-Georg Gadamer (1900-2002), a student of Heidegger, expanded upon Heidegger's ontological perspective (McConnell *et al.*, 2009). Heideggerian-Gadamerian phenomenology is rooted in tradition, which marks a shift from an epistemological focus on understanding essences and seeking universal truths to an ontological understanding of a person's being in

the world. Being-in-the-world encapsulates the idea that knowledge of our everyday existence is intersubjective, temporal, and relational (Evans and O'Brien, 2005; Gadamer, 2012). Heidegger and Gadamer concur that individuals cannot avoid preconceptions, and attempting to exclude them is unattainable (Annells, 1999; Gadamer, 2012). In light of this, the researcher acts as an instrument of the interpretive process and cannot 'bracket' prior knowledge and understanding, as data is gathered and analysed within the interpretive tradition. This departure from Husserlian phenomenology is notable. Therefore, the philosophical hermeneutic interview is a distinctive form of questioning that differs and necessitates fidelity to the philosophical assumptions aligned with Heideggerian and Gadamerian thought.

3.4 The hermeneutics of Gadamer

Hermeneutics concerns both the philosophy of understanding and the science of textual interpretation (Gadamer, 2012). Gadamer's philosophical hermeneutics seeks to uncover the nature of human understanding by asking how understanding is possible. Gadamer viewed hermeneutics not as developing a specific method but as clarifying the conditions in which understanding occurs (Gadamer, 2012). He was influenced by Heidegger's focus on 'the question of being' and developed his work in 'Truth and Method' (original English version 1989, 2012). His work relates to the situatedness of human knowledge, the impracticality of reducing truth to mere research methods, and the development of understanding through openness to dialogue with others (Hovey, Rodriguez and Jordan, 2020).

Gadamer does not provide the researcher with a specific method or set of rules to follow (Gadamer, 2012), but recognises that a systematic approach is necessary to gain a deeper understanding of a text. This can be challenging for novice hermeneutic researchers, who often need structure to guide the research process. Van Manen (1997) agrees that it is essential to adopt an approach that helps direct the research and facilitates interpretation, with various methods demonstrated in the literature (Colaizzi, 1978; Van Manen, 1997; Giorgi, 1997; and Koch, 1996). These methods typically relate to phenomenological or hermeneutic research but are often not differentiated correctly or do not accurately reflect the underlying philosophical principles (Fleming *et al.*, 2003).

3.4.1 Development and understanding of Gadamer's hermeneutic

Gadamer's work is cited in nursing research and used to explore the concept of understanding in the natural sciences (Todres and Wheeler, 2000; Fleming *et al.*, 2002; Miles *et al.*, 2013; Austgard, 2013). Crotty (1996) had previously concluded that there had been an uncritical misuse of hermeneutic sources in the nursing science literature after studying thirty research articles which identified the use of hermeneutic sources but often failed to act upon many central concepts identified, and in a more recent article, Fleming and Robb (2018) also found

that a large number of studies misrepresent and inaccurately cite Gadamer's philosophical concepts.

Gadamer's discussions recognise that people experience the world through language (dialogue), in which dialogue serves as the conduit for understanding and the development of knowledge (Gadamer, 2012). Gadamer views interpretation of language as essential to all activities and considers the social, cultural, and gender implications involved (Koch 1999; Dowling 2007), asserting that 'Language is the universal medium in which understanding occurs. Understanding occurs in interpreting' (2012, p. 390), which then becomes the 'text'. Gadamer saw interpretation as a fusion of horizons, in which a dialectical interaction occurs between the interpreter's (researcher's) expectations and the meaning of the 'text' (Polkinghorne 1983, Lamb 2006).

Studying various scholars' texts that claimed to employ Gadamer's hermeneutics to pursue authenticity and understand their research approaches proved *beneficial*. These texts, previously identified in this chapter and listed in Appendix 2, helped shape my early understanding of Gadamer's key concepts and influenced my research direction. Additionally, I learned from Geanellos (2000) the importance of exercising caution when applying hermeneutics, a warning that many authors of 'hermeneutic' studies have overlooked by not faithfully following the philosopher's concepts.

Gadamer's original work was written in German (1960) and initially published in that language. Since 1975, it has been available in English, and over the years, it has undergone several updates. More researchers have since used this work, demonstrating that Gadamer's key concepts are applicable across contexts. Some German terms lack direct English equivalents; when this occurs, it is acknowledged, and minor adjustments based on colleagues' suggestions were made to overcome these differences. Austgard (2013) and Skar (2008) also noted translation challenges in their studies. They believe that using a translation is acceptable as long as it is justified within the context of the reading and the text (Skar 2008). Thus, appropriate advice and consideration were provided to support my understanding of the literature and theoretical framework. To prevent any misunderstanding of the language or terminology used in this thesis, a list of definitions of key terms or words is included at the beginning of this thesis.

In reviewing the literature that informed this research, several authors claimed to employ Fleming *et al's.*, (2003) method in their hermeneutical studies (Howlin, 2008; Grassley and Nelms, 2008; Wiriya *et al.*, 2009), though some did so more accurately than others. After examining their work and Fleming *et al's.*, (2003) publication, the research method identified and used by Fleming *et al.*, (2003) which closely aligns with Gadamer's philosophical hermeneutic principles (Gadamer, 2012), was adopted.

The research method of *Fleming et al.*, (2003) is grounded in fundamental concepts of Gadamer's philosophical hermeneutics, thereby facilitating accurate interpretation. *Fleming et al.*, (2003) describe five steps that serve as a logical guide for applying Gadamerian concepts and integrating them into research. Being a novice in hermeneutic research is challenging, and understanding 'how to be and stay open' can be confusing. I therefore incorporated and built upon this approach to better understand and analyse any dialogue or text.

3.5 The importance of the theoretical framework

Theoretical frameworks provide the conceptual scaffolding that guides research design, analysis, and interpretation of findings (Grant and Osanloo, 2014). Bradshaw (2013) suggests that by following important concepts, Gadamer's philosophical hermeneutics enables the emergence of new truths and, consequently, new knowledge, which benefits nursing research.

Since Gadamer's philosophical hermeneutics (2012) was chosen to aid in interpreting and understanding the APNP role from both service users' and service providers' perspectives, engaging with his key philosophical concepts deepened the understanding of his ontological stance. This confirmed that his ideas offered a solid foundation for this study. Gadamer's key concepts support the idea that understanding is possible (Gadamer, 2012). His philosophical key concepts provided a pathway for developing the research aims while recognising and working within my own historical context (Gadamer, 2012; Geanellos, 1998; *Fleming et al.*, 2003; Austgard, 2013).

There is, of course, some criticism of hermeneutics, often concerning its subjectivity and its heavy reliance on tradition (Habermas, 1980; Hirsch, 1967). However, some postmodernists argue that Gadamer's use of tradition did not go far enough (Heidegger, 1962; Nietzsche, 2019). Additionally, if findings are not reported accurately, they can be challenging to validate and may be biased (Parahoo, 2006). Several studies have also been accused of failing to align with the original intentions of the theoretical framework, and this is considered problematic (Crotty, 1996; Geanellos, 1998; Skar, 2008; Austgard, 2013).

With this in mind, the next section outlines and discusses Gadamer's (2012) key concepts, which were found to be important for this study.

3.6 Key Concepts used by Gadamer

Gadamer's philosophical hermeneutics provides the conceptual foundation for this study, with several key concepts central to its interpretive framework. Language, tradition, and culture form the backdrop against which understanding is shaped, while horizon and pre-understanding highlight the situated nature of interpretation. The hermeneutic circle

describes the dynamic movement between whole and part, and the fusion of horizons illustrates how new meaning emerges when perspectives encounter one another. Dialogue, both spoken and textual, is the medium through which this process unfolds, enabling understanding to remain open, reflexive, and continually evolving. The following section will explore each of these concepts in turn and their role in shaping the interpretive process.

3.6.1 Language, tradition and culture

For Gadamer, language is not merely a tool of communication but the very medium through which understanding is enabled. Yet language cannot be separated from the traditions and cultural contexts in which it is embedded. Tradition provides historical continuity that shapes meaning, while culture situates interpretation within a community's lived practices and shared values. Taken together, these concepts form an interdependent triad: language articulates, tradition informs, and culture contextualises. In methodological terms, it underscores the interpretive process of this study, where participants' accounts are understood not in isolation but as expressions shaped by historical inheritance and cultural horizons, and where meaning emerges through dialogue that fuses these horizons with those of the researcher (Gadamer, 2012).

3.6.1.1 Language

Language is central to Gadamer's philosophy, with Gadamer (2012) describing it as the universal tool for understanding. Understanding occurs through Logos, serving as a means of communication with others, thus making understanding possible (Gadamer, 2012). This use of language activates words that characterise objects, which we recognise mentally (Regan, 2012). When we unconsciously think about these objects, we can connect to others through a shared tool of communication. Language enables an individual to create a picture of their world (Lawn, 2006) and fosters shared understanding through the commonality of language (Palmer, 1969; Lawn, 2006). This enables the development of ways to understand and predict the world around us. However, this ability to predict introduces bias in our understanding of both spoken and written language, as we only become aware of the language we use in unusual situations. Gadamer indeed contends that understanding depends on language and the traditions transmitted through it (Gadamer, 2008).

3.6.1.2 Tradition

Gadamer argues that tradition is integral to the human sciences and states, 'our understanding of a text is not an act of subjectivity but proceeds from the commonality that binds us to the tradition' (Gadamer 2012, p. 293). Our traditions and language constantly shape the commonality of language. Gadamer's key thought is that, as human beings, we all

find common ground, which makes understanding others possible. For Gadamer, commonality and historicity are closely connected, and this is a concept we grasp through living in a world with a historical context, which becomes more meaningful as Dasein, meaning 'being there' (Heidegger, 2003). For example, from the moment we are born, our existence has a past that quickly connects with our future, and our essence merges into the ancient world. Therefore, Gadamer proposes that we belong to history, rather than history belonging to us (Gadamer et al 2012). Regan (2012) compared this to our 'biological clock' that gradually diminishes even before we become aware of our mortality. To understand this, we must recognise that our socially and culturally constructed identity is continually linked to the past. Self-awareness arises when we provoke our past by reflecting on our pre-understanding of any given situation, which helps reveal new insights and knowledge.

3.6.1.3 Culture

Dasein is also connected to the sharing of cultural information and learning from others, which shapes our social communities and sense of belonging (Gadamer 2012). The potential for understanding must also be viewed through the lens of cultural information. Cultures are complex, distinctive, alive, and interconnected through language; they are unique and vibrant. Culture comprises many aspects, including social customs, religious beliefs, rituals, practices, and may have their own written texts. In relation to this research, culture is primarily considered in the context of nursing and the developing APNP role.

Individuals and communities learn from one another through communication, which consists of language, tradition, and culture within our social groups and relationships. It is through the embedded linguistic traditions that we pass down information that is significant and influences what we see, hear, read, or speak, which is then interpreted (Gadamer 2012). Gadamer suggests that all inscription is a form of alienated speech that must be converted back into speech and meaning (Gadamer, 2012). Once language is understood as speech, it is appreciated as dialogue. Therefore, when interpreting a text, bringing the meaning of words to life is essential, achieved by working with the text as a partner in dialogue. By engaging in conversation, dialogue is revitalised and understanding develops. This renewal of the text takes us back to the themes of our pre-understanding, where the meaning remains dialogical and questioned, staying open to possibilities, and the text for the interpreter may then develop differently (Gadamer, 2012).

3.6.1.4 Language, Culture and Tradition: Positioning the researcher

Self-reflection is important to this study to remain true to Gadamer's key concepts in Philosophical Hermeneutics. I acknowledge that my background as an experienced nurse and nurse educator underpins my knowledge and understanding of the history, traditions, and art of nursing and nurse education in the United Kingdom (UK).

Some participants in this study might share my understanding of the APNP role and its development, or they might see it differently due to shared professional and cultural aspects as qualified nurses. Differences could arise based on where they trained in the UK, but many similarities in language, culture, and tradition are likely, as all nurses are regulated by the NMC (Nursing and Midwifery Council, 2018). Having facilitated learning and served as a programme leader for an Advanced Clinical Practice (adult, paediatrics, mental health) programme at a Scottish university for over 11 years, I need to remain open to how my educational background has shaped my understanding of this role and consider how it may contrast with views in the clinical practice context where this study takes place.

For this study, three key groups of people were involved. Conversations were conducted with eight APNP participants, eight 'others' who were colleagues of APNPs, and five parents in order to gain an understanding and meaning of their perspectives on the role. As a programme leader for Advanced Clinical Practice, I had previously spoken with APNPs who were trainees on the programme, as well as with stakeholders with a vested interest, such as colleagues working alongside APNPs in various capacities. However, I had not previously spoken with any parent of a child who had been cared for by an APNP. By acknowledging this, I allowed myself to remain open to new perspectives in my understanding of the role. Finally, it is important to note that the study included both urban and rural areas in Scotland where the APNP role is active, which could reveal notable differences in how this role is understood

3.6.2 Horizon

The term 'horizon' refers to the understanding a person possesses about any aspect of their world. Gadamer regards 'horizon' as our perspective on the world and as a broadening of our outlook (Lamb 2006, Gadamer 2012). Gadamer explains that 'The concept of the "horizon" suggests itself because it expresses the superior breadth of vision that the person who is trying to understand must have' (Gadamer 2012, p 305). When applied to language and understanding, Gadamer considers 'horizon' as providing us with boundaries that make understanding possible.

Consciousness is shaped by a fusion of horizons that reflect tradition, historicity, culture, society, and future expectations (Lawn 2006). Palmer (1969) agrees that to understand the present, one must look beyond one's own horizon or past. Gadamer (2012) suggests this can be achieved through inquiry and the anticipation of what lies behind spoken words, as well as through consideration of many possibilities. This approach enables one to go beyond current knowledge and explore new horizons. Gadamer highlights that horizons are open and dynamic (Gadamer 2012), not fixed but temporary, shaped by one's historical awareness.

3.6.3 Pre-understanding (sometimes called prejudice)

Another key concept identified by Gadamer (2012) is prejudice. The word prejudice etymologically is broken down into prejudice or pre-judgement (Lamb 2006). In the context of Gadamer's philosophical hermeneutics, the concept and meaning of prejudice is neutral for Gadamer, and he uses the term positively, as awareness of our history and tradition. However, the term prejudice in English can carry negative connotations in everyday language; therefore, past authors (Koch, 1996; Gaenellos, 1998; *Fleming et al.*, 2003; Robb, 2006) have adopted the term 'pre-understanding' to reflect on an individual's awareness of past history and tradition. Therefore, the term pre-understanding will be used in this study.

Pre-understanding is 'a judgement that is rendered before all the elements that determines a situation has finally been examined' (Gadamer 2012, p 273). Gadamer (2012) believes that it is impossible to deny one's pre-understanding, and it is crucial to recognise this, as our historicity and reflection on it enable further understanding to develop. Indeed, Gadamer considered pre-understanding to be the very foundation of our knowledge.

Self-reflection is crucial because biases and assumptions are ingrained in a person's daily language, traditions, and culture, making it vital to the interpretive process (Gadamer, 2012; Lavery, 2003). This concept, known as reflexivity (Creswell, 2007), should be recognised in pre-understanding. Reflecting on a developing horizon involves ongoing consideration of pre-understandings, showcasing this reflexivity, which is also emphasised by Geanellos (1998), Fleming et al. (2003), and Koch (2006) as significant.

3.6.4 The hermeneutic circle

The hermeneutic circle serves as a metaphor for ongoing movement where a definitive starting point cannot be identified. Palmer (1969) traces the idea of the hermeneutic circle back to the philologist Ast, who explored the meaning of ancient texts. Schleiermacher, Dilthey, Heidegger, and Gadamer all considered and applied the concept of the hermeneutic circle in their work. Schleiermacher suggests that understanding can only be demonstrated when part of the text is contrasted with the meaning of the whole (Gadamer, 2012). Dilthey, a student of Schleiermacher, proposed the hermeneutic circle as essential for understanding historical expression, as comprehension of the lived world in the present is culturally connected and inextricably linked to the past (Lawn, 2006). Palmer (1969) explained how we interpret individual words within the context of an entire sentence, while the sentence's meaning depends on the understanding of the individual words. Thus, understanding develops through moving from parts of the text to the whole of the text and then back again to parts of the text, forming the basis of the hermeneutic circle.

Lamb (2006) describes this process using the analogy of reading a book. When reading, one is always anticipating the overall meaning of the text while attempting to understand the story and plots. The reader must make all the individual parts of the text fit together to grasp the book's overall significance. The reader is continually engaged in reading a small part of the work, through a word, sentence, or paragraph, all of which contribute to the overall meaning, resulting in a constant oscillation and movement back and forth between the parts and the whole of the book (Lamb, 2006).

Consequently, recognising pre-understanding is essential for understanding the present and enables interpretation within the hermeneutic circle, as understanding occurs when a fusion of horizons between past and present takes place (Grondin, 2003; Gadamer, 2004). The dialogue within a text leads to the formation of an opinion about *die Sache* (meaning the thing), which is always open for 'discussion'. Therefore, caution is essential because implicit pre-understandings, over which we have no conscious control, influence interpretations unconsciously. Engaging with the hermeneutic circle by addressing and reflecting on these pre-understandings will support the realisation and development of a new fusion of horizons (Gadamer, 2012).

The interrelationship between the whole and its individual parts must not, however, be viewed as a *circulus vitiosus* (vicious cycle), from which one cannot escape. In the hermeneutic circle, one does not remain in the same place but continuously gains new knowledge. Consequently, the circle is a positive opportunity for acquiring new understanding (Gadamer, 2012). It has been argued that the hermeneutic circle should be seen more as a spiral, due to the continual development of new knowledge, in order to avoid deterministic assumptions (Ödman, 1979; Polkinghorne, 1983).

Temporal distance (distance in time) is important to consider in this process and enables the reflective reassessment of preunderstandings, which negotiates between the traditions that fuse into newness. Temporality affects all interpretations of speech and text (Regan, 2012). The transient nature of speech develops alongside cultural influences for the interpreter within their own temporal understanding (Gadamer, 2012). Thus, temporality is grounded in the process of where the past and present are situated, with 'time' being aware of tradition and supporting understanding by highlighting what is present now (Gadamer, 2012). Gadamer views the passage of time as supporting a more objective understanding, as it allows feelings and emotions to become more distant. This can enable fuller reflection, for example, through using a reflective diary to record challenging encounters.

Understanding occurs when pre-understandings that can lead to misunderstanding are sifted out through the interplay of the whole and the parts in the hermeneutic circle (Gadamer, 2012). However, it is not about understanding better, but rather that 'we understand in a different way, if we understand at all' (Gadamer, 2004, p. 296). Neither is it about moving towards a final 'objective' solution (Gadamer, 2012), as the hermeneutic circle is not

conclusive. The hermeneutic circle illustrates the coming together of interpreter and text in a fusion of horizons (Gadamer, 2012). Hermeneutics is a process where someone tries to clarify what seems unclear. Therefore, the hermeneutic circle can be seen as the framework for interpretation and reasoning. (Palmer, 1969; Polkinghorne, 1983).

3.6.5 Fusion of horizons

Gadamer developed the phrase ‘fusion of horizons’, which occurs in everyday conversations in which language serves as an intermediary for understanding (Miles *et al.*, 2013). Gadamer described the miracle of understanding as an event and evidence of truth that happens when the interpreter comprehends the concepts of the text and can share their own interpretation of them (Gadamer 2012, p. 380). Sharing different perspectives on a phenomenon allows points of view to merge and generate new insights, leading to a deeper understanding. In research, fusion occurs as the researcher becomes immersed in the analysis of the text, illuminating new awareness and insight. This process of developing understanding is infinite and not static (Gaenellos, 1998). Even as fusion occurs, the shared understanding and the coming together of horizons continue, and there is movement forward toward further interpretation and understanding (Koch, 2006; Gadamer, 2012). Therefore, although “fusion of horizons” is ultimately the goal, it can never be fully achieved or have final completion (Lamb, 2006).

In essence, a fusion of horizons can occur with each individual conversation. Gadamer (2012) does not suggest that one horizon can be easily reconciled with another but supports the idea that the need for interpretation is constant and ever-present. Gadamer (2012) states that ‘the fusion of the horizons of interpretation is nothing that one ever fully achieves, as ‘the horizon of interpretation changes constantly, just as our visual horizon also varies with every step that we take’ (Lamb, 2006, p 66). Thus, the fusion of horizons extends the concept of the hermeneutic circle (Robb, 2006).

The fusion of horizon (understanding) occurs through a dialogue with the text, requiring openness to different understandings, and in this way, no horizon holds more importance than another. Fusion of horizon occurs when the researcher's horizon aligns with the horizon of what is being interpreted and is reflected upon to gain understanding (Lamb, 2012; Gadamer, 2012).

The fusion of horizons is not an end point, but in research terms, it is important to consider when to stop, or the whole process could continue indefinitely. Fleming et al (2003) suggest that this is often due to practicalities such as the resources and time available to undertake such a study.

3.6.6. Dialogue

Gadamer recognises the primacy of spoken language over written language and suggests that knowledge arises from logical discussion created through dialogue between the interpreter's pre-understanding and the text (Lamb, 2006; Austgard, 2013). Therefore, pre-understanding guides questioning and conversation, shaping the reader's understanding through the written interpretation of what has been said (Gadamer, 1989).

This dialectical movement is an interpretational movement back and forth in the text, forming part of the process within the hermeneutic circle. The dialectical movement is not only in relation to the whole and parts of the text, but also relates to the communication between the researcher's pre-understanding and the text (Austgard, 2013). Gadamer (2012) discusses a 'play' of dialogue within the text, which naturally arises within a conversation or between a reader and the text. The players are immersed within it, but not every play is the same. Each has its own spirit, which is expressed in the rules and orders confining its movement to a particular 'playing field'. The play is everything; the play itself, the players and the audience. The play is the subject and is independent of any audience. But it is only through them that the play can be represented (Gadamer, 2012). The researcher does not see the play as an object but becomes part of it, becoming totally absorbed. If this does not happen, the game will still be seen as an object, and the researcher will misunderstand the truth. Gadamer defines this transformative process as 'evidence of truth' (Gadamer, 2012, p. 488).

3.7 Summary

In this chapter, Gadamer's philosophical hermeneutics has been presented as the theoretical framework underpinning this study. Gadamer's philosophical hermeneutics (2012) offers key concepts that provide the foundation for an interpretive hermeneutic approach, guiding the exploration of developing understanding and meaning. While his philosophy establishes the ontological and epistemological orientation of the research, it does not offer a methodological approach. Consequently, the methodological approach adopted has been informed by further study and will be outlined in detail in the next chapter.

The purpose of this study is to gain an understanding and meaning of the APNP role viewed through a whole-systems lens that incorporates the perspectives of service providers and service users. To achieve this, the research objectives focus on three dimensions: APNPs' reflections on their own role, the perspectives of multidisciplinary colleagues named 'others', and the exploration of the experiences of parents who have engaged with APNP service delivery. The aim and objectives align closely with Gadamer's hermeneutic philosophy, which emphasises interpretation through dialogue and the development of understanding.

By placing the study within this interpretive paradigm, the research is set to yield nuanced insights into the APNP role and its importance within the broader healthcare system. The methodological approach will be detailed in Chapter 4.

CHAPTER FOUR – Method

4.1 Introduction

Chapter 3 explored Gadamer's (2012) philosophical hermeneutic framework, which examines the possibility of understanding. While Gadamer (2012) discusses how to develop a deeper understanding of a text, he does not provide a specific method for doing so (Austgard, 2013). His main aim is to highlight conditions that promote understanding within the interpretative tradition, an aim not intended for scientific investigation, typically associated with the positivist paradigm, but rather as 'being-in-the-world' (Debasay, Naden & Slettebo, 2008). This presents a challenge for novice hermeneutic researchers, who need to find a structured approach to guide their research. Van Manen (1997) agrees that developing an approach to guide research is essential. However, Van Manen (1997) argues that no fixed method or foolproof set of techniques exists for interpreting and understanding human experience. Both Koch (1996) and Van Manen (1997) emphasise the importance of reflecting on the method chosen to ensure the approach used to facilitate interpretation can be justified.

This chapter therefore discusses the method selected for this study, detailing the reasons and influences that led me to adopt Gadamer's philosophical hermeneutics (Gadamer, 2012). As no single definitive method exists for developing understanding, the approach used is based on the method offered by Fleming *et al.*, (2003), which is congruent with Gadamer's hermeneutic philosophy.

Although alternative methods exist, such as Colaizzi's (1978), an interpretative, step-by-step approach would need to be modified to align with Gadamer's philosophy. Colaizzi's (1978) method supports Heideggerian phenomenological research and recommends returning to participants to confirm findings. However, this conflicts with Gadamer's philosophical hermeneutics, which emphasises the researcher's uncovering of understanding through a fusion of horizons, without being influenced by participants' views. Therefore, Colaizzi's (1978) approach is not regarded as a purist perspective. Koch (1996) also distinguished between Husserl's phenomenology and Heidegger's hermeneutics. Koch (1996) conducted research applying three Gadamerian concepts, but upon further evaluation, a limited connection was identified between Gadamer's work and the concepts used; thus, the method is not appropriate.

Fleming *et al.*, (2003) propose a method for conducting a Gadamerian-based study, demonstrating a thorough approach by clearly separating phenomenology and hermeneutics to avoid confusion between the two. As native German speakers, Fleming *et al.*, (2003) translated Gadamer's 1990 work, **Truth and Method**, originally written in German, to establish a shared understanding of its meaning. This was to avoid misconceptions or assumptions arising from previous translations that could be misleading. This approach

provided me with a systematic framework to guide my study. This methodological approach will now be discussed in the following sections.

In presenting this chapter and beyond, the thesis is predominantly written in a formal, academic style. However, having identified Fleming *et al.*'s (2003) hermeneutic approach as the guiding method, it was necessary to acknowledge my own role within the interpretive process. Accordingly, in sections where I refer directly to my actions, decisions, or reflections as a researcher, I have intentionally adopted the first-person voice. This choice is consistent with qualitative hermeneutic inquiry, in which the researcher's positionality and reflexive engagement are integral to the analysis (Koch, 2006; Fleming *et al.*, 2003). Using the first person allows transparency in describing the practical steps undertaken, acknowledges the influence of my pre-understandings, and situates my role within the dialogical process through which understanding was developed. In this way, the methodological approach remains faithful to Gadamer's hermeneutics, ensuring openness, reflexivity, and the continual unfolding of meaning.

4.2 Rationale for use of the Gadamerian-based research method of Fleming *et al.*, (2003)

As identified in Chapter 3, Gadamer's contribution to the field of hermeneutics is primarily philosophical. However, he does not entirely dismiss the use of method and offers key concepts to support his philosophy. Gadamer considers that to reach an understanding, a systematic and methodical approach is required (Gadamer, 2012). By adopting a method recommended by other authors and deemed trustworthy, the method used by Fleming *et al.*, (2003) was selected.

Fleming *et al.*, (2003) offer a method congruent with hermeneutic research. One of the reasons for choosing this methodical approach is that the aim of the study is clearly congruent with the hermeneutic task, and Fleming *et al.*, (2003) offer a logical and structured means for a novice researcher to gain understanding through the interpretation of conversations with participants. Thus, it enables the researcher to enter the hermeneutic circle and achieve a fusion of horizons, once understanding has been realised between the movement from the whole to the individual parts and from the individual parts back to the whole in accordance with Gadamer's ideal. Fleming *et al.*'s, (2003) methodological approach is rooted in the concepts outlined by Gadamer's philosophical hermeneutics (2012) of language, culture, tradition, horizon, pre-understanding, the hermeneutic circle, fusion of horizons, and dialogue. It provides an accurate understanding of these concepts, thus offering a practical application of his philosophical ideas.

Fleming *et al.*, (2003) highlight concerns that there can be a misconception between phenomenological and hermeneutic research, with researchers frequently blurring the

boundaries between the two, causing confusion and inappropriate methodologies being utilised that are not congruent with the research aim. In 2017, In 2018, Fleming and Robb conducted a systematic critique of published studies that claimed to employ their Gadamerian-based research method. Across the period 2003–2017, they identified 362 citations referencing this approach. However, closer examination revealed significant inconsistencies in how the method was represented and applied. Of these, 163 studies made only cursory reference to the method, citing it in passing without substantive engagement. A further 16 articles misrepresented the approach, conflating Gadamerian hermeneutics with phenomenological traditions and thereby obscuring its philosophical distinctiveness. An additional 117 studies offered only partial identification of the method, failing to demonstrate a coherent application of its principles. Strikingly, only 60 studies provided sufficient detail to evidence meaningful methodological use (Fleming and Robb, 2018).

This analysis underscores a persistent challenge in the field: while Gadamer's hermeneutic philosophy is widely cited, its methodological translation into research practice is often superficial, inconsistent, or conceptually blurred. The findings from Fleming and Robb (2018) highlight the need for greater methodological rigour and transparency when operationalising philosophical frameworks, particularly in interpretive research traditions where the distinction between ontology, epistemology, and method is critical.

Dowling (2007) also found that boundaries between philosophy and method in research are often blurred, resulting in a multitude of ideas. However, Dowling (2007) has also been criticised for adopting a constructivist phenomenological stance, embracing broad philosophical and sociological positions rather than making a clear distinction between phenomenology and hermeneutics.

A critical review of studies claiming to employ a Gadamerian philosophical hermeneutic framework was undertaken (See Chapter 2, Table 4), with the outcomes presented in Appendix 2. This review was particularly valuable in developing and applying an understanding of the complexities inherent in applying philosophical hermeneutics to research. It revealed persistent confusion among researchers regarding the distinctions between the philosophical frameworks and methodological approaches of phenomenology and hermeneutics, with many studies demonstrating only partial or superficial engagement. Such findings highlight the challenges of operationalising philosophical traditions in a methodologically coherent manner.

Given this context, adopting Fleming *et al's.*, (2003) methodological approach is justified as both suitable and reliable. Their framework provides a practical way to translate Gadamer's hermeneutic philosophy, an interpretive paradigm rooted in ontology and epistemology, into a feasible research method. This, in turn, provides the necessary methodological clarity to ensure that Gadamer's focus on dialogue, interpretation, and the creation of understanding and meaning is effectively realised in this study.

4.3 The Research Method of Fleming *et al.*, (2003)

Fleming *et al.*, (2003) outlined a five-step method: first, determining the research question; second, identifying pre-understandings; third, enhancing understanding through dialogue with participants; fourth, deepening understanding through dialogue with the text; and finally, establishing trustworthiness. These will now each be discussed in more detail.

4.3.1 Step 1: Deciding upon a research question

In any research, it is essential to align the research question with appropriate methodological frameworks, as this is key to planning and executing a successful study (Parahoo, 2014). Research questions often originate from vague ideas, which may stem from clinical practice interests or discussions with colleagues (Gerrish and Lacey, 2010). Using Gadamerian concepts, this research aims to understand and interpret the APNP's role from a whole systems perspective of service providers and service users. Gadamer (2012) emphasises that well-formulated questions open up possibilities for understanding and stresses the importance of selecting the right questions to develop the hermeneutic situation. Therefore, the initial question shapes the entire research process. Gadamer (2012) notes that understanding requires active questioning in any conversation, and that there is a delicate balance between the two, a balance that is fundamental to hermeneutic research.

Fleming *et al.*, (2003) recognise the importance of the research question and its alignment with the aims of interpretative hermeneutics, ensuring that any data collected and conclusions drawn (Fleming and Maloney, 1996) will contribute to the development of new knowledge (Todres and Wheeler, 2000; Austgard, 2013). Research following the Gadamerian hermeneutic tradition must ensure that developing a deep understanding of the phenomenon is possible (Fleming *et al.*, 2003). As a nurse educator at a Scottish university with an interest in advanced practice across Scotland, and how the role of the APNP is understood has always been of interest, especially after discussions with students about their role and given the limited and mostly positivist literature available (Bonsall and Cheater, 2008; Begley *et al.*, 2014; Newhouse *et al.*, 2011; Evans *et al.*, 2020; Fothergill *et al.*, 2022).

The overarching aim of this study is to gain an understanding and meaning of the APNP role from a whole-systems perspective, incorporating the views of service providers and service users through engagement with three distinct stakeholder groups. This aim was established prior to selecting the methodology. Once the aim was decided upon, it was judged to be most appropriately aligned with a Gadamerian philosophical hermeneutic approach (Gadamer, 2012), after investigating a variety of other approaches as outlined in Chapter 2 (Table 3), as Gadamerian concepts favour interpretation, dialogue, and the possibility of developing meaning and understanding. To ensure the robustness of the research design, an extensive literature review was initially conducted before starting the study to justify the research

question. A detailed research proposal was subsequently prepared, and ethical approval was sought and granted (see Appendix 3), thereby ensuring that the study was conducted in accordance with established academic, professional and research standards (Department of Health, 2005; Health Research Authority, 2017).

4.3.2 Step 2: Identification of pre-understandings

Gadamer's (2012) philosophical hermeneutics emphasises the necessity of being aware of one's horizon and identifying pre-understandings before engaging in research. Gadamer (2012) advocates for the deliberate conscious recognition of pre-understandings as a means of acknowledging biases, thereby allowing dialogue and textual interpretation to "be present in all its newness and thus be able to assert its own truth" (Gadamer, 2012, p. 237). Central to Gadamer's perspective is the notion that pre-understandings often surface when challenged or provoked, and that researchers must remain receptive to hidden or unexamined pre-understandings, ensuring that such biases do not limit the horizon of understanding (Fleming *et al.*, 2003).

My horizon in relation to this study was shaped by my prior knowledge of the APNP role, informed by extensive nursing experience as an adult and paediatric-trained nurse, ward manager, practice development role, health visitor, and programme lead of advanced practice education within a Scottish HEI. These professional roles, alongside engagement with students, awareness of health policy agendas, and immersion in relevant literature, formed the pre-understandings I brought to the research. Within Gadamer's philosophical hermeneutics (2012), such pre-understandings are not bracketed or set aside, as Husserl's phenomenology (2012) would suggest, but acknowledged as integral to the interpretive process. To ignore them would risk misjudging the meaning of participants' accounts. Instead, recognising these assumptions allowed me to enter the hermeneutic circle (Schleiermacher, 1998), in which understanding develops through the dynamic interplay between the researcher and participant horizons. This reflexive engagement, revisited throughout the study, ensured that my positionality was transparent and that a new understanding of the APNP role could emerge dialogically.

Fleming *et al.*, (2003) advocate the systematic use of recordings to provoke and critically engage with pre-understandings, consistent with Gadamer's philosophical hermeneutics (Gadamer, 2012). At the outset, a recording was undertaken to capture the researcher's initial pre-understandings of the phenomenon under investigation. Following the completion and transcription of all conversations in each distinct group, a subsequent recording and transcript were undertaken to articulate emergent understandings. Crucially, the initial recording must be revisited during immersion with the conversational data and throughout analysis, ensuring that I, as the researcher, remain reflexively aware of prior assumptions. This iterative process, contrasting early horizons with insights gained through dialogue, enables recognition of the

limitations of initial perspectives while opening possibilities for newness and deeper understanding. Fidelity to this principle safeguards against a restricted horizon and sustains the continual emergence of meaning, thereby reinforcing the hermeneutic commitment to reflexivity and openness (Geanellos, 1999). Table 8 below (also see Appendix 6) shows the timelines of the pre- and post-conversation recordings, relating to the themes generated from these, as shown in Appendix 6, with timelines included.

Pre-understanding was provoked throughout this study, as identified above, and is shown below (Table 8 below, also Appendix 6). After each conversation within each group, the conversations were transcribed, and an analysis for each group was conducted once all group participants' conversations were complete.

Table 8: Pre-understanding Table

Table 8 (See Appendix 6 and this chapter) Pre-understanding Table

Appendix 6	A generic overview of my pre-understanding of the APNP role carried out prior to starting study with a colleague
Appendix 7	General overview and influences of pre-understanding of the APNP role (what I understood to influence me and my understanding of the role) prior to starting my research conversations
Appendix 8a	Pre-understanding of APNP role (undertaken prior to conversations with APNPs), undertaken in 2015
Appendix 8b	APNPs post conversation subthemes (undertaken after all 8 conversations with APNPs) in 2016
Appendix 8c	Fusion of Horizon for APNPs (3 main themes developed after analysis of conversations with APNPs) initially in 2016, then reviewed in 2023
Appendix 9a	My pre-understanding of Parents thoughts about APNPs (undertaken prior to conversations with parents) in 2015
Appendix 9b	Parents post conversation subthemes (undertaken after all conversations with parents) in 2016
Appendix 9c	Fusion of Horizon for Parents (3 main themes developed after analysis of conversations with parents) initially in 2016, then reviewed in 2023/24
Figure 7 page 90	Pre-understanding of 'Others' (undertaken prior to conversations with APNPs), undertaken in 2015
Figure 8 page 91	'Others' post conversation subthemes (undertaken after all conversation with 'Others')
Figure 10 page 92	Fusion of Horizon for 'Others' (3 main themes developed after analysis of conversations with 'Others') initially in 2015/16 and then reviewed in 2023/24
Appendix 10	Fusion of Horizon overall (developed after analysis of all conversations) developed in 2023/24

4.3.3 Step 3: Gaining understanding through dialogue with participants

Fleming *et al.*, (2003) argue that the term 'gaining understanding ' more appropriately captures the hermeneutic process than the conventional notion of 'data collection'. Within hermeneutics, knowledge is not extracted but emerges through a dialectical movement generated in conversation and text (Austgard, 2013). This movement is characterised by a continual oscillation between the whole and its parts, enabling the researcher to enter and re-enter the hermeneutic circle. Through such engagement, conversation becomes the medium of immersion into the subject matter, facilitating the unfolding of meaning and the achievement of deeper understanding.

Gadamer (2012) and Smythe and Spence (2012) emphasise that dialogue is the essential medium through which researchers can come to understand others' perspectives. Significantly, dialogue extends beyond spoken conversation to include the engagement between reader and text, enabling immersion in the subject matter and the unfolding of meaning. Within hermeneutics, this process of dialogical engagement facilitates the fusion of horizons, whereby the researcher's pre-understandings encounter and are reshaped by the perspectives revealed through conversation and text (Fleming *et al.*, 2003; Gadamer, 2012; Smythe and Spence, 2012). Fusion occurs when one's horizon is expanded through dialogue, leading to the conscious recognition of new understanding. Van Manen (1997) further argues that such conversations should be undertaken directly by the researcher rather than delegated, as this personal engagement is integral to cultivating deeper insight into the phenomenon under investigation.

Thus, conversation is considered the primary method of data collection in hermeneutic research as it allows for participants' descriptions and stories to be explored, illuminated, and probed (Kvale, 1996; Wimpenny and Gass, 2000). So, what would traditionally be known as a research interview under other methodologies is now regarded as a conversation with hermeneutic-based research, as it aligns with the aims of hermeneutic studies (Laverty, 2003; Holroyd, 2008). These conversations adopt a flexible, less-structured, more in-depth approach to achieve a deeper understanding. Conversations evolve naturally and should be conducted through active listening, questioning, and receiving responses. The hermeneutic conversation is interpretive and not guided by predetermined question sets, allowing the meaning of the dialogue to be co-created. By engaging directly with participants, the researcher entered into dialogical encounters that allowed new understandings of the APNP role to emerge, consistent with Gadamer's (2012) view that knowledge is generated through openness, reflexivity, and the continual unfolding of horizons.

As a novice researcher, this was quite challenging, so a 'pilot' conversation was conducted with a colleague who knew the APNP role before any conversations began, to test whether I

could facilitate a discussion that evolved naturally. This conversation was not included in the study findings.

4.3.4 Step 4: Gaining understanding through dialogue with text

Fleming *et al.*, (2003) operationalised Gadamer's philosophical hermeneutics (2012) by recommending that researchers return transcripts or preliminary interpretations to participants, arguing that such feedback strengthens reflexivity and supports the hermeneutic circle. However, this position is contested. Scholars such as Smythe and Spence (2012) emphasise that Gadamerian inquiry is grounded in openness to dialogue with text and tradition, rather than procedural validation through participant checking. Similarly, van Manen (1997) cautions that delegating or re-checking with participants risks reducing hermeneutic engagement to a technical exercise, asserting that the researcher's direct and personal involvement in conversations is essential for cultivating deeper understanding. These differing perspectives highlight a methodological tension: whether participant feedback is necessary for rigour or risks misaligning hermeneutic inquiry with phenomenological practices of verification.

In this study, transcripts were not returned to participants for validation. This decision was informed by Gadamer's (2012) recognition that one's horizon always shapes understanding and that each individual interprets differently. Within philosophical hermeneutics, the aim is not to seek participant confirmation of the researcher's interpretations, but rather to remain open to the dialogical process through which meaning unfolds. To return transcripts for validation would imply that participants could authoritatively confirm or deny the researcher's understanding, which is inconsistent with Gadamer's view that understanding is never fixed but continually evolving. My role, therefore, was to engage reflexively with the conversations and the texts, acknowledging my pre-understandings while allowing new horizons to emerge, rather than seeking validation of interpretation from participants.

Fleming *et al.*, (2003) propose a four-stage process for achieving understanding through dialogue with the text, emphasising the interpretive nature of research conversations. Their framework highlights the importance of identifying expressions within dialogue as a means of accessing meaning. Importantly, these stages may be undertaken either sequentially or in a more iterative, non-linear manner.

- Firstly, initial textual analysis involves a close reading of the text to uncover meaning embedded within language and expression. This process facilitates the identification of emergent themes that begin to shape interpretation.
- Secondly, a sentence-level analysis follows, in which individual sentences are examined to elicit their specific meanings. From this, themes are further developed

and subsequently interrogated by juxtaposing them against the researcher's pre-understandings, which have been systematically recorded and transcribed.

- Thirdly, contextual integration requires that each sentence be considered in relation to the text as a whole. This movement between the parts and the whole constitutes the hermeneutic circle—a metaphor central to hermeneutic philosophy. As Gadamer (2012) argues, understanding is never achieved in isolation but rather through a continual oscillation between detail and the whole, in which the interpreter's horizon of understanding is expanded through engagement with the text. Crucially, the hermeneutic circle cannot be fully realised without this continual oscillation towards the whole.
- Fourth, completion of the hermeneutic circle is achieved through the identification of passages that embody shared understanding between researcher and participant. This stage provides deeper insight into the phenomenon under investigation, in this case, the role of the APNP.

By placing Fleming *et al's.*, (2003) framework within the wider hermeneutic tradition, it is clear that their approach operationalises Gadamer's philosophical insights into a practical research strategy. The focus on dialogue, pre-understanding, and the dynamic movement between part and whole reflects the epistemological view that meaning is co-constructed rather than solely discovered. Therefore, the process not only clarifies textual meaning but also highlights the relational aspect of interpretation, where the researcher and participant participate in a shared act of understanding.

4.3.4.1 Application of Fleming *et al.*, (2003) steps and the development of analysis and interpretation

Following each conversation within the participant groups, interviews were transcribed verbatim, and analysis commenced once all conversations within a group were complete. The analytic process engaged with the transcribed texts by considering the whole in relation to its parts, and then reflecting from the parts back to the whole. In this way, individual segments of the text informed the identification of subthemes. In contrast, the overall text contributed to the broader themes presented in the *fusion-of-horizons* chapters for each participant group. Fleming *et al.*, (2003) describe this as transcending the horizon to achieve a deeper understanding of the phenomenon, in this case, the APNP role within NHS Scotland.

This process was demanding, yet it required openness to new knowledge and a willingness to challenge my pre-understandings. Conversations with colleagues and my supervisory team, alongside the maintenance of a reflective diary, supported this reflexive engagement and facilitated the development of understanding. Through these practices, my interpretation of both service users' and service providers' perspectives began to transform. Regular reflection

on the conversations, together with re-reading my reflexive accounts, enabled me to re-enter the hermeneutic circle, moving iteratively between part and whole as understanding evolved (Schleiermacher, 1998).

In undertaking this analysis, I considered the influences on my interpretation and how new knowledge emerged through the continual broadening of my horizon. Gadamer's philosophical hermeneutics emphasises that individuals, shaped by distinct cultural and historical contexts, inevitably understand differently, and that no single interpretation can claim finality (Gadamer, 2012). It is therefore essential to remain open, transparent, and explicit in the methodological process so that others can see how my horizon developed in dialogue with the three participant groups, and how my pre-understandings may have influenced interpretation (Austgard, 2013). This was addressed in the study by systematically recording and reflecting on my pre-understandings at each stage, acknowledging what I knew, what I thought I knew, and recognising the new knowledge that emerged through the interpretive process.

The analytical process was guided by Gadamer's philosophical hermeneutics (Gadamer, 2012), emphasising language, horizons, pre-understanding, the hermeneutic circle, fusion of horizons, and dialogue. Each stage of interpretation was shaped by these concepts, ensuring that meaning was approached as dynamic, reflexive, and co-constructed rather than as static data.

Before commencing the study, I pre-recorded an initial general pre-understanding of the APNP role (see Appendix 6), providing an overview of general knowledge about the role and serving as a pilot for how to carry out and record pre-understandings. While waiting for ethical approval and access to the eight health boards, I completed another pre-understanding as I had engaged with more literature at this stage (see Appendix 7), offering a more specific overview of my understanding and influences related to the APNP role at that point in time. After gaining access to the health boards, and once I began planning the research conversations, I conducted a further pre-understanding recording for each of the three participant groups.

In the following pages of this thesis, the application of the analytical process used is demonstrated. Table 9 takes you through a step-by-step process, and then Figures 3 – 10 illustrate explicitly the process undertaken and how the subthemes and themes were developed for 'Others'. The information regarding pre-understandings, and post-conversation subtheme development, and emergent themes for APNPs is included in Appendices 8a-8c. For parents the same information is in Appendices 9a-c. Appendix 10 presents my final fusion of horizon for all three groups, which is further detailed in Chapter 8 (fusion of horizon) and Chapter 9 (concluding remarks and making a difference).

The following sections illustrate how I applied the analysis and interpretation process throughout this study.

Immersion in the Texts (Conversations). Interviews were transcribed verbatim to preserve participants' language, recognising that meaning is embedded in words rather than abstracted from them. Transcripts were read repeatedly to gain familiarity and listened to alongside the recordings, with initial meanings highlighted in colour-coded annotations on the transcripts. Each transcript was treated as a dialogical text rather than raw data, and printed transcripts (sentences, stories or paragraphs) were arranged into thematic groupings to support the development of fusion of horizons.

Acknowledging Pre-Understandings. Consistent with Gadamer's (2012) recognition that interpretation begins from one's horizon, I recorded my personal assumptions, professional background, and expectations on audio tape, which I later transcribed and supplemented with a reflexive journal. These reflections were revisited throughout analysis to ensure transparency and to acknowledge how pre-understandings shaped, but did not determine, emerging interpretations.

Entering the Hermeneutic Circle. Analysis proceeded through iterative movement between parts (individual statements, sentences, or stories) and the whole (the essence of the APNP role and the story being told to). This cyclical engagement allowed openness to newness and ensured that understanding evolved, rather than being prematurely fixed.

Dialogical Engagement with the Text. Transcripts were approached as conversations that continued beyond the interview encounter. Reflective notes and ideas that arose afterwards were incorporated, and interpretive questions were posed to the text: What is being revealed here? How does this challenge or extend my horizon? This dialogical stance ensured openness to participants' perspectives and resisted premature closure of meaning.

Fusion of Horizons. New understanding emerged through the integration of participants' horizon, their lived experiences of the APNP role, with my own professional and scholarly horizon. This fusion produced insights that neither horizon could achieve alone, exemplifying Gadamer's (2012) notion of understanding as dialogical and transformative.

Identification of Key Themes. Themes were not imposed but surfaced through interpretive dialogue. Attention was given to how language, tradition, culture, and context shaped participants' accounts. Themes remained provisional and were revisited as understanding developed, reflecting the evolving nature of hermeneutic interpretation.

Reflexive Documentation. A research diary was maintained to record evolving interpretations, emotional responses, and methodological decisions. Reflexivity was used to

critically appraise how positionality influenced the analytic process, ensuring transparency and rigour.

Development of Understanding. Insights were synthesised across participant groups (APNPs, others, parents) and situated within the broader cultural and organisational context of NHS Scotland. This process highlighted how the study contributes new knowledge to the APNP role, addressing the paucity of evidence in the literature and extending understanding through the hermeneutic commitment to openness, dialogue, and the continual unfolding of meaning and understanding.

This summary of step-by-step analytic framework (Table 9), and pictures below which demonstrate an honest and open process to interpretation and development of understanding:

Table 9: Analytical framework

Step-by-step process for each of the three groups of participants.

Immersion in the texts (conversations)	<p>Transcription of interviews were made verbatim to preserve participants' language.</p> <p>Transcripts were read repeatedly to gain familiarity and begin identifying initial meanings. These were highlighted in colours.</p> <p>Each transcript was treated as a dialogical text, not raw data, recognising that meaning is embedded in language. Colour coded transcripts were printed off and arranged into themes to help development of fusion of horizon. See picture 1 – 3 below.</p>
Acknowledging Pre-Understandings	<p>Recording of personal assumptions, professional background, and current knowledge, or expectations on audio tape and then transcribed and use of a reflexive journal (picture 5 below demonstrates how my pre-understandings were represented once recorded and transcribed).</p> <p>Revisit these reflections throughout analysis to ensure transparency. Recognise how these pre-understandings shape interpretation and new understanding.</p>
Entering the Hermeneutic Circle	<p>This was done by moving iteratively between parts (individual statements, sentences or stories) and the whole (the essence gained and phenomenon of the APNP role). (Immersion in pictures 2-4 iteratively on at least 2 separate occasions).</p> <p>Allowing my mind to remain open to newness and understanding through this cyclical process, recognising that interpretation evolves over time.</p>
Dialogical Engagement with the Text	<p>I approached transcripts as a conversation that continued beyond the conversation. Reflecting on notes and ideas that came to me afterwards.</p>

	<p>Ask interpretive questions of the text: What is being revealed here? How does this challenge or extend my horizon? (Referring back constantly to Picture 5 pre-understandings).</p> <p>Remain open to participants' perspectives, resisting premature closure.</p>
Fusion of Horizons	<p>Integration of participants' horizons (their own experiences of APNPs) with the researcher's horizon (professional and scholarly pre-understandings).</p> <p>New meaning emerges through this fusion, producing insights that neither horizon could achieve alone.</p>
Identification of Key Themes	<p>Themes were not imposed but allowed to surface through interpretive dialogue.</p> <p>Focus remained on how language, tradition, culture, and context (participants background) shaped participants' accounts.</p> <p>Themes became provisional and revisited as understanding developed.</p>
Reflexive Documentation	<p>Maintenance of a research diary to record evolving interpretations, emotional responses, and methodological decisions.</p> <p>Use this reflexivity to critically appraise how positionality influences the analytic process.</p>
Development of Understanding	<p>Synthesising insights across participant groups (APNPs, colleagues, parents).</p> <p>Situating findings within the broader cultural and organisational context of NHS Scotland.</p> <p>Highlighting how the study contributes new knowledge to APNP role, addressing the paucity of evidence in the literature.</p>

The following pictures are an example of how the development of subthemes and themes came about:

Figure 3: Example of original transcript from 'Others'

<p>SP 1 I think that um, they have experience in terms of what they have done as a nurse, and often as senior nurses that more junior medical staff haven't yet got, and therefore they are able to bring that at an early stage in their development as a nurse practitioner, and therefore they add the medical skills they haven't got yet and as a mix, that's pretty powerful. Umm, they are often a bit older as well, compared to our junior medical staff and therefore they have a bit more life experience which I think is very when you are looking at the fact that we are not just dealing with a patient, we are dealing with extended family and that in itself can be quite complex. And <u>actually</u> having someone who has worked as a member of nursing staff has understood the skills you need to deal with often psychosocial aspects, that perhaps more junior medical staff haven't yet gained yet – is hugely beneficial. Em, I think as well often when they have been working as senior staff nurses, they are very aware of autonomy and they're quite happy to work independently but with good support. And <u>again</u> that's a nice skill to have in terms of being able to work in a busy unit and I certainly know with any of the 4 APNPs who work in the unit that I'm based in are there. I know they're trustworthy, they will go off and see their patients, sort of feedback how things are going, we'll have an interchange of any concerns, we know that we can speak</p>	<p>an original transcript where, once transcribed, immersion takes place in the text, occurring by reading text and listening to audio tapes. Part of transcript from 'Others'.</p>
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Figure 4: Initial meanings colour coded

<p>SP 1 I think that um, they have experience in terms of what they have done as a nurse, and often as senior nurses that more junior medical staff haven't yet got, and therefore they are able to bring that <u>at an early stage in their development as a nurse practitioner, and therefore they add the medical skills they haven't got yet and as a mix, that's pretty powerful.</u> Umm, they are often a bit older as well, compared to our junior medical staff and therefore they have a bit more life <u>experience</u> which I think is very when you are looking at the fact that we are not just dealing with a patient, we are dealing with extended family and that in itself can be quite complex. And <u>actually</u> having <u>someone who has worked as a member of nursing staff has understood the skills you need to deal with often psychosocial aspects, that perhaps more junior medical staff haven't yet gained yet</u> – is hugely beneficial. Em, I think as well often when they have been working as senior staff nurses, they are very <u>aware of autonomy and they're quite happy to work independently but with good support.</u> And <u>again</u> that's a nice skill to have in terms of being able to work in a busy unit and I certainly know with any of the 4 APNPs who work in the unit that I'm based in are there. I know they're <u>trustworthy, they will go off and see their patients, sort of feedback how things are going, we'll have an interchange of any concerns, we know that we can speak</u></p>	<p>demonstrating reading with initial meanings colour coded annotations marked to start development of the parts – initial reading of sentences or words.</p>
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Figure 5: Colour coding for initial subthemes.

draft chapter – 'Others' Analysis chapter.

SP1

they're an absolute integral part of the team. They're very reliable, we have consistency in their approach and their availability is very beneficial to us

they do a lot of follow-up of their patients and therefore we think we are getting a really good service from them

they bridge the gap between nursing and medical staff in terms of the skill base that they bring

Skills: have experience in terms of what they have done as a nurse... and often as senior nurses that more junior medical staff haven't yet got and therefore they are able to bring that at an early stage in their development as a nurse practitioner, and therefore they add the medical skills they haven't got yet and as a mid, that's pretty powerful, often a bit older as well, compared to our junior medical staff and therefore they have a bit more life experience

we are not just dealing with a patient, we are dealing with extended family and that in itself can be quite complex.

having someone who has worked as a member of nursing staff has understood the skills you need to deal with often psychosocial aspects, that perhaps more junior medical staff haven't yet gained yet – is hugely beneficial

aware of autonomy and they're quite happy to work independently but with good support. And again that's a nice skill to have in terms of being able to work in a busy unit

trustworthy, they will go off and see their patients, sort of feedback how things are going, we'll have an interchange of any concerns, we know that we can speak about it, but that actually they are working independently

that when things are busy, things are moving

fundamental skills, I mean they bring many to the table but reliability and consistency are definitely up there

need to keep their skills up because they are not doing a job that they have done for years and years, and therefore they have got to a level where there isn't a huge amount left to learn, it's about continuing to do it well.

that's not always necessarily reflected in junior members of the team because they may not have got to the point yet of knowing definitely that they are going to go into paediatrics but they don't know what they don't know yet, and therefore we are steps further along than our APNP staff

demonstrates colour coding for initial subthemes. Continued on a second reading and process repeated, and these were then important to a document (see picture 4 below) where all participants parts were put together into theme

Figure 6: Combination of quotes from all the research participants

demonstrates a combination of quotes from all the research participants in this group which are meaningful and put into themes.

Figure 7: My pre-understandings of 'others' prior to starting my conversations

Figure 8: 'Others' post conversation subthemes

After all conversations had taken place

Figure 8: Immersion in text, and coding from subthemes

The image shows a handwritten page titled "Themes" with three columns: "APNs", "Others", and "Parents".

- APNs:**
 - 1. APNP model of nursing & alignment to current nursing education approaches.
 - 2. Address communication skills.
 - 3. What it needs to be on APNP - time autonomy & role (no role change but also working in primary care).
 - 4. Challenges & expectations of APNP role in the future & education on role - or change role transition service delivery.
 - 5. **TO BE A NURSE**
 - 6. Boundaries professional identity.
 - 7. **Professional identity**
 - 8. Link Autonomy - why do nurses or how do nurses interpret autonomy or part of profession. Lack of autonomy - interaction with various roles.
- Others:**
 - 1. Bridging the gap
 - 2. Challenges of APNP for
 - 3. Local scope to APNP
 - 4. APNP qualities
 - 5. ~~Supervision~~
 - 6. **Service needs**
 - 7. **Bridging the gap**
 - 8. Discharge that APNP are almost completely back still steps with them.
 - 9. **Disparity between APNP & medicine - boundaries & challenges in integrated care.**
 - 10. **Disparity with APNP in your unit or system!**
- Parents:**
 - 1. Importance of value attributed in the role
 - 2. Communication skills & difference that makes in care experience
 - 3. Different experiences in APNP approach to care.
 - 4. Peace of mind easier access shared decision making feelings of isolation confidence + trust Bridging the gap
 - 5. **Personal communication added value**
 - 6. **Advocacy**
 - 7. **A holistic approach higher level of care safe 'more'**

demonstrates how after immersion in text, and coding from subthemes as above, I then wrote down ideas which formulated from the stories told when thinking about the emergent themes and went from the part to the whole story and back to the part again. These themes changed over time until I decided on the story and the themes presented in the text today.

Figure 9: 3 themes of my Fusion of Horizon for 'Others'

demonstrates the 3 themes of my Fusion of Horizon for 'Others' which were formed after considering the subthemes I had developed, and capture an essence of these subthemes which were important to the research.

4.3.5 Step 5: Establishing Trustworthiness

In research underpinned by Gadamer's philosophical hermeneutics, trustworthiness is not about eliminating subjectivity but about demonstrating that interpretation has been conducted with integrity, reflexivity, and openness to dialogue. Trustworthiness is crucial because the research does not aim for objectivity in the positivist sense, but for credibility and authenticity in interpretation. It reassures the reader that the findings represent a genuine fusion of horizons, rather than a researcher-imposed narrative. Thus, trustworthiness functions as the methodological counterpart to Gadamer's philosophical commitment to dialogue, pre-understanding, and the hermeneutic circle

Sandelowski (1993) asserts that validity and rigour in qualitative studies should be understood in terms of *trustworthiness*, ensuring that research is transparent and auditable. This stands in contrast to positivist traditions, where 'truth' and 'value' are measured through reliability and validity (Tappen, 2011). Within qualitative inquiry, the responsibility for establishing rigour and trustworthiness rests with the researcher, who must demonstrate that the process and findings are credible and defensible (Rolfe, 2006).

This perspective aligns closely with Gadamer's philosophical hermeneutics, where the presumption of truth is not grounded in objective measurement but in the openness of the interpreter to dialogue and the fusion of horizons (Gadamer, 2012). In Gadamerian terms, trustworthiness is established when the researcher acknowledges their pre-understandings, engages reflexively in the hermeneutic circle, and demonstrates that meaning has been co-constructed rather than imposed. Thus, the presumption of truth becomes part of the hermeneutic process itself, reinforcing transparency and audibility in interpretation.

Fleming *et al.*, (2003) operationalise this philosophical stance by embedding trustworthiness into their five step method. The final stage, completion of the hermeneutic circle, represents not only shared understanding between researcher and participant but also the culmination of a rigorous, reflexive process that embodies Gadamer's commitment to openness and dialogue. In this way, trustworthiness is not an external criterion applied to hermeneutic research but an intrinsic outcome of the interpretive process itself.

To establish trustworthiness and rigour in research, Guba and Lincoln (1989) propose a framework to ensure adherence to high standards. Koch (1996) and Grassley & Nelms (2008) have previously demonstrated the applicability of these criteria in Gadamerian-based studies examining the experiences of older patients within a hospital setting and the experience of maternal breast-feeding, respectively. Guba and Lincoln's (1989) framework provides a practical set of criteria: credibility, dependability, confirmability, and transferability that align closely with Gadamer's hermeneutic principles:

- Credibility in qualitative research refers to the extent to which findings authentically represent the phenomenon under investigation. While Guba and Lincoln (1989) equate credibility with internal validity in positivist paradigms, its application in hermeneutic inquiry is distinct, requiring faithful representation of participant perspectives (Fleming *et al.*, 2003). In this study, credibility was enhanced through the inclusion of verbatim quotations, allowing readers to evaluate the plausibility of interpretations (Austgard, 2013; Fleming *et al.*, 2003). This practice reflects Gadamerian hermeneutics, where methodological coherence and researcher responsiveness are central. Coherence was maintained by consistently aligning the Gadamerian framework with practical aspects of the study, while responsiveness was achieved by remaining open to participants' narratives and representing them with integrity (Laverty, 2003; Alsaigh and Coyne, 2021). Credibility was further strengthened through triangulation, including textual evidence, field diary entries, supervisory feedback, and debriefing sessions, providing multiple layers of reflexivity and ensuring the rigor and trustworthiness of the findings (Shenton, 2004).
- Transferability in qualitative research concerns the extent to which findings may resonate beyond the immediate study context. Rather than aiming for generalisability, this hermeneutic study sought to provide a nuanced, context-specific understanding of the APNP role from three perspectives. As Guba and Lincoln (1989) note, reproducing identical conditions across settings is inherently difficult, particularly within Gadamer's philosophy, where understanding is historically situated and shaped by the interpreter's horizon (Gadamer, 2012). Replication is therefore neither possible nor desirable; instead, value lies in the depth of insight achieved within context. Fleming *et al.*, (2003) argue that emphasis should be placed on the truthfulness of findings, demonstrated through transparency in methodological decisions, the inclusion of verbatim extracts, and situating interpretations within the hermeneutic circle. Such practices enable readers to judge plausibility and consider the relevance of findings to other settings. Thus, transferability is offered not as universal applicability but as contextual resonance, consistent with Gadamer's view of understanding as dialogical and historically situated.
- Auditability in qualitative research refers to the transparent tracing of the research process and the scrutiny of interpretive decisions. Unlike quantitative inquiry, where replication is possible, qualitative studies acknowledge that phenomena cannot be reproduced identically (Tappen, 2011). Auditability, therefore, requires systematic documentation of methodological and analytical choices, often through an audit trail that enables others to follow the researcher's reasoning (Koch, 2004; Lincoln and Guba, 1989). In this study, auditability was achieved by adhering to Fleming *et al.*'s, (2003) hermeneutic method, which operationalises Gadamer's emphasis on openness and reflexivity, making pre-understandings and interpretive decisions visible. A

research journal was maintained throughout to record daily decisions, reflexive insights, and methodological shifts, thereby ensuring coherence and transparency. Auditability thus functioned not only as a safeguard of rigour but also as a hermeneutic commitment to openness, dialogue, and truthfulness in interpretation.

- Confirmability in qualitative research refers to ensuring that findings are demonstrably grounded in participants' accounts rather than researcher bias. While Guba and Lincoln (1985) frame it as the qualitative counterpart to objectivity, its application in hermeneutic inquiry emphasises transparency and reflexivity. Although Fleming *et al.*, (2003) suggest returning transcripts to participants to enhance confirmability, others argue this is unnecessary in interpretive traditions, as understanding is dynamic and continually evolving (Webb, 2003; Mcconnell-Henry *et al.*, 2011; Gadamer, 2012). In this study, transcripts were not returned; instead, confirmability was established through methodological transparency, reflexive documentation, and situating analysis within the hermeneutic circle. The inclusion of verbatim extracts further demonstrates that findings are grounded in participants' narratives while acknowledging the interpretive role of the researcher. Thus, confirmability was achieved as a hermeneutic commitment to openness and truthfulness, rather than as a positivist requirement for replication or consensus.

Thus, Guba and Lincoln's (2003) framework provides trustworthiness and rigour criteria that reinforce Gadamer's philosophical hermeneutic (2012) commitments, and supports the method of Fleming *et al.*, (2003). Trustworthiness becomes both a philosophical and practical imperative: it ensures that hermeneutic research is rigorous, auditable, and credible, while remaining faithful to the interpretive, dialogical nature of understanding (Gadamer, 2012).

4.4 Research Considerations

Building on the method outlined by Fleming *et al.*, (2003), attention now turns to other key considerations, including ethical considerations for research participants, the nature of participants, recruitment and consent, sampling and recruitment, the conversation settings and reflexivity.

4.4.1 Ethical Considerations with Research Participants

Ethical standards in research have become more stringent over time (Johnson and Long, 2007). However, ethics should not be seen merely as external regulations but as fundamental to the very being and approach of inquiry (Lesham and Trafford, 2007). For nurse researchers, ethical principles are central to their professional identity, influencing their goals, methodological choices, and research path (Milton, 2013). This is especially important in

qualitative studies, where delicate issues often lead to complex ethical dilemmas (Streubert *et al.*, 2007).

International frameworks such as the Nuremberg Code (1949), the Declaration of Helsinki (1964, revised 2000), and national governance structures (Research Governance Framework, 2013) outline principles of non-maleficence, beneficence, justice, respect for persons, confidentiality, informed consent, and the right to withdraw (Gerrish and Lacey, 2010; Wang and Huch, 2000). These principles are not mere abstract obligations but active responsibilities within the dialogical space between researcher and participant. From a Gadamerian hermeneutic perspective, ethics is inseparable from understanding itself: dialogue, openness, and the fusion of horizons position ethical responsibility as intrinsic to interpretation. Fleming *et al.*, (2003) demonstrate how Gadamerian hermeneutics (Gadamer, 2012) can serve as a methodological approach, in which ethical practice develops through attentiveness to participants' voices, respect for autonomy, and co-creation of meaning.

4.4.2 The nature of the participants

In keeping with the Gadamerian hermeneutic emphasis on dialogue and the co-construction of meaning, careful consideration was given to the selection of participants in this study. The overarching aim was to deepen understanding of the APNP role within NHS Scotland by engaging with perspectives that together provide a rounded and multifaceted account of a role that remains sparsely reported in the literature. APNPs themselves were critical participants, offering insight into their perspectives on the role and its ongoing development. 'Others' working alongside APNPs, including nurse managers, nurse directors, medical consultants, and a staff nurse, contributed an alternative dimension, illuminating how the role is perceived and situated within the wider clinical domain. Finally, parents whose children had been cared for by an APNP were included, representing perhaps the most significant perspective, as their understanding of the role provides a unique and previously unexplored vantage point. By engaging with these three groups, the study sought to enact Gadamer's principle of the *fusion of horizons*, allowing diverse voices to enter into dialogue and thereby enriching the interpretive process.

4.4.3 Consent

In this study, informed consent was operationalised through transparent communication: tailored information sheets, adequate time for reflection, opportunities for clarification, and reaffirmation of consent at interview. Participants were reminded of their right to withdraw at any time, though none did so. While groups lacking full capacity for self-determination (e.g., children or those with diminished mental capacity) require heightened ethical consideration (Gerrish & Lacey, 2010), they were not included in this research. Beneficence was ensured by

minimising harm and maximising potential benefit, though ethical approval was delayed when the NRES committee sought clarification regarding parental involvement, mistakenly assuming children themselves were participants. Justice was upheld through fair recruitment processes, mediated via Paediatric Clinical Nurse Managers to avoid inappropriate targeting of vulnerable groups (Belmont Report, 1979).

Confidentiality and anonymity were safeguarded through the use of pseudonyms, restricted access to raw data, and secure storage, in compliance with the Data Protection Act (1998), the GDPR (2018), and university governance protocols. Given the potential identifiability of APNPs within NHS Scotland, particular care was taken to reassure participants that neither names nor clinical locations would be disclosed. Thus, ethical integrity was enacted not only through adherence to governance frameworks but through hermeneutic engagement that honoured participants' autonomy and situated them as co-participants in the interpretive dialogue.

4.4.4 Sampling and Recruitment

Sampling and recruitment of research participants is extremely important, and will now be discussed.

4.4.4.1. Sampling

Sampling decisions are central to the integrity of qualitative inquiry, as they determine the extent to which data can illuminate the study's aims (Parahoo, 2006). While numerous strategies exist, purposive sampling is particularly appropriate when participants must demonstrate specific characteristics or experiential knowledge relevant to the phenomenon under investigation (Morse, 2006). This approach enables the deliberate recruitment of individuals capable of articulating their experience, though it is often critiqued for introducing bias through non-random selection (Laverty, 2003). Morse (2006) distinguishes between purposeful bias, an inherent feature of qualitative design, and unintentional bias, such as over-reliance on a narrow subset of participants, which risks undermining analytic depth.

Within a Gadamerian hermeneutic framework (Gadamer, 2012), such purposive selection is not a methodological weakness but a means of fostering dialogical engagement. Understanding emerges through language and the fusion of horizons between researcher and participant (Lawn, 2006). Conversations with participants thus became interpretive encounters, generating rich insights into the APNP role. Reflexivity was sustained through the use of a research diary, enabling ongoing examination of pre-understandings and their influence on interpretation (Bradshaw, 2013; Van Manen, 1997). This reflexive stance is

integral to hermeneutics, where the researcher is both participant and interpreter, continually revisiting assumptions throughout the analytic process.

Sample size in qualitative research is rarely predetermined, evolving instead in relation to emerging insights, available resources, and pragmatic constraints (Morse, 2006; Cohen et al., 2011; Burns & Grove, 2011). Sandelowski (1995) emphasises that adequacy lies not in numerical representation but in the richness of information obtained. In this study, I diverged slightly from this, and a target of about 24 interviews was set for practical reasons. Eight participants from each of the three groups were chosen, as this was considered sufficient to gather diverse perspectives while fitting within the doctoral timeline, given working full-time, the need to organise a working diary, and budget constraints. In the end, 21 conversations were conducted: eight APNPs across eight health boards, covering both urban acute hospitals and rural community settings; eight colleagues, including Nurse Directors, consultants, and staff nurses; and five parents. This distribution mirrors the geographical diversity of NHS Scotland and ensures a balanced representation of stakeholders involved with the APNP role. Thus, sampling was not merely a technical exercise but a hermeneutic act, shaped by ethical responsibility, reflexivity, and the pursuit of understanding. By purposively engaging participants positioned to illuminate the phenomenon, the study generated dialogical data that will be explored in depth in subsequent chapters.

4.4.4.2. Recruitment

Following ethical approval, participant recruitment was facilitated by Clinical Nurse Managers, who acted as gatekeepers within their respective health boards (Parahoo, 2014). Information leaflets were distributed to potential APNPs, colleagues, 'others', and parents whose child had been cared for by an APNP in the previous three months before the study, in their clinical areas. These leaflets outlined the study's purpose, its ethical safeguards, and emphasised the voluntary nature of participation. Interested individuals were invited to contact the researcher directly, thereby ensuring autonomy in the decision to participate. Where initial distribution did not elicit responses, a gentle reminder was issued to the Nurse Managers, who re-circulated the invitation via email to ensure staff were aware of the opportunity.

Once contact was established, participants were given opportunities to ask questions and seek clarification before consenting, which reinforced transparency and informed choice. This recruitment strategy protected ethical integrity while also reflecting the hermeneutic commitment to dialogue and openness. By engaging participants through trusted clinical leaders and ensuring that participation was voluntary and informed, the process honoured Gadamer's emphasis on respect for tradition, culture, and individual autonomy. Recruitment was therefore not just a procedural step but an interpretive act, fostering trust and laying the groundwork for the dialogical encounters that underpin Gadamerian hermeneutic inquiry.

While the use of Clinical Nurse Managers as gatekeepers facilitated access to participants across diverse health boards, it also introduced potential limitations. Gatekeepers may inadvertently influence who receives or responds to invitations, thereby shaping the composition of the sample. This raises questions about representativeness and the possibility of excluding individuals less visible to managerial structures. However, within a Gadamerian hermeneutic framework, the emphasis lies not on statistical generalisability but on the depth and richness of understanding generated through dialogue. By acknowledging these limitations and maintaining reflexivity throughout the recruitment process, the study ensured that ethical integrity and interpretive openness remained central to participant engagement.

4.4.5 Conversation settings

Interviews were conducted in mutually agreed settings to foster trust and sensitivity, consistent with Streubert and Carpenter's (2011) guidance. For APNPs and professional colleagues, NHS premises were chosen for convenience, though occasional interruptions occurred due to clinical responsibilities. Parents were interviewed either on NHS premises or in their homes, according to preference.

Data collection (Gaining understanding) followed an open-ended conversational approach, inviting participants to share personal narratives of their experiences with the APNP role. Each interview began with a broad prompt ("Can you tell me about your experience of...") and was followed by exploratory questions ("Can you expand on...", "Can you tell me more about...") to encourage deeper reflection while maintaining openness to participants' perspectives.

4.5 Reflexivity

Reflexivity entails the critical examination of one's own beliefs, assumptions, and practices, and their influence on the relational and interpretive dimensions of research (Creswell, 2007). Within a hermeneutic framework, such biases are not eliminated but acknowledged as integral to the interpretive process (Gadamer, 1989; Lavery, 2003). Gadamer's philosophical hermeneutics positions reflexivity as a continual engagement with experience, whereby pre-understandings are surfaced, interrogated, and reshaped through dialogue.

Koch (2006) emphasises that the researcher's stance is never static but requires ongoing self-critique, resonating with Gadamer's notion of the fusion of horizons. Similarly, Primeau (2003) argues that reflexivity enhances awareness of positionality and its influence on knowledge construction. Fleming *et al.*, (2003) extend this by demonstrating how Gadamerian hermeneutics operationalises reflexivity as methodological practice, embedding the researcher's evolving self-understanding within the interpretive encounter. In this study, reflexivity was enacted through the maintenance of a research field journal, which documented pre-understandings and reflections throughout the inquiry. This iterative process has been integral to both the interpretive analysis and the writing of the thesis,

ensuring that the researcher's voice and positionality remain transparent within the hermeneutic dialogue.

4.6 Chapter Summary

This chapter has outlined the methodological foundations of the study, situating the inquiry within Gadamer's philosophical hermeneutics (Gadamer, 2012) and guided by Fleming *et al's.*, (2003) methodological framework. By positioning the researcher and participants as co-constructors of meaning, the study embraced dialogue, reflexivity, and the fusion of horizons as central to the interpretive process. Methodological choices were shaped by both philosophical commitments and pragmatic considerations, ensuring ethical robustness, contextual sensitivity, and alignment with the aims of hermeneutic inquiry.

The analytic process reflected Gadamer's philosophical hermeneutic (2012) concepts by immersing in the texts as dialogical encounters, acknowledging pre-understandings, engaging iteratively within the hermeneutic circle, and remaining open to the continual unfolding of meaning. Reflexive documentation, supervisory dialogue, and transparency in methodological decisions ensured rigour and integrity. In adopting this stance, the study moved beyond description to generate new insights into the APNP role, situated within the context of NHS Scotland.

Trustworthiness was addressed through credibility, transferability, auditability, and confirmability. Credibility was enhanced by the inclusion of verbatim quotations, triangulation, and methodological coherence, ensuring faithful representation of participants' perspectives. Transferability was offered as contextual resonance rather than generalisability, consistent with Gadamer's view of understanding as historically and dialogically situated. Auditability was achieved through systematic documentation, a reflexive diary, and adherence to Fleming *et al's.*, (2003) Gadamerian hermeneutic method, enabling transparency and scrutiny of interpretive decisions. Confirmability was established not through participant verification but through openness, reflexivity, and grounding interpretations in participants' narratives, recognising that understanding is dynamic and continually evolving.

Together, these methodological commitments demonstrate why Gadamer's Philosophical hermeneutics (2012) provided the most appropriate lens for exploring the APNP role. Fleming *et al.*, (2012) ensured that the study remained faithful to its philosophical foundations while producing rigorous, transparent, and contextually situated findings. This methodological framework underpins the subsequent chapters (Chapters 5–7), which present the interpretive analysis of conversations with APNPs, Others, and parents, thereby contributing substantively to the limited body of knowledge on advanced practice nursing in NHS Scotland.

CHAPTER FIVE – ‘Being’ an advanced paediatric nurse practitioner

5.1. Introduction to the APNP conversations

This chapter meets the study objective for this group and aims to explore APNPs’ perspectives on their own role. It outlines the emerging themes from my conversations with 8 APNPs, who worked in diverse rural and urban paediatric clinical settings across 8 different NHS Scotland health boards. Anonymised demographic details of the 8 APNPs are provided anonymised below and with more detail in Appendix 7. The theoretical underpinning and method used to carry out this study have already been described in Chapters 3 and 4.

For consistency, the term APNP will be used to refer to conversations with the individuals involved in this study in the following chapters. All practitioners in this chapter involved in this study are APNPs who have obtained an MSc in Advanced paediatric nursing practice prior to the start of this study, and are working within NHS child health services across Scotland.

Each conversation began by requesting a general overview of the APNP's individual role and its development. This allowed the focus to be on the key points identified in each conversation, reflecting individual interpretations of the role.

As the conversations developed, the following themes/subthemes emerged:

- 5.2 A new role
 - 5.2.1 Role transition
- 5.3 Decision making
 - 5.3.1 Autonomous practice
 - 5.3.2 Professional identity
- 5.4 The nurse doctor game
- 5.5 Communication and family centredness
- 5.6 Being an APNP
 - 5.6.1 Support networks

All names have been anonymised, but to facilitate understanding of which APNP worked in which clinical area across NHS Scotland in this chapter, the relevant data is provided below. The complete demographic data collected are available in Appendix 7.

Name	Clinical area of practice
Lesley	General paediatrics (rural DGH)
Andi	General paediatrics/assessment unit (rural DGH)
Jamie	Emergency department

	(City DGH)
Jo	General paediatrics (City DGH)
Rowan	General paediatrics (City DGH)
Bobbi	Community (rural)
Alex	Emergency department (city DGH)
Jordan	Assessment unit (rural DGH)

5.2 A new role

All conversations indicated that, for the APNPs involved in this research, their role was undergoing development. Although these discussions occurred in 2016, this point remains relevant today, as reflected in current literature discussing the evolving role of advanced practitioners (Hyde *et al.*, 2020; Evans *et al.*, 2021; Fitzpatrick *et al.*, 2023; Kilpatrick *et al.*, 2024; Miller *et al.*, 2024). The literature highlights ongoing issues such as unclear role identity for many practitioners, often unstructured and informal training, and the challenges and opportunities that come with a limited or inconsistent understanding of role responsibilities (Kucawski *et al.*, 2024; Britton and Blackwood, 2024). Each participant was the first APNP in their role, describing it as a challenging yet exciting opportunity to lead and influence the development of the APNP role. It was clear from all discussions how dedicated and motivated these individuals were.

Andi identified that,

“my role has developed a lot pioneering the first role [here] ... little was known as exactly what the role would entail and what direction it was going to take”.

While Lesley acknowledged,

“It was quite difficult, as there was no one to model on”.

From the conversations, it was clear that each APNP valued the chance to shape their evolving role. This created exciting opportunities for each, but also the challenge of having no prior role model to guide them. Although challenging, it provided an opportunity to customise each role according to local needs. These challenges and opportunities were made more complex by the absence of a standardised approach across the UK and in Scotland for the role, a situation that still persists today in some areas (Fitzpatrick *et al.*, 2023; Nuffield Trust 2023).

All participants discussed how 'learning on the job' affected their growth, alongside completing an advanced practice educational programme.

Jaimie emphasised the concept of on-the-job learning, viewing it as an apprenticeship-style training. They mentioned that the role expanded through '*in house training*' designed to address gaps in service, as identified by both the APNP and senior doctors.

"It's been managed through competency packages which we've designed along with a few of the consultants here and I'm talking about things like lumbar punctures Something that was not even considered when the role was first bought into being we could see patients, saw babies with temperatures for instance who needed septic screens and we could do everything apart from the lumbar puncture".

Alex stated,

"I was interviewed and was actually put into a seconded post as a nurse practitioner I was working at the same time, on the job What that allowed me to do was actually consolidate".

5.2.1 Role Transition

Role transition was a key theme in my conversations, as most participants acknowledged the challenges they faced when integrating into a new role and learning on the job, often without a defined job description. In a qualitative thematic synthesis study by Moran and Nairn (2018) analysing eleven articles on role transition for ACPs, six key themes were identified as critically important: experience of change, mentorship, role orientation, clinical supervision, clinical skills, and Master's level education. All 11 article conclusions were similar, demonstrating a failure to acknowledge appropriate support in these areas. Where agreed objectives were unclear or not achieved due to lack of support, people resigned from their roles. Therefore, these areas are recognised as fundamental to success. Some of these ideas came up in my conversations.

Lesley identified the difficulty of being in a new role, on a unit they had previously worked as a staff nurse,

"Kind of separating the role from what I used to do can be difficult"

Rowan explained how their role transition affected their professional identity,

“It’s a totally different way of working, although you’re still nursing you’ve got that medical part to your nursing”.

Andi recognised that deconstructing their previous knowledge was necessary for their journey into this new role,

“You start a massive, massive transition, Emm, going through it [learning on the job], so it equips you with all the basic skills you need and actually strips off all the layers you have there It is a totally different way of thinking. A lot of the nurses are very experienced, so you’ve got your intuition and your knowledge as a nurse that you had for years, and so it’s very hard to get your mind into a different way of thinking Peeling back these layers to start thinking differently”.

Jordon also discussed the complexities and challenges they encountered during this transitional period,

“I think you have to just look at it differently, because I think as a nurse, you’re kind of thinking all fluffy kind of nurse things.... So actually, trying to think, it’s ok, so what do you think is wrong with this child, and I have to kind of think more medically about things ..., and stepping back from the kind of nursing, nurturing thing, that you like to do as a nurse”.

This transition period was more challenging for some APNPs than others. From the conversations, there were differences in how this role was implemented across various units. Some units lacked clear role requirements and a formal job description. However, the APNPs valued the opportunity to influence and shape their roles through collaboration with their clinical colleagues, who supported the APNP position. The 8 participants were the inaugural advanced practitioners in these roles across Scotland; all having completed a Master’s in paediatric advanced practice from the same educational institution.

It was evident that different clinical settings had varied approaches to preparing for the role's introduction. Discussions highlighted themes similar to those in Kuczawski *et al.*, (2024), including how the role was introduced, the support and supervision provided, development of knowledge and clinical skills, uncertainties about the role, and efforts to build confidence and demonstrate competence.

Jordon identified,

“I don’t think I really had much of an idea what, what it meant. When I started it full time in the ward, the majority of the staff didn’t have a clue of what I did either I took the lead from one of the Consultant paediatricians [who had a vision for what the service needed] ... she kind of let me and my

manager know what she wanted from the service To kind of speed up the patient journey”.

Jordon noted that the unclear vision for the role early on negatively affected the development of APNP skills during the initial transition, a point echoed in other discussions. These conversations suggested that many Consultant paediatricians had a say in shaping the role, often because they had neonatal experience where the neonatal AP role had been introduced some years earlier (Association of Perinatal Medicine, 2011). As a result, the role was initially driven by medical perspectives, but gradually became more nurse-led as APNPs gained confidence and recognised new opportunities.

Alex pointed out that vague expectations from senior managers about the service redesign and the roles necessary to fulfil service needs impacted their unit discussions. It required considerable effort to explore various nursing roles and determine the appropriate level of practice needed before concluding that a new APNP role was necessary to meet service requirements,

“We were looking at redesigning our service which was really about the sustainability of the service ... and there was an opportunity to go on and develop a nurse role with extended skills. At that time, we weren’t sure what it was going to be, was it like going to be a nurse specialist, a clinical nurse specialist and in fact, that was the initial plan. However, rather quickly through the whole process it became clear quickly that the job required was sitting a level above that, if you like”.

In the place where Andi worked, there was a more organised and constructive approach, evolving from initial role development to supporting a comprehensive package of quality care from admission to discharge,

“We sat down as a group of people after the course [Masters’] was finished and had a look at the direction we wanted to take role in, so that it had a clear focus... I can carry out most, if not all, of their care components right through from any nursing skills to advanced skills in diagnosis, treatment and explain it all to them”.

Andi indicated that this approach was suitable for her, highlighting that, in addition to mentoring from a consultant, a progressive development plan helped her enhance her skills, knowledge, and confidence. These experiences were shared with other APNPs, who also reported increased confidence, most of whom were mentored by a consultant paediatrician. Andi suggested that the role was necessary to ‘Bridge the gap’ between medical and nursing staff, as junior doctors often lacked experience and nursing staff lacked the advanced clinical skills needed for the service. This role complemented medical service needs, especially due

to the shortage of junior and middle-grade doctors (Savrin, 2009), and facilitated role development for nurses,

“They started to see the advanced skills that I had acquired ... I had increased my confidence and was able to consolidate my theory as well, and that was displayed in my practice. And I think that that’s required, you have got to prove yourself. That’s a journey as well”.

Jordon discussed that as the role was embedding, support and understanding from clinical staff grew, which enabled the role's ongoing development, and he demonstrated this by saying,

“I wrote some guidelines that were agreed by the consultants that would allow me to see patients without them ever having to see a doctor ... just some very basic normal things that I felt I could do, and I could see the patient would be comfortable with”.

Bobbi’s APNP role was originally created to reduce hospital admissions by early detection of illnesses in children with complex healthcare needs within the community. During his transition, Bobbi supported themselves by arranging a period of clinical practice consolidation at a local paediatric unit. This experience boosted their confidence to work as an APNP in the community, which was crucial for understanding and fulfilling service needs. Bobbi told me,

“I asked for a period of consolidation. I didn’t, once I’d qualified, say thanks very much and run away ..., I asked if I could continue In an acute environment so I could practice my history taking skills, make differentials and prescribing a plan of care”.

Rowan shared similar concerns about the difficulty in distinguishing this new role from their previous one, as the staff did not understand the new responsibilities and felt pulled in different directions. However, Rowan also expressed optimism about some opportunities this change created. This included the idea of ‘taking a chance,’ which embodies hope and belief in making a difference for children and their families, managing service requirements, and being both personally and professionally satisfying,

“All through my professional development plans, I had mentioned I was really keen to do this, and if it had been available years ago, I would have done it years ago”.

All 8 APNPs clearly expressed the difference they perceived after transitioning from a ‘ward nurse’ to an APNP.

Alex applied caution to the notion of the difference between the APNP and ‘ward nurse’

“cos I guess that the question then comes from that – is where do you draw the line Where do we stop being nurses and where do we start to pretend to being mini-doctors? ... I think we have to always try and remind yourself and ground yourself that we are nurses ... we have a lot to give from our nursing experience”.

The APNPs highlighted that senior ‘ward nurse’ [i.e. Senior Charge Nurse] roles are primarily managerially focused on patient care, while staff nurses perform basic nursing tasks for children; thus, APNPs were bridging the gap between these two roles.

Each APNP recognised that, although their initial training categorised them primarily as nurses, they had now developed advanced skills and training suited to their expanded roles, extending beyond traditional nursing duties (Britton and Blackwood, 2023). All APNPs identified essential skills such as complex decision-making, patient history-taking, physical examinations, formulating differential diagnoses, and appropriately managing the patient journey, including prescribing treatments, providing anticipatory guidance, and fulfilling other relevant roles within the four pillars of practice (Evans *et al.*, 2020).

5.3 Decision-making

Clinical decision-making is essential to all practice. Over the years, various strategies and theories have been developed to help nurses and healthcare professionals implement appropriate care pathways for patients. In a comparative study on clinical decision-making processes of nurse practitioners versus doctors, Thompson *et al.*, (2016) found that doctors and nurse practitioners use similar decision-making strategies. However, nurses took longer to diagnose than doctors did, until nurse practitioners had more than 2 years of experience, at which point both professions showed comparable consultation times and outcomes. The study also observed that nurse practitioners often use a more holistic approach during consultations. In contrast, doctors tend to be more paternalistic—making medical decisions based on their judgment of what is best, often without fully involving the patient.

Rowan identified,

“You [APs] are diagnosing now, ... going from taking a nursing history to assessing a child, examining a child, making a diagnosis, ... plan of action, deciding what you are going to do for this child, prescribing, other interventions. There is a full circle here, ..., it is pretty much a medical model not a nursing model so it’s totally different Some skills are still the same like our venepuncture, cannulations It’s just different Doing more advanced stuff Now we’re leading on these things”.

Lesley acknowledged the decision-making skills they had cultivated, highlighting how these set their role apart from that of a staff nurse. Lesley discussed this decision-making process, demonstrating their ability to operate at a level of practice expected for AP roles,

“When that child came up, ..., I would go through the history, ...examine the child ...if the child deteriorated and needed a cannula, then I would put the cannula in, ... the continuing care would be that I would be reviewing the child. So instead of getting a doctor or junior doctor to review that child, it would be me who would review the child.... I would phone for the blood results, I would prescribe the fluids ...liaise with the doctors, liaise with the team If that child needs to be transferred, then you know that’s a whole different matter, I would be liaising with the transfer team as well, um, so that’s where it is different from a staff nurse role ... But my role, it’s not completely changed, it’s not as if I’m doing a completely alien thing I wasn’t doing before, I’m still a registered nurse at the end of the day, but, Emm, my skills are a lot more extended than anyone else on the ward. I’m the only person on the ward who has that qualification and can perform some of the skills and duties that I need to do”.

5.3.1 Autonomous practice

The APNPS discussed the concept of autonomy. All nurses are considered autonomous at registration (NMC 2015/2018), with the NMC recognising varying levels of autonomy and responsibility linked to professional judgement. Registrants are also accountable for their work. I was eager to understand how APNPs perceived their autonomy.

Autonomy is a multidimensional concept defined professionally as a practitioner's ability to make decisions related to patient care, improve quality and safety, and positively influence the work environment (Varjus *et al.*, 2011; Watkins *et al.*, 2016). Although often confused with accountability (Pursio *et al.*, 2021), both concepts encourage continuous reflection and re-evaluation of professional practice.

An integrative review of 27 studies by Pursio *et al.*, (2021) on nurses' understanding of autonomy showed that staff nurses mostly associate autonomy with clinical decision-making, rather than broader professional independence. This focus is likely because nurses typically follow doctors' orders within specific clinical protocols, leading many to doubt that nurses can achieve full autonomy (AllahBakshian *et al.*, 2017).

Whereas Lockwood *et al.*, (2022) conducted a narrative review of 19 studies examining the levels of clinical autonomy among nurse practitioners. Since nurse practitioners operate at higher levels of care, they are expected to demonstrate more overt autonomous practice. The review identified four main themes, which they named "Stepping up" covering how advanced

nurse practitioners accept and transition into their roles; "ANPs Living it" focusing on how they learn task mastery and independence; "ANP bounce ability" how they face and overcome challenges that may affect their autonomous practice; and "ANP Setting in Motion" which is related to indirect care and service activities.

In this study, conversations suggested that APNPS' autonomy was linked to their specific role or level of practice. This varied by the APNP's workplace, with all roles generally operating at a level somewhere between junior doctor and registrar.

Jaimie viewed autonomy as an evolving concept as their role developed, becoming more confident in their decision-making throughout the assessment process and each patient journey. This newfound confidence stemmed from the consultants' support, who also sought reassurance about the value of this evolving role. Jaimie indicated that they believe nurses and APs still do not have full autonomy by using the phrase 'pretty much',

"It was a learning experience for the consultants, because it was a relatively new role for them too, Emm, and over the years we have kind of refined the role and got it to a point where we have full autonomy pretty much with every patient we see".

Jo's sense of autonomy appeared to be linked to their level of practice and responsibility, which functioned at the registrar level. This suggests that Jo recognises that as they advance in this role and build confidence, their practice starts to expand beyond traditional professional boundaries expected for nurses,

"Ultimately in this new role the buck stops with me ... it's huge. Much, much greater. And especially being the registrar level, compared to being a junior doctor. The junior doctor goes and sees a child, clerks them in but actually doesn't really have any responsibility in the management of the child ... so really the buck stops with the senior person On the middle grade rota ... that's the whole point of our job to make decisions like a registrar will ... I know my limits and those limits have definitely gone further as the role evolves and boundaries change with the more confidence I have gained".

Lesley agreed that autonomy was aligned with decision-making, as their role and responsibilities had increased,

"It's also about that continuing care and what do you do with that child at that point ... I'm making decisions. Four years ago, I would have had to basically phone a junior doctor to run that by sometimes, whereas now the decisions are getting made by myself".

Bobbi believed the role's autonomy and responsibility were clear, as reflected in the job title, and linked their higher salary to greater autonomy compared to other ward nurses.

“My job title and the responsibility that comes with it I am also paid differently to make me more autonomous; I don't have a colleague I can turn to and ask, what do you think about this?”

5.3.2 Professional identity

Several of the APNPs linked autonomy with wearing a national uniform, feeling that it interfered with their professional identity and this affected their ability to carry out their role freely and remain autonomous at all times.

While wearing a uniform alone doesn't create a professional identity, conversations with some APNPs revealed clear frustration. Some APs, who previously did not wear any uniforms like medics, felt particularly unhappy about being required to wear one. The NHS policy on wearing a uniform (Scottish Government, 2010 – CEL 42) stated that staff who did not previously wear a uniform were not obliged to adopt one; however, nurse managers enforced the wearing of uniforms for all. Professional identity is an important element within any profession as individuals assume certain behaviours, norms and values that are important within their occupational group (Academy of Medical Royal Colleges, 2020). The NHS National Uniform was introduced to all health boards in Scotland in 2010 with a recommendation that all staff had to wear the national uniform by December 2012 (Scottish Government 2010, CEL 42), except for doctors. Nursing staff involved in patient care had to wear a range of tunics in five shades of blue with navy trousers, giving an NHS corporate identity, and this was considered good for the public, who would then be able to recognise staff. The APNP role (or generic Advanced Practitioner role) was not discussed as a separate professional entity, and all health boards adopted the light blue tunic for the APNPs, the same as a staff nurse. This caused several challenges and concerns for the APNPs, who felt that it created a power imbalance in terms how colleagues and patients saw them, despite their job purpose.

Andi stated,

“The issue of uniforms. You are not visually different to a staff nurse, so you introduce yourself [to parents] as an APNP or as a nurse practitioner sometimes and explain that I am going to have a brief chat about what is happening They don't fully understand who you are in relation to the skills that you have got and a lot of them don't understand that they won't necessarily be seen by a doctor ... there is I think still a lack of understanding regarding the role amongst the public”.

Jo also explained how wearing the staff nurses' uniform affected her ability to perform the APNP role freely,

"I didn't have to wear a uniform for the past 3 years and then in November I had to wear a uniform, ... they [management] decided that uniforms were part of the Scottish Government policy and that nurse practitioners weren't named in the policy [management then decided] you will wear a uniform no matter what! So, I have to wear a cornflower blue uniform ..."

Jo provided a compelling account of an incident where wearing this uniform led to a challenging situation during a child resuscitation. Her role was to lead paediatric resuscitations at the district general hospital where she worked, but her uniform caused doctors unfamiliar with her to question her authority and role because of its cornflower blue colour.

Jo stated,

"It definitely doesn't help in my job role when I turn up to A & E in the capacity to lead a resus and I'm wearing this! If I don't know the person that is there [referring to doctors who have been called to the resuscitation], it is very difficult, and I understand why it's very difficult for them and it's difficult for me and then it's really horrible for a parent to have doctors questioning 'who are you?' all the time [especially in a resuscitation situation] ... These challenges are difficult ... If you're working in the middle grade [doctors] rota, then I don't feel you should be wearing the same as a brand-new staff nurse who qualified yesterday. I don't think it helps anyone!"

Participants further discussed their professional identity, focusing on their role within the nursing or clinical team and, at times, on how others perceived them. Andi commented,

"the consultants are very good and right at the very beginning they do say that [APNP] will work at a registrar level ... she will be able to do it ... I think they do [junior doctors] worry a bit, some of them come in with the immature, just life skills part of "well, I'm a doctor and you're a nurse" – that is just life. They soon work out actually a nurse who's been qualified for 30 years on the ward is far greater and important to listen to than someone who has been qualified for only 3 months"

Jordon described how they did not fit into any particular team, so forming a role identity within the team was a challenge,

"I don't fit into the nursing team at all (laughing) To begin with the nurses didn't really understand what I did, and they would still be expecting me to do nursing type things, but they would expect me to do the doctors medical side of things as well I have had some run-ins with nurses. Somebody said

to me once, oh, so because you've got a degree, you think you are better than us? And I was just like, actually no, ... that is not my job anymore".

Furthermore, some APNPs observed that uncertainty or lack of understanding about their role caused some junior doctors to become 'tetchy' when they realised an APNP was regarded as senior, highlighting issues related to structural hierarchies and professional identity.

Jo said,

"Junior doctors get confused about what kind or what can a nurse practitioner do I think they get a little bit nervous about the fact that they are going to be left alone in the hospital with a nurse who is more senior than them".

Jordon stated,

"I feel more comfortable now. I still remember one junior doctor in particular who thought I was just a jumped-up nurse and that I was too big for my boots I disagreed with what was his decision, and it just caused a major upset He acted like a spoilt little child and actually stomped off, and then when someone said to him later on – are you wanting this baby to have fluids or not –he said – oh just ask me (APNP)[with attitude] And I thought, do you know this, this isn't what it was meant to be, we were meant to be working together".

5.4 The nurse-doctor game

Teamwork can both hinder and facilitate role development, a theme found across many studies. McInnes *et al.*, (2015) reviewed barriers and enablers among nurses and general practitioners to identify factors that influence collaboration and teamwork. Principles that promote effective teamworking often include supporting diversity and differences within teams, fostering a positive environment where individuals can thrive, encouraging intra-team respect, and recognising and resisting protectionism and silo working. (Academy of Medical Royal Colleges, 2020).

Professional protectionism is acknowledged when blurring traditional professional boundaries is seen as a threat and may lead to conflict if not managed swiftly and appropriately. This concern is increasingly recognised due to the introduction of many new roles.

Jo identified positive enablers to the role, and suggested that being an APNP within the unit supported team working between nurses and doctors,

“We are a consistent presence whereas the medical staff are only here every 6 months We are here all the time, and we know the processes here. I think we are seen as the people to ask”

Jo described themselves to be ‘an in-between person’ within their team, as someone who had an understanding of both nursing and medical professions and was therefore able to float between and negotiate between both,

“We’ve not had any major problems with nursing staff, and we’ve actually had no problems with medical staff. So, I am actually the in-between person – so if doctors are sort of slating nurses ... I can say ‘well look coming from this side’, cos I have been a nurse And at the same time if nurses are saying ‘why are doctors doing that [?]’, I can take it from the medical side So, it’s actually been a really good role”.

Jordon described a more challenging teamworking situation and explained that it was difficult to handle during the initial days of their transition into the role,

“I feel more comfortable now. I still remember one junior doctor in particular who thought I was just a jumped-up nurse and that I was too big for my boots I disagreed with what was his decision, and it just caused a major upset He acted like a spoilt little child and actually stomped off, and then when someone said to him later on – are you wanting this baby to have fluids or not –he said – oh just ask me (APNP) And I thought, do you know this, this isn’t what it was meant to be, we were meant to be working together”.

These conversations suggest that teams within clinical practice still demonstrate imbalances in power dynamics (as in 5.3.2). These imbalances may be viewed as a form of professional protectionism and as part of traditional medicine and nursing hierarchical structures, which can become imbalanced as new roles emerge.

5.5 Communication and family centredness

All 8 APNPs emphasise that advanced communication skills are crucial for developing their roles. They highlighted the importance of building relationships through communication with families and various staff groups, which are vital to their work. As previously noted, paediatric nursing involves many complexities, including working with families, managing diverse care needs across different developmental stages, the illness itself, and the often conflicting expectations of parents versus the child's best interests, which may not always align (Yehene *et al.*, 2022),

Jo told me,

“You have to have really good communication skills. You have to be able to communicate obviously with children, ..., you have to be able to communicate in a different way with parents, so as a nurse you have to have amazing communication skills with parents I take pride in the fact that I was the nurse who was left with those parents, so I will always try and gauge if they have understood”.

Excellent communication skills are essential for the APNP, and all APNPs take pride in their advanced abilities, which they attribute to their prior experience as a nurse. Advanced communication skills facilitate the delivery of high-quality, family-centred services that are effective and ethically sound, fostering trusting therapeutic relationships with the child, their family, and colleagues (Institute for Healthcare Communication, 2011; Stein *et al.*, 2022). However, the APNP role faces specific challenges, sometimes related to intrateam dynamics. These issues may stem from unclear role definitions and, as Paton *et al.*, (2013) suggest, from advanced practitioners being viewed as a ‘middleman’ within some healthcare teams (Stein *et al.*, 2022).

Jo demonstrates becoming the ‘middleman’ within this scenario while also demonstrating leadership,

“I led one resus where I had to call the death and ‘cos it was the night shift, we had called the consultant to come in, and he was on the way in, but we were in agreement that it was enough. And so, I had to communicate that to the parent and family and had to lead the team”.

Since APNPs are experienced nurses, their communication skills support a holistic approach to patient care. Junior doctors are often younger, recently graduated from medical school, and may struggle with the communication skills needed to interact effectively with children and their families, possibly because they have not been exposed to the same experience yet.

Rowan shared their views on communication differences by saying,

“They just go “I’m the doctor – I’m doing x, y and z! Whereas I might involve a little bit of play in my examination You have got to take in the whole family I think our approach is different. I think the way we speak to families, communicate with them, they are all different. That’s learned behaviours from nursing and probably the length of service helps cos you’ve learned lots in that time. So, you know how to communicate, you know when not to communicate, and you know when to communicate, so lots of learned behaviours It makes a difference to the families”.

Jordan shared a similar viewpoint, supporting the idea that the APNP has developed broader communication skills compared to a junior doctor, and stated,

“I watch some of the junior doctors and they just approach things medically, ..., they just want to know this, this and this. They have got a list in their head of things that they want to know, whereas I think as a nurse with over twenty years nursing, and I think, I’ve got a certain way of going about things ... As an APNP you approach it differently to a doctor, you just do”.

Bobbi emphasised that communication with families is essential in establishing a unique partnership between the APNP, the child, and their family. They believe this greatly influences the quality of the care provided, describing it as ‘bridging the gap’ between parental needs and service requirements through good communication and shared decision-making, which ultimately makes a significant difference to the care experience. Bobbi said,

“The decisions [on care] is always a joint decision Very much a partnership with the parents Because they know them [child] better than anybody. ... it is time to readdress that balance to give the parents their place”.

5.6 Being an APNP

Many of the APNPs recognised that they had high self-expectations linked to their enthusiasm and motivation for the role. All 8 APNPs demonstrated a strong passion for their work and the potential achievements in this field. However, this role could lead to confusion or conflict with others' expectations. An additional challenge is understanding advanced practice within the nursing profession, specifically what nursing is and does, and how the advanced practice role differs from other roles (Lowe *et al.*, 2012). Many new roles are emerging within teams, with team factors identified as key barriers and facilitators to successfully implementing AP roles (Torrens *et al.*, 2020).

Lesley discussed their developing role and mentioned that initial talks with their mentor, a consultant paediatrician, focused on their aspirations for the role. Due to limited guidance from nurse management, their discussions with the mentor were supportive, helping them align with their own expectations.

“There was an agreement with my mentor at the very beginning of the kind of things he would expect of me ...So, we are very, very lucky that the kind of example had already been set from that point of view”.

Lesley also recognised that issues with role clarity originated within the clinical team, including junior doctors and ward nurses,

“The junior doctors were a wee bit put out ...The way the rota works, they are only in paediatrics for 6-8 weeks, they don’t know the way the ward is run,

so in a way I have that knowledge [laughing] ... Some of my challenges would have actually been from some of the nurses who didn't really see what my role was and would try and pull me in all other directions".

Andi observed that a common challenge when introducing the role was that clinical staff and parents often lacked clarity about how the APNP role differed and what the APNP was capable of doing.

Andi illuminated these challenges,

"At the start it was very difficult and there were an awful lot of challenges because staff and probably parents, as well, weren't as aware of the role, Emm, probably had no idea of the role whatsoever, what it was going to entail, or what an APNP was, and the skills that they had ... in the beginning the staff were quite wary and unsure of what I could do It probably took a year to iron out all the seams of them believing in me Some of the junior doctors, they felt threatened at times, as at times it would seem that I had more knowledge and skills than them, Emm, they didn't like me trying to help them So, I had to allow them to get their experience as well".

Jaimie noted that attitudes at their workplace were changing as the role started to demonstrate its benefits on the unit,

"Attitudes are changing there was certainly some degree of suspicion certainly about our role from other staff who definitely saw a nurse's role as being well defined and, well, limited, but umm, not only have we managed to overcome or mostly overcome that slightly negative attitude from nursing staff but also, definitely from medical staff who hugely value our role".

The reality of transitioning to working as an APNP was also considerable. Many of the APNPs interviewed (6 out of 8) had previously worked within the same unit as either a staff nurse or senior nurse, which introduced additional challenges,

"They knew me as a staff nurse And there were told not to expect to rely on me to do a staff nurses job, ... my first priority was now my advanced skills and knowledge".

Lesley shared insights experienced with one particular clinical colleague,

"Professional jealousy to a certain extent! Yeah, probably one person, in particular, I would say, but I think it was just a lack of understanding. And, Emm very much feet on the floor, as in – I don't care if you are a nurse practitioner, this still needs to get done!".

5.6.1. Support networks

Another interesting aspect of this new role was related to who was supporting the staff and their development. Several APNPs highlighted that their roles were primarily medically driven and shaped by Consultants. In contrast, some areas kept the role strictly within the nursing domain by nurse managers.

Lesley said,

“There’s a kind of network, nurse practitioner network, Emm, but I would say my support is in-house. We work very much as a team, and I get supported from the nurses, I get supported from my manager, I get supported from the consultants. So, I feel quite happy that the support is there locally”.

For Jordan, the support networks were complex. Local backing came from the nurse manager and charge nurse in the clinical area, primarily focused on implementing the role. However, most of the support eventually came from a medical perspective, particularly the unit's Consultant team. Jordan had to arrange his own mentor, and together they figured out how to develop the role.

“I still have the same supervisor [Consultant] that I had throughout my course, we formally meet once a year but other than that she’s there if I need to go to her for support, and I do and I have done And the Registrar on the ward is there for support as well”.

In 2016, all of the APNPS were in their initial roles; there were no nationally formalised support networks or supervision frameworks. These APNPs took the initiative, meeting informally as colleagues to foster their professional development, while following local support practices and governance procedures. Currie and Grundy (2011) emphasised the importance of support mechanisms as part of NHS Scotland's advanced practice succession planning, but these did not develop into a standardised system. Today, support structures are gradually improving through the Transforming Roles Agenda (Scottish Government, 2017), though they remain inconsistent across Scotland and the four UK nations.

5.8 Summary of Chapter - Towards a Fusion of Horizon

This chapter reflects on conversations with the 8 APNPs in order to gain understanding and meaning of the APNPs personal experiences and perspectives as their role across eight NHS Scotland health boards. These discussions have enabled a range of viewpoints to surface and have fostered new insights for me.

Themes emerged from my conversations, centred on Taking a chance, Professional identity, Communication, and Family centeredness. The 8 participants spoke openly and unconditionally about the significance of their role, the challenges they face, and the job satisfaction they derive not only from being an APNP but also from influencing the development of this role.

The next chapter will highlight the emerging themes from the conversations conducted with 8 'others', the clinical colleagues who work alongside the APNPs within children and family services in NHS Scotland.

CHAPTER SIX - 'Others' Perspectives of the APNP role

6.1 Introduction

Building on the previous chapter, which explored the conversations and emergent themes from the APNPs themselves, this chapter aims to investigate the perspectives of multidisciplinary colleagues, referred to here as 'others', on the APNP role. In keeping with Gadamer's philosophical hermeneutics (Gadamer, 2012) and the methodological approach outlined by Fleming et al. (2003), these conversations are treated as dialogical encounters in which understanding is constructed through the hermeneutic circle. By situating each participant's conversation within this interpretive framework, the chapter seeks to illuminate how meaning of the APNP role is shaped, challenged, and expanded through the perspectives of those working alongside or managing APNPs.

The chapter outlines the key themes that emerged from conversations with eight colleagues working across rural and urban paediatric clinical settings within the same NHS Scotland health boards as the APNPs. The objective for this group was to investigate multidisciplinary colleagues' perspectives on the APNP role. This group comprised four consultant paediatricians, two clinical nurse managers or Lead Nurses, one clinical director of nursing, and one community staff nurse team member. Each participant was invited to share their understanding of the APNP role, drawing on their professional relationship with APNPs and their experience of service delivery in their respective contexts.

Conversations began by exploring participants' own roles and their connections to APNPs, before moving to their reflections on the APNP role within their clinical setting. This approach, consistent with Fleming et al.'s emphasis on openness to dialogue, enabled me to foreground the individuality of each perspective while also identifying shared themes. In Gadamerian terms, these conversations represent moments of horizon-fusion, where pre-understandings and lived experiences of 'others' encounter the evolving identity of the APNP role, offering valuable insights into its meaning and significance within NHS Scotland.

The previous chapter identified the conversations and emergent themes from the APNPs' conversations. This chapter continues by investigating a range of multidisciplinary colleagues' perspectives [referred to as 'others'] on the APNP role. The chapter outlines the key themes highlighted from my conversations with these 8 'others' who worked in various rural and urban paediatric clinical settings within the same NHS Scotland health boards as the APNPs. Each participant either worked alongside or managed services provided by the APNPs and was asked to share their understanding and meaning of this role. The group included four consultant paediatricians, two clinical nurse managers or Lead Nurses, one clinical director of nursing, and one community staff nurse team member who engaged in a conversation with me.

Each conversation began with asking about the participants' roles and their relationship to APNPs, followed by their opinions on the APNP role within their clinical setting. This approach allowed me to focus on key points from each conversation and highlight individual perspectives on the role.

The main themes generated from our conversations were:

- 6.2 Bridging the Gap
- 6.3 Blurring of professional boundaries
 - 6.3.1 APNP development and education
 - 6.3.2 Educating junior staff, children and families
 - 6.3.3 Uniforms
- 6.4 Perceptions of parental response to APNPs
- 6.5 Qualities of APNPs
- 6.6 Supervision
- 6.7 Inconsistency within the service context

All names and identifying details have been removed, but for ease of understanding which profession 'others' belonged to during my conversations in this chapter, the relevant data is provided below. The full demographic data collected is available in Appendix 7.

Name	Post
Ainsley	Consultant paediatrician
Chris	Consultant paediatrician
Taylor	Consultant paediatrician
Jackie	Clinical nurse manager
Nikki	Consultant paediatrician
Corey	Community Children Nurse
Sam	Lead nurse
Lindsay	Chief nurse/clinical director of nursing

6.2 Bridging the Gap

All participants agreed that APNPs are highly valued members of the clinical team, able to work smoothly between nursing and medicine. They emphasised that the APNP role is well-regarded and offers significant clinical benefits. APNPs were appreciated for their prior clinical experience as nurses, which was seen as a 'quality' and described as providing additional value or delivering a 'higher level of service'. This contrasted with some comments criticising junior medical staff for their lack of experience. Therefore, the APNP role was viewed by all

participants as valuable to the service because it 'bridges the gap' both within the service and between professions, ultimately benefiting child and family care.

Ainsley explained how APNPs are able to transition between both professions, a flexibility that junior doctors lack,

"They have got great [emphasised]communication skills, they have got great psychosocial skills and all of that has come from years of their nursing jobs. And it's hard to replicate that! junior medical staff just haven't got that yet ... and therefore they [APNPs] can add the medical skills they haven't got yet and as a mix, that's pretty powerful".

Taylor explained why they valued APNPs for providing an improved service.

"What I mean by a much higher level of service is that they are able to um, take a history, do a full clinical assessment and um, come up with a differential. They can prescribe and they are able to communicate at a very high level with the family which brings in a dimension that junior doctors and sometimes others aren't able to do. They can think 'out the box' and families are on the whole very happy with this".

Jackie summed up APNPs by saying,

"They have got something ... which takes into consideration the medical need as well as the nursing need for the child and family, ... bringing two elements together".

Each conversation showed that APNPs were seen as reliable, trustworthy, and offering a sense of stability to their patients and families through the perspective of 'others'. All Consultants trusted APNPs to work independently within regulatory frameworks; where part of their appeal was also providing continuity and stability by not rotating between different departments like junior doctors do.

Nikki said,

"The benefits of that is doctor's change every 3 months or 4 months, she's [APNP] a stable figure on the ward, ... So, she's there, she's up and running, she's keeping them right. Also, she has had a previous role ..., and she uses that as well, very well".

Nikki viewed APNPs as the steady foundation within a unit, supplying stability and, consequently, supporting both professions,

“Well, she is providing a support and she’s sort of like a rock for that, for the unit, so when they come [junior doctors], when they start, they know nothing and they are very, very fresh. [including registrars] ..., and she’s the sort of fixed feature that knows how things work; knows how systems work; knows how, where to find things. She’s a very, very good source for that”.

Jackie expanded on the concept of flexibility in the role,

“[They] can work up or down at any level, umm, they can completely cover the range of skills, knowledge and expertise and experience of the most junior person on the floor to the most senior person on the floor”.

All participants agreed that APNPs not only perform nursing duties but, especially in the case of experienced APNPs, also take on roles traditionally considered medical, thereby 'bridging the gap' between the professions to address clinical needs. Hall's (2016) unpublished thesis examined the role and value of advanced practitioners in general practice, concluding that nurses now possess the skills to expand their practice into traditional medical areas. My conversations with participants further support this idea.

6.3 Blurring of professional boundaries

The issue of blurred professional boundaries emerged as a key theme, often discussed in terms of 'bridging the gap'. A variety of challenges were identified by 'others' working alongside APNPs and appeared to focus on the traditions of nursing and were linked to how nurses were trained before becoming APNPs. All Consultants agreed that the traditional nurse training, which all the APNPs in this study received, impeded the early growth of the APNP role.

The Consultants noted additional challenges, such as APNPs being consistently labelled as 'just nurses' by colleagues, particularly junior doctors and often other nurses. This, the Consultants noted, caused some sense of conflict for the APNPs, likely shaped by traditional professional boundaries such as differing opinions around the identity of the APNP, and also linked to the wearing of a nursing uniform which did not distinguish APNPs from staff nurses.

Lewis (2022) analysed workforce shortages and explored the development of advanced practice nursing by applying sociological theory to understand nursing identity, professional power dynamics, and gender issues hierarchy. Lewis (2022) argues that these issues are linked to the shortage of medical staff, the necessity for cost efficiency, and medicine's status as the dominant profession, with nursing generally regarded as subordinate. This relationship is reinforced by the higher social capital attributed to medicine, which is more highly valued. These points may relate to longstanding nursing traditions, like the predominantly female workforce (Lewis, 2022), leading to nurses or APNPs being regarded simply as 'just nurses'.

These ideas highlight issues surrounding 'blurring professional boundaries', a concept discussed in the literature and illustrated in conversations below (Nancarrow *et al.*, 2005; Kilpatrick *et al.*, 2012; Inwood *et al.*, 2021), where, for example, junior doctors may find it challenging to see APNPs as more knowledgeable or senior.

6.3.1 APNP development and education

Taylor extensively discussed the uncertainties and decision-making challenges faced by APNPs, arguing that initial nurse training was limited. Taylor argued that nurse training was overly structured, with strict protocols and guidelines that stifled free thinking and problem-solving, making it more difficult for APNPs to adapt their thinking to their new roles. In contrast, medical training emphasises systematic problem-solving approaches from the start. Taylor argued that this significantly impacts an APNP's ability to confidently make complex care decisions early on, as they must deconstruct existing knowledge to reset and develop new understanding and decision-making methods. This impacted early role development, causing APNPs to take longer to see patients, diagnose, and develop treatment plans. Thompson *et al.*, (2016) conducted a study showing that advanced practitioners took longer when gathering history and making clinical decisions during their first two years in the role, supporting Taylor's idea, though a direct link has not been definitively proven.

Chris also identified challenges related to the educational aspects of the role for nurses. Chris noted that nurses frequently find it challenging to learn new data about patient groups, including analysing and interpreting information, and then deconstructing and reconstructing this knowledge to inform clinical decisions. (Crosskerry and Nimmo, 2011). These skills are often not anticipated or included in traditional nurse education because of how nurse training is structured.

Chris said,

"I was trying to explain ...that they already knew a lot of it, but ... they were perceiving the complexity of it rather than thinking about the whole generic thing that they did know".

Several doctors, including Ainsley, Chris, and Taylor, believed that junior doctors and many senior trainees had little prior contact with APNPs and therefore did not understand the pathway APNPs took to develop this role. They also did not value the knowledge and experience each person brought to the role from many years as a nurse. It was suggested that this could cause conflict as all trainees (doctors and APNPs) competed to gain similar, often limited experiences, in order to extend their knowledge. Additionally, Ainsley, Chris, and

Taylor acknowledged that they had occasionally witnessed other doctors trying to exert authority over APNPS, while assuming they knew more than 'just a nurse'.

Ainsley said,

"I think it's easier as a medic to say to another medic 'no, no, I'm fine' but an APNP, depending on how confident you are feeling, if you have a medic coming and saying 'oh, maybe I should just have a look at that', I think that's a really difficult area for them. We [doctors] need to be better at recognizing the skill mix that they bring".

This illustrates not only a blurring of boundaries but also a potential source of conflict: APNPs have shifted away from traditional nursing roles and are therefore neither part of the nursing team nor fully recognised as part of the medical team. This affects role development and reflects a power imbalance between the professions, as discussed in the APNP chapter (5.3-5.4), rooted in traditional nursing and medical role perceptions (Clarín, 2007; Barnes, 2015; Lewis, 2022).

Ainsley highlighted that APNPS have a duty within their units to supervise junior doctors during their ward rotations. This by itself could create conflict, as clinical norms often view doctors as more senior than nurses, making some junior doctors reluctant to accept mentorship from 'a nurse' (Braithwaite *et al.*, 2016).

6.3.2 Educating junior staff, children and families

APNPs were recognised as a resource for training others including nurses, junior doctors, children, and families thus providing continuity and strengthening connections between professions and patients. This was attributed to their knowledge and experience, which some considered to be unique to the role.

Chris said,

"You have somebody who crosses between nurses and medics and has an excellent appreciation of how nurses work, ..., she can teach the medics understanding. She can cross that; she can be the bridge to teach the medics and get them to understand the role of the nurses and to be the person in between she's a great educator of the junior doctors because junior doctors need to be trained in the practical aspects of nursing ..., [she] teaches them to be able to be a bit of both and not just to be the medic who is just dealing with the medical and then walking off, so she brings something quite unique into her role".

Most participants believed that the role ‘bridged the gap’ between medicine and nursing by offering a unique adaptability to teaching in both fields.

The APNP is well positioned to educate junior doctors about their responsibilities and how to approach patient care using patient- and family-centred strategies (Martinez-Gonzalez *et al.*, 2014). This shifts focus away from the task-oriented patient management often undertaken by junior doctors early in their careers. Consultants, in particular, found this approach highly beneficial. Ainsley highlighted that consultants should clearly communicate to junior doctors that APNPs are not meant to fill gaps with assigned tasks merely but to collaborate and work alongside the team as part of a cohesive unit.

Ainsley said,

“No, [as if speaking to a junior doctor] their role isn’t like yours and they manage a patient. They will give you a hand with that [referring generally to medical tasks] but they don’t get given a task, and that’s probably one of the things for junior medical staff to realise”.

Chris also thought that the actions of APNPs could break down some of these professional barriers,

“Very quickly, the doctors who are just arrogant medics, with a medics attitude, you know, us doctors versus you nurses,, doctors in training who still think they are above, think they are above other people, so [APNP] will very quickly, because of how she works, will be able to very quickly break down those barriers”.

Ainsley and Chris indicated that APNPs at their workplace generally had built a close working relationship with the supporting consultants. They noted that junior doctors quickly realised that these individuals possessed something special and, if they were wise, understood they could learn from them.

6.3.3 Uniforms

The four medics I spoke with believed that the uniform worn by APNPs presented a notable challenge. While doctors typically do not wear a uniform, in adult units they may wear a white coat, but this is rare in paediatric units. The medics believe that wearing uniforms reinforces the ‘nurse’ label, which they think limits the role's development, by affecting parents' trust in APNPs to manage their child’s care fully, as well as creating concerns for other staff. It continues to emphasise the hierarchical nature of clinical practice and has a negative impact on the role (Kilpatrick *et al.*, 2012; Kilpatrick *et al.*, 2013). Interestingly, the same idea was not widely expressed by the other participants from a nursing background. This contrasted with

the APNPs, who personally expressed concerns about the stigma of wearing a uniform, which they felt impeded their practice. (see Chapter 5.3.2).

Chris contributed to these points, specifically mentioning,

“I think there is still a bit of stigma for them [having a different role], firstly because she is in uniform, and secondly because she still has a ..., still has a nurse label attached, ummm ... Get her out of uniform”.

6.4 Perception of parental responsiveness to APNPs

The main feedback from my conversations was that parents generally did not express negativity towards APNPs. However, it was very much felt that parents often lacked understanding and awareness of the role, which occasionally led to a parent requesting to see a doctor instead, even once the APNP had introduced the role.

Lindsay’s conversation indicated that, for the most part, people are unsure about who cares for them, and even more significantly, they seem indifferent.

Lindsay stated that,

“If they know you’re a nurse, they don’t seem to care either”.

The participants were asked about their perception of parental confidence in the APNP, based on the APNP’s demonstration of clinical competence. Lindsay suggested that most parents were satisfied if they felt listened to, their child was assessed, care was provided, and a clinical outcome was achieved that made the family happy.

Lindsay also mentioned that in her senior nursing role, she had informally asked parents for their opinions on the APNP role. She firmly believed that parents closely associate competence with confidence, and she was not aware of anyone having expressed otherwise,

“You’re a nurse, I wanted a doctor”.

Where Ainsley worked occasionally the APNPs had met some resistance from parents to their role, describing how,

“When a parent asks for a doctor this probably reflects either a situation where the family have been in hospital several times and therefore have an expectation that they see a doctor, or it’s been potentially a gender situation ... maybe a father may just think they should see a doctor. Mothers usually aren’t quite as fazed”.

When I attempted to delve deeper into the potential differences in expectations between fathers and mothers, Ainsley was unable to explain why this might be.

During another rare occasion, Ainsley explained that one parent had objected to being seen by an APNP. However, after discussing this with the APNP to avoid undermining their authority, both agreed that the family should see the doctor, as this would support family care by reducing stress. Ainsley explained that generally it was quite reasonable to listen to the parent and say, *“ok, well fair enough, let’s move forward”* and they [doctor] would see the child instead.

Several conversations suggested that parents are more likely to ask nurses questions than doctors. This is partly because of the communication strategies employed and the therapeutic relationships often built with APNPs, which also receive positive feedback in various studies. (Lindberg *et al.*, 2012; Kinder and Allen, 2013; Thibodeau *et al.*, 2022). Lindsay’s following quote relates to how doctors are sometimes held in different esteem compared to nurses and APNPs, and therefore parents felt they could not always ask appropriate questions to doctors. Lindsay said,

“There is still a bit of medical staff and godliness, you understand, but whether there is, it’s a reality and certainly some of our APNPs have said that themselves”.

6.5 Qualities of APNPs

When asked about the qualities that ‘others’ perceived APNPs to have, only a few qualities were verbalised and identified directly. However, during the conversations, the qualities of APNPs were verbalised and expressed, even if the participants did not recognise this. The words or phrases used to describe APNPs included confident, motivated, ambitious, highly experienced and able to upskill, demonstrating personal qualities suitable for all APNPs. The participants also emphasised the APNP capacity to work across both medicine and nursing. The personal qualities that APNPs brought to their roles enabled them to develop beyond typical nursing expectations.

Ainsley proposed that these qualities ultimately helped individuals develop and make independent decisions,

“A bit of ambition, very much self-worth, that if you learn the skills and with the experience that you’ve had as a member of nursing staff, you should be able to do it. Confidence is a huge part of it and being a really good team worker Because you are now going in between two areas!”.

Nikki and Chris praised APNPs for being highly motivated in choosing to become an APNP, and for taking a risk as experienced nursing staff even though supported by a good training programme.

Chris had said,

“[she’s] hungry to learn and hungry to better herself, and to develop, and she knows she can be better than what she is”.

This is an interesting phrase used by a Consultant here, meaning ‘she knows she can be better than what she is’. This comment unintentionally aligns with ongoing perceptions of the status difference between medicine and nursing, embedded in clinical tribalism, hierarchy, and stereotyping introduced early in both professions' training (Braithwaite *et al.*, 2016). However, it also demonstrates the qualities that Chris feels an APNP.

6.6 Supervision

Several notable challenges emerged in the conversations, particularly concerning supervision for APNPs. Clinical supervision offers support and creates opportunities for the AP to reflect on their practice, discuss clinical cases, identify areas of good practice, and make necessary improvements (Lee *et al.*, 2022). As a newly developing role, all APNPs in this study received mentorship from senior medical staff, mainly consultants, to support their clinical skill development. However, as they became embedded within their clinical areas, some of the supervision structures were modified, and at times APNPs were supervised by a clinical manager, or other senior nurse (Lee *et al.*, 2022).

Lindsay talked about the supervision structures where she was employed,

“One of the models, or parts of the model was making sure they had a very, very strong structure in terms of their professional supervision within the nursing model. In the early days, like many of us, you’d require consultants, ..., to support the education and learning and the practical elements of that, but as we’ve grown them [APNPs], more and more, we’re now actually making sure that they’re mentored and supervised by another APNP. Absolutely they will work with medical staff, ..., but actually the competency sign-off process now sits with a nurse”.

However, some discussions revealed a split between medical and nursing supervision. In certain clinical settings, APNPs were supervised solely by medics, in others by nursing managers, and in some cases by both. This variation warrants attention, as it could lead to confusion about role expectations and service requirements.

Chris viewed supervision as an issue, noting that the nurse manager responsible for supervision lacked understanding of the APNP role. Chris stated,

“She [APNP] is a qualified as a nurse, under that roof, but the problem is who has responsibility for clinical supervision, and her educational supervision, and ‘what narks’ everyone who looks after her [referring to medical colleagues] is that no one has ever seen any of the managers [nursing] who look after her, ..., and yet they seem to pull the strings, but with no understanding of her role”.

This poses a challenge for supervision, as the APNP is overseen by a nurse manager but benefits from clinical support and skill development from medics. Chris explained that, historically,

“There has always been a nursing versus medic kind of mmm, better not go there, So, it’s a problem, because an APNP can be supervised by a doctor, but yet, someone else is telling her to do A, B, and C, not knowing what her real every day-to-day role is”.

6.7 Inconsistency within the service context.

Service needs are often discussed in terms of clinical outcomes and are assessed on value for money when patients receive care from APs versus doctors (Newhouse *et al.*, 2011; Walker and Hooks, 2020; Fothergill *et al.*, 2021).

When asked about how the APNP role integrated into the service, various opinions emerged. The nurse participants mainly focused on existing service models for nurses, while the Consultants discussed how the role aligned with a medical care model. This already hints at potential areas of clinical inconsistency.

Lindsay, the clinical director of nursing, initially found this role challenging to understand due to the absence of national or UK-wide strategic models for advanced practice roles. She perceived that this lack was evident in how the role had developed differently across the UK and Scotland.

Lindsay initially was unsure about the role and how it contributed to nursing, as she recognised that current holders of the position were mainly filling gaps in care that had traditionally been provided by medical staff. It seemed that the role was merely a,

“Stop-gap, and it was a very task-delivered role”.

However, Lindsay then went on to explain that,

“As I kind of read about it, and actually began to meet some of the APNPs, and saw models elsewhere, the penny dropped I actually found that it would be extremely valuable in the service context”.

Lindsay recognised a lack of clarity regarding roles within her clinical service areas and noted similar confusion when discussing the APNP services with other providers in different regions. She also acknowledged that APNP roles were developed differently across various clinical services and health boards (Newhouse *et al.*, 2011). Lindsay didn't oppose this, but she raised concerns about the role's governance, as it seemed inconsistent. Governance is established within formal policy and legislation to support policies and structures that help achieve organisational goals. This can include aspects of regulation, which consist of legally binding policies and require nationally regulated benchmarks set as standards (Brook and Rushforth, 2013, Nuffield Trust, 2023, NMC, 2024).

Governance and regulation of the nursing profession through the NMC aim to protect the public from harm and to enhance public professional confidence (NMC, 2018, 2024). There has been ongoing debate about introducing further regulation for advanced practitioners because of the development of complex, autonomous, and specialised roles across various practice areas, but this has previously been opposed (DOH, 2010, Council for Healthcare Regulatory Excellence, 2009). As discussed in Chapter 2, the regulation of AP for nurses is likely to come into force through the NMC in 2029 but still has many dimensions that need considered and decisions made on (NMC, 2024).

At the same time, evidence shows an inconsistent approach to developing these roles through education, training, qualifications, responsibilities, and governance. This variability could increase risks to the public (Brook and Rushforth, 2013; Nuffield Trust 2023). Standardising these roles would help build greater public confidence.

Taylor and Jackie [nurse managers] believed that service needs led to boundary blurring, which management found difficult to address due to the lack of a consistent, fair approach.

Jackie recognised that, as a manager, there was an issue with remuneration for qualified APNPs. She faced budget constraints that prevented her from paying for these additional roles or supporting more than one or two staff members, which hindered her ability to provide 24-hour AP coverage. She also worried about the lengthy process of training staff and building their confidence.

“We are not in the situation where you have a raft of APNPs and you've taken five years to grow them, and it'll take you five years to grow the next lot. We need to be doing it on a rolling programme so that you have different levels within the team of expertise”.

This ultimately results in a situation in which APNPs cannot provide a 24/7 service, leading to inequalities in the services offered.

Taylor also acknowledged that the APNP service on their unit was delivered inconsistently when no APNP was scheduled. This was an issue because Taylor understood that the service provided to children and their patients was about dealing with,

“Volume of patients, seeing patients who would have traditionally been the remit of the junior doctors”.

Taylor was also concerned that because APNPs are typically paid at a higher grade than staff nurses and senior charge nurses, they should have a higher skill level that includes management duties, for example, running a clinical area. She admitted that banding can be problematic, since senior ward managers are usually paid at a lower grade than APNPs, and Taylor did not believe this was fair.

This point is noteworthy because training for advanced practitioners focuses on the four pillars of practice (NES 2008): clinical, leadership, research, and management. However, during this period, the emphasis was on developing advanced clinical skills and holistic patient case management for paediatric patients and their parents, rather than covering an entire clinical area as a senior charge nurse does. This conversation revealed some ambiguity about the role. It indicated a potential miscommunication between practitioners, early role supporters (such as consultants), and service needs and expectations of the clinical nurse managers in paediatric units.

Jackie offered an alternative viewpoint, discussing the value of the educational currency for APNPs and expressing her appreciation for the personal and professional growth staff gained through this training. Jackie recognised the motivation and ambitions of staff eager to undertake this training and understood it was a risk they were prepared to accept, supporting staff in pursuing further training for their roles. Jackie articulated this as follows,

“Putting money in the bank, in their educational bank, by going on these courses and gaining the skills and qualifications”.

Jackie recognised the challenges related to budgets and allocating time for staff to attend these courses. She also expressed concerns that once the APNPs are qualified, they might seek jobs elsewhere, which would be a personal blow for her and affect local services. However, she understood and appreciated the situation. Jackie reiterated,

“The whole world of children’s nursing, the children are still gaining by those practitioners being qualified and able to practice as APNP’s”.

Sam expressed similar concerns regarding the development opportunities for APNPs in community settings and the associated challenges. The Nursing 2030 Vision (Scottish Government, 2017) suggests that, whenever possible, hospital admissions should be managed as day cases. This requires a stronger paediatric community nursing service, including APNPs, to support children and their families before admission and after discharge. Sam pointed out that obtaining backfill is very difficult from a service perspective, which hinders training and development opportunities for experienced paediatric nurses to become APNPs.

Corey's experience of the APNP role was unique because they were based in the community as a children's staff nurse, but they saw the AP role as a valuable enhancement to the team. Corey felt that the challenge for the children's community team was that there was only one APNP in post, which limited their availability, and led to inconsistency in APNP cover in the community setting. Corey realised that the APNP role provides more advanced paediatric clinical skills, like chest auscultation, which staff nurses are not trained in, as well as the expertise to conduct comprehensive child assessments in the family home, prescribe medications, and oversee the entire patient journey. This often prevented the child and family from needing to visit a GP surgery or hospital ward, which can be upsetting for both. Many children seen by the APNP were already known to the community team, making this role very supportive of their service.

A systematic review (Swan *et al.*, 2015) on the quality of care delivered by APs in primary care showed some evidence that there are very few differences between care provided by advanced practitioners and physicians; indeed, for some measures, care was better when delivered by advanced practitioners (Swan *et al.*, 2015). Patient outcomes from the systematic review showed equal or improved performance in physiological measures. The consultation length indicated that APs spent more time per visit, resulting in higher patient satisfaction. Some evidence suggested that patients cared for by APNs needed fewer visits over time. APN care contributed to lower healthcare costs and increased overall patient satisfaction. Regarding safety, it was concluded that APNs deliver safe and effective primary care (Swan *et al.*, 2015).

Corey described how the APNP made a positive difference to their service with this example,

"We can call (APNP) to come and listen to the chest and look in the ear and that might mean that the child will not be admitted to hospital but can stay at home but still be treated with appropriate medicine".

Jackie was concerned about the variety of titles used for APNPs, which led to a lack of clarity regarding roles, inconsistency in service approach, and confusion about who was using them and whether they were entitled to do so. Jackie said,

“I think that people say that they are working at an advanced level and you might get people calling themselves advanced practitioners but certainly, it’s not clear to everyone what an advanced practitioner is, I think that people would want the reassurance that the training was of a universal standard maybe across the UK, .. nurses ... who have done their qualification in Scotland, is that recognized as well in other countries [and vice versa], is that at the same level and does it meet the same outcomes as the Scottish qualification, so again, it’s about everybody’s confidence and clarity around those things”.

Generally, the Consultants believed the role should be adapted to fit the individual and their capabilities, which is why it varies so much. Chris thought the role functions differently at various levels, from junior doctor to senior doctor or registrar, and therefore believed it should be tailored to the person. Those at a more junior level would typically support rather than lead, whereas more confident and secure individuals could assume a more senior role depending on their personality.

All of the consultants viewed this role very positively, with three out of four expressing a desire to see it expanded and implemented more widely to strengthen paediatric teams. One of the consultants viewed this as merely a backfill role due to the previous shortage of junior doctors. They were not interested in having more than one APNP in their unit, as the workforce had stabilised and no longer faced staffing issues or unmet service needs. Since they already had one APNP, they did not plan to create additional APNP positions.

6.8 Summary of Chapter - Towards a Fusion of Horizon

This chapter has considered the conversations held with ‘Others’ who are colleagues of APNPs, to understand their perspectives on this evolving role. The eight participants shared open and honest reflections, enabling me to gain a new understanding through immersion in the texts and by provoking my pre-understandings within the hermeneutic circle. From these conversations, three central themes emerged: professional identity, bridging the gap, and inconsistency within the service context.

The theme of professional identity reflects the ongoing negotiation of boundaries between nursing and medicine, highlighting how APNPs are positioned and perceived within multidisciplinary teams. ‘Bridging the gap’ captures the unique contribution of APNPs in providing continuity of care and mediating across professional divides, thereby offering a seamless service for children and families. Inconsistency underscores the variability in supervision, service provision, and role clarity across different contexts, revealing structural challenges in embedding the role sustainably.

The participants spoke openly about both the challenges and opportunities they perceived in developing the APNP role. While some concerns were raised about role clarity and integration, there was also optimism about the service's potential to strengthen care delivery. Together, these themes illuminate the interpretive complexity of the APNP role and justify their prominence in this study, as they represent both the tensions and possibilities in advanced practice development.

The next chapter builds on this analysis by exploring emergent themes from conversations with parents and offering further insight into how the APNP role is understood and experienced from the perspective of service users.

CHAPTER SEVEN – Parents’ perspective of the APNP role

7.1 Introduction

This chapter meets the study objectives by exploring parent user perspectives on the APNP service delivery as experienced by those parents with a child previously cared for by an APNP. Chapters Five and Chapter Six provided insights into the APNP role from the viewpoints of APNPS and ‘Others’. Since children and their families are central to healthcare services and children have unique health needs, parents can provide valuable insights by sharing their experiences of the APNP role.

I had five conversations with parents whose child had been cared for by an APNP in the previous three months. This time frame was chosen so that any contact with an APNP caring for their child would still be recent in the parents’ minds. Because the child and their family are at the centre of the service and have specific healthcare needs, parents have much to share about their experience. Parents can offer a deeper understanding of the APNP role from their perspective. This provides parents with a voice and highlights the value they see in the APNP role.

All names and identifying details have been anonymised. To clarify which parent is involved in each conversation and the type of condition their child has in this chapter, the relevant data is provided below. The complete demographic information collected is available in Appendix 8.

Parent name	Where interviewed	Child condition – acute or chronic
Pete	Acute paediatric ward	Acute
Lorna and Adam (couple)	Own home	Chronic and acute
Margaret	Own home	Chronic
Lisa	Acute paediatric ward	Acute
Wendy	Acute paediatric ward	Acute

The parent conversations occurred in various settings: three in hospitals and two in family homes. Four individual parents agreed to participate in this research, along with one couple who had two children looked after by an APNP (one with a chronic condition and the other with an acute episode). Therefore, a total of five parent discussions were conducted, although efforts were made to recruit eight parents from different health boards. Four conversations were face-to-face with individual parents, and the fifth conversation involved a couple. The

remaining planned conversations did not take place on the scheduled day due to family illness or unforeseen last-minute commitments, and it was not possible to rearrange them.

MacDonald (2008) critically examined the challenges and complexities of conducting qualitative interviews with parents and children in their own homes. He noted that participants tend to be more open and trusting when they feel safe, comfortable, and relaxed, which is often the case in a family setting. However, MacDonald (2008) also notes that interviewing in a participant's social environment can be chaotic and messy due to unavoidable interruptions at home, which may compromise methodological purity.

Conversations with parents in their family homes were notably more open than those in a hospital setting. In one home, a parent spoke uninterrupted, appearing calm and clearly valuing someone to talk to and listen. In contrast, the experience with both parents present aligned with MacDonald's (2008) suggestion that home interviews can be chaotic and disorderly. The discussion was often interrupted by the parents preparing food and drinks, and the father's phone kept ringing. This created some chaos, making it challenging to maintain focus on their experiences with the APNP role. Later, when transcribing this conversation, the background noise (the use of kitchen utensils to make food and the telephone ringing) made transcription more difficult and time-consuming. Writing notes in a reflective diary immediately after this conversation in my car proved especially helpful when reviewing the conversation transcripts. As the researcher, I found this interview more chaotic and felt like an intruder in someone's home. I asked if we should reschedule, but the parents declined and insisted they were happy to continue sharing their experience.

Three key themes emerged from my conversations with parents:

- 7.2 Bridging the gap.
- 7.3 Communication skills and clinical competence.
- 7.4 Caring behaviour.

The rest of this chapter offers a dialogue on these themes.

7.2 Bridging the gap

The theme of Bridging the Gap emerges strongly through parents' accounts of their experiences with APNPs. Parents consistently describe APNPs as offering a unique form of support that extends beyond the traditional roles of doctors and nurses. Feelings of isolation and despair are met with empathy and guidance, while shared decision-making fosters confidence and trust. The reassurance and 'peace of mind' provided by APNPs illustrate how their role bridges the gap between clinical expertise and the emotional, relational needs of families, creating a connection that other professional roles often leave unfulfilled.

7.2.1 'Peace of mind'

All parents interviewed valued the APNP role highly. Several mentioned that the role gave them 'peace of mind,' describing their experience with it. This sentiment was shared by parents whose children were treated by an APNP either at home or in the hospital setting.

Lorna and Adam were asked about their experience of the role, and said,

"I think a lot of it is peace of mind, ... not having to drag our (daughter) out, take them to the doctors, even to go up to the hospital, because we prefer to keep (daughter) at home, and do most of her care. So, it should only be that she goes to the hospital if she needs IV antibiotics So having (APNP) come out and checking her over and giving us advice and supporting us is massive".

Lorna and Adam also said the APNP service was much more reliable and provided consistency to the family, identifying a general sense of frustration when discussing access to health care services through a GP. They both added,

"(APNP) is more likely to phone me back, than when I phone up surgery and ask for Dr ...".

This indicates that peace of mind is connected to easier access and quicker responses from the APNP, compared to the local family GP or hospital doctors, whom parents believe lack sufficient knowledge and understanding of their own family circumstances and how the complexities of their child's illnesses affect them.

One parent, Margaret, expressed her experience of the APNP by highlighting the importance of being listened to, communicated with, and sharing in decision-making,

"I've called (APNP) 3 times now because of (child's) health, (APNP) has been there, ... come out, ... listened to what I have said, ... examined him but (APNP) thinks about everything you say, ... doesn't jump in, like if you go to the doctors, they just jump in and say 'oh you!' whatever, You know I wished there were a few more like (APNP)! They'd examine (child) thoroughly, listen to his chest, check over other bits of his body, if necessary, think about things and make decisions with me".

Another parent highlighted that ease of access to the APNP provided them with 'peace of mind'.

Wendy said,

"I know that I can pick up the phone even if it was just a stupid question, ... I like to ask questions. I like to know, but (APNP) will happily stand for ten, fifteen minutes and talk ... "

7.2.2 Shared decision-making

The parents in this study also referred to the concept of 'making decisions with me'. This enabled an understanding that making decisions allowed parental control, something they felt was missing often in consultations with doctors, or when their child was admitted to any hospital setting.

Lorna and Adam identified,

"And they make sure that we as a family are happy with the choices, decisions we have made before they leave".

Margaret said,

"They'd examine him thoroughly, and make decisions with me".

This concept of being listened to and shared decision-making between the parent and APNP is important, as parents often believe they are ignored when their child is ill, which can lead to feelings of isolation, a loss of confidence, and anger at their perceived loss of control.(Lindberg et al 2012, Bradshaw 2013). Involving children in the decision-making process is also important, ensuring age-appropriate participation and engagement in their healthcare, as demonstrated by this discussion with a parent,

Wendy,

"And (APNP) also gives him [child] the opportunity to do things for himself, simple things like finger pricks for his blood sugars. Nobody else gives him the opportunity to do that for himself without supervision, you know, and I think that comes from (APNP) coming back and saying I know he can do it".

7.2.3 The despair of isolation

Some parents expressed feelings of despair and isolation, partly because of the stress caused by their child's illness, and partly because they feel a loss of control and feel unheard when their child is unwell. All of the parents had experienced this at some point when their child was unwell. They discussed the difference in care approach with an APNP, who they felt considered their feelings, lessening a sense of isolation:

Wendy stated,

“Sometimes you feel that everything gets taken away from you, because your child’s here, because it does get taken away from you but (APNP) involves you and tells you what’s going to happen ... others are too busy ... you do sometimes feel like you’re shunted to the side. You’re not asked your opinion on things, but I can never say that about (APNP)”.

This parent expressed a similar feeling of isolation through frustration when faced with being in hospital due to the lack of facilities and the loss of ‘homeliness’ that were important to her and her child.

Margaret said,

“I don’t think they get the care in hospital, they’ve not got the provisions in the hospital, (child) has a specialised bed, they haven’t got the specialised bed. Umm, when I go in the (hospital) with (child), I have to sleep in the bed with (child) ..., it isn’t practical, but they haven’t got the appropriate things um, and I find it so annoying, you know”.

7.2.4 Confidence and trust

Parents also reported greater confidence and trust in the specific APNP they interacted with, as well as in how the APNP role addressed their and their child's needs. This was articulated in a variety of ways:

Margaret said,

“I think it’s about the confidence (APNP) gives you”.

Wendy stated,

“To be honest, I think it helps knowing that somebody is that wee bit more advanced than just your normal nurse. It’s more, it puts me at ease, because I know that there is somebody there that my son looks up to when he needs a certain procedure done, you know”.

Some parents expressed confidence and trust when they saw the APNPs interacting with other staff and teaching both nurses and doctors. They believed APNPs showed greater knowledge and understanding by supporting staff development in various ways.

Pete expressed how impressed he was with an APNP,

“I’ve seen how she (APNP) works and teaches some of the doctors”.

Wendy expressed a very strong statement, showing the deep feeling and confidence that the APNP inspired in her.

Wendy identified,

“Whether it is down to her experience, whether it’s down to the confidence, she does have that confidence. It kind of radiating, you know she’s confident enough in her job, she knows how to do it, so it gives you the confidence, I think. And she has a lot of faith when you say something and that’s what you need, because she sees it from our side”.

7.2.5 Bridging the gap

Parents described the APNP not just as a clinical practitioner but as someone who offered holistic care, including emotional support, practical advice, and reassurance. In their accounts, the APNP role was portrayed as more than providing medical expertise; it involved giving the family everything they needed to feel supported, informed, and confident in managing their child’s care. In this way, the APNP was seen as uniquely placed to blend the technical aspects of medicine with the relational qualities of nursing, creating a comprehensive support system that other professional roles did not fully provide. All of these aspects contributed to the themes of peace of mind, shared decision-making, the despair of isolation, confidence, and trust, ultimately bridging the gap.

Pete stated,

“For me as a parent, she bridges a gap, it’s important to be able to understand at that level”.

Lisa also said,

“I think it’s just that she’s more... it’s hard to explain, because she’s more..., explains it better to him (child), he can relate to her and seems to really like her, so he’s okay when she can do it. If it’s anybody else he’s a bit taken aback and a bit scared”.

While parents expressed that the role was important to both them and their child, they held differing views on what the role specifically involves. The following two parents were uncertain about the exact meaning of the role but mentioned their ability to handle a range of complex issues.

Lisa said,

“I just know that when we seen the Doctor, mm, he said that there was the one woman that dealt with HSP so that’s all I know her as the HSP doctor, the one that deals with HSP, but I don’t know probably much about her job”.

Wendy was a little confused about the title APNP and the role itself,

“What does that mean, is she a Nurse or half a Doctor? You know, so it, I think, I think it is a bit confusing, you know I think you’re so used to seeing Staff Nurse, Nurse, Sister whatever! And to be honest it kind of, makes me kind of think of Sister status, but it does confuse people”.

Another parent was not able to articulate exactly what the role meant but was confident in how the role met their needs.

Pete gave a good analogy of how he understood the role and expressed,

“I am a firefighter, so what I do is learn all the basics about firefighting, but if I wanted to move up in roles and need to become more instant command-based and know that knowledge, so that becomes more specialised, if I was to go in a more specialised fire investigation route, I still need to know my basic fire skills, but I need to know increased fire skills. So, a staff nurse to me would, eh, obviously be more senior but maybe not as specialised as someone like (APNP) might be and have the knowledge that she has got”.

7.3 Communication skills and clinical competence

The theme of Communication Skills and Clinical Competence highlights the central importance parents placed on effective communication with Advanced Practice Nurse Practitioners (APNPs). Parents valued the open and consistent communication channels established with APNPs, describing these as vital to feeling informed, supported, and involved in their child’s care. Beyond direct interactions, APNPs were also seen as advocates, ensuring parents’ voices were heard and their concerns addressed within the wider healthcare team. In doing so, APNPs not only demonstrated clinical competence but also modelled effective communication practices to other staff, reinforcing their role as trusted intermediaries who bridged gaps in understanding and strengthened collaborative care.

7.3.1 Personal communication

Parents noted that the way APNPs communicated with them was often more personalised and that APNPs were able to engage with them and their children at an appropriate level, fostering closer relationships.

Lisa emphasised that personal communication with both herself and her child was also important,

“I mean she’s been really, really good to talk to and explained it a lot more but mm, you know she’s brilliant with my wee boy. She explains everything to him so that he can understand instead of all the medical terms, you know, to understand what they mean”.

Wendy discussed how the APNPs communication skills shone through her interactions with the APNP,

“One day I was so upset regarding you know, just ..., and she stood for a good twenty minutes, you know, and she said you’ve to just take a step back now and again. She was right! I think she’s got that kind of, she’s one of these people that sees it from all angles, rather than just seeing it from what she needs to see it as”.

Parents also observed and communicated their perceptions of how APNPs interacted and communicated with other staff members, and how parents perceived that other staff members also valued the APNP role. This ‘added value’ to the APNP role in parents' eyes further fostered trust.

Wendy stated,

“I could see it from the way she was speaking to our doctor this morning, and the Doctor really did kind of stand back and listen to her. That’s worth you know, they do listen to her, ..., but I think (APNP) sees it more from the patient’s side ... the softer side rather than ‘that is not going to work for so and so, why don’t we do it this way?’”

Wendy also stated,

“Doctors certainly wouldn’t do half of what the Nurses do, and she’s (APNP) very well respected, ... , even the Doctors respect her, you know, you can see it...”.

The literature indicates that the role of advanced practitioners is considered valuable for its efficiency, effectiveness, and cost-effectiveness, primarily shown through health outcome studies (Dale *et al.*, 2013; Newhouse *et al.*, 2008; Bonsall *et al.*, 2008), which underscores the importance of evidence. However, there is no existing literature that demonstrates the importance of the emotional or psychological value of the APNP beyond higher-level nursing skills, or its added benefit through communication channels with the child and family.

7.3.2 Advocacy

Listening to parents' feelings about shared decision-making and isolation revealed that advocacy is very important to them. It serves as a support mechanism that the APNP can provide to parents. Advocacy involves securing support to ensure their voices are heard (Choi, 2015). Some parents I spoke with received advocacy from APNPs, who helped parents attend multidisciplinary meetings, offered specialist advice, provided information, or directed them to relevant resources.

Parents indicated that this was appreciated and contributed to alleviating feelings of isolation and loss of control identified earlier. Most described key advocacy concepts, such as safeguarding patient autonomy to enable healthcare decisions, protecting children's and families' rights, values, and wellbeing, acting as intermediaries when needed, and advocating for social justice to ensure equal access to healthcare for these families (Vaartio *et al.*, 2006; Bu and Jezlewski, 2007).

Margaret said,

"He's come to a meeting with me. He's helped me with the meeting and said what we've changed and what we've done, but it's nice to hear somebody else listen to him because sometimes you'll go along and sometimes nobody will come with you and they'll look at me and go 'umm what are you doing here like!' but that ain't that with (APNP), it seems that everybody has got respect for him, he knows what he's talking about, he gives you the support you need, and what I like".

Wendy stated,

"I sometimes need somebody to stand up for us, cos you do sometimes feel like you're shunted to the side. You're not asked your opinion and things, but I can never say that about her (APNP)".

Patient advocacy is seen as a crucial responsibility for all nurses, yet it seems especially valued and exemplified by APNPs based on parental experiences.

7.4 Caring behaviour

This theme captures parents' accounts of the ways in which APNPs demonstrated care that went beyond routine clinical practice. Parents consistently described APNPs as providing a higher level of care that felt both safe and reassuring, while encompassing a more holistic approach to meeting the needs of the child and family. This was not limited to technical competence, which parents often found difficult to describe, but extended to behaviours that

conveyed attentiveness, compassion, and a genuine commitment to family wellbeing. In their narrative, APNPs were portrayed as embodying care in its fullest sense and delivering more than expected, which fostered trust, and ensured families felt supported at every stage.

7.4.1 Holistic care

One parent mentioned that the APNP treated their child more quickly, efficiently, empathetically and appropriately than junior doctors, whom they felt were experimenting on their child to learn and improve their skills. However, parents often found this unacceptable, often in distressing circumstances. They were not happy with this, especially when their children have complex illnesses or additional health care needs. Parents also appreciated care that considered the whole family's needs.

Wendy said,

“He’s not a guinea pig! You know what I mean, (APNP) been there, she knows what she’s doing and she’s done it. ‘that’s it, it’s done!’”

Parents also told me that APNPs adopt a more holistic approach by treating their child as part of a family unit. In contrast, junior doctors are perceived as more task-oriented and less confident across all aspects of patient care.

Lorna and Adam discussed their feelings about the differences in approach by doctors and the APNP when their child was unwell and needed medicine, but they preferred to avoid hospital admission,

“Whereas sometimes when you go to the doctors, it’s very kind of cut and dry ... you need to take her up to the hospital while we give her antibiotics, whereas (APNP) kind of looks in a bit deeper than that ... [APNP]’s more personal, they understand us as a family ... and what’s needed”.

Pete explained that the APNP collaborates with them by establishing a relationship with the child and family, fostering trust that supports a holistic and person-centred care approach. In contrast, doctors have generally shown a less personable manner. This is very important to parents.

Pete said,

“But I think in particular (APNP) shows by example, umm, doesn’t just sit there and talk blatantly to the adult and ignores the child, she talks to the child and that’s a no, always double checks ‘I’m about to do this is that ok?’. Cos it was yesterday and my other daughter was in with something different and someone else looked at her, and both my partner were sitting there and

she, the doctor used a stethoscope on her chest and everyone else we've had, either popped it down through there (pointing down top) or let us know what's gonna happen, but no she just whipped up her top and she's [daughter] is at that age where she's starting to get self-conscious and I feel self-conscious cos I'm her step-dad and am like, ok I'm going to turn away here! And I'm feeling quite embarrassed, she's feeling quite embarrassed and that's the first time I've seen that".

Lorna and Adam supported this theme with this statement,

"And when you speak to (APNP) he has an idea of us as a family, he has an idea of (daughter) and (APNP) can say "well, try this or I'll come out". The difference is at that level".

This APNP approach to holistic care is summed up here and appeared to be threaded naturally throughout many of the conversations that I had with parents.

Pete said,

"(APNP) is certainly much more hands on, (APNP) is much more comfortable in both handling and hands on with patients, umm, how she speaks to patients and speaks to the parents or adults who are there with her ... definitely doesn't want to shy away from anything, just feels more confident within herself ... and knowledgeable".

7.4.2 Higher level of care

The parents described instances in which APNPS provided a higher level of care. While they found it difficult to precisely define what this meant, I interpreted it as a combination of the themes I identified earlier in our conversations.

My pre-understanding before these conversations demonstrates that I believed parents would be interested in or aware of the differences in physical care offered by APNPS. However, they did not consider this aspect important and struggled to identify specific differences in care when asked to compare this with others nurses. This surprised me; however, what matters to parents is that they acknowledge the role's difference and recognise that APNPS have more advanced knowledge than staff nurses. This understanding is enough for them. as shown by one parent's statement:

Pete said,

"I don't really understand too much about the role apart from it being a much more senior role ... I've seen (APNP) teach students, give much more

information and umm, a much higher level of care... more specialised ... a higher understanding of my child, and the particular needs of my child”.

Wendy stated,

“More specialised and highly more knowledgeable than a staff nurse”.

No other studies have identified all of these points from the parent’s perspective.

7.4.3 Safe

Parents reported feeling secure and at ease with APNPs due to both their clinical knowledge and their respectful, approachable manner. This helped parents manage the challenges and stresses related to their child's health issues. This was shown through a compelling discussion with Wendy:

Wendy stated,

“None of that guinea pig status and that’s what I can’t abide by.... (child) knows that if APNPs on, it’s simple, whereas everyone else, horrible word but just pussyfoot about ‘oh have you seen this before, oh have you done that before, you know!... Because sometimes at 12 years old, it’s hard to get through to a boy, very hard, but he listens (implied to APNP), so it makes a big difference to us, it does, and he knows that she is one step above, or two steps, he’s not sure kind of what she is on the grading system, but he knows she’s kind of up there.

... When my son at 12 years old can hold someone in such high regard, it means more to me, cause I know he’s safe ... and he listens to her which means a lot to me. Because sometimes at twelve years old, it’s hard to get through to a boy, very hard, but he listens, so it makes a big difference to us, it does, and he knows that she is one step above”.

The idea of ‘more’ was frequently expressed by parents, too. This is interlinked with feeling ‘safe’.

Lisa appeared to associate feelings of safety with the relationship established between an APNP and her child,

“I think it’s just that she’s more... it’s hard to explain, because she’s more..., explains it better to him, he can relate to her and seems to really like her, so he’s okay when she can do it. If it’s anybody else he’s a bit taken aback and a bit scared”.

In my conversation with Wendy, she explained that she believes the APNP can handle any situation because of their experience and honesty. This instilled a sense of safety and reassurance for her family,

“From my experience you go into a room with a nurse, and they could do ‘one to ten’ but for someone that is that more advanced they could maybe do ‘eleven to fifteen’, and they can explain it that wee bit more, they’ve been through, they’ve done it. They know exactly what they are talking about rather than somebody going like it ‘might be this or it might be that, it might be the other’ whereas someone who’s been there and had the experience can say ‘right, this is it, this is it and you do feel that wee bit more. To me, it’s that wee bit more calming and I know I can go and ask her any questions, she’ll still give me a straight answer on it”.

I have not come across any studies involving parents where this idea of ‘more’ is discussed.

7.5 Towards a Fusion of Horizon

This chapter has illuminated the voices of parents whose children had previously been cared for by an Advanced Practice Nurse Practitioner (APNP). In seeking to understand their perspectives, parents offered candid and unreserved reflections on the APNP who had looked after their child, enabling engagement with their narratives through the hermeneutic circle and deriving meaning from their experiences.

The analysis revealed a series of emergent themes underscoring both the significance of the APNP role and its profound impact on families. Although parents often struggled to articulate the precise technical skills that distinguish APNPs, their accounts conveyed a deeper resonance: the APNP role was understood less in terms of discrete competencies and more in terms of what it represents: competence, fairness, and genuine care. Parents did not require detailed knowledge of clinical distinctions; rather, their trust was grounded in the assurance that the APNP could meet their child’s healthcare needs with integrity and compassion.

Central to these accounts was the recognition of the APNP’s unique caring approach. Parents consistently emphasised the holistic, family-centred nature of the role, which included both the child and the family as a whole. This outlook fostered perceptions of higher-quality care, creating feelings of safety, reassurance, and genuine care. It was in this context that parents described the APNP role as offering “more”, a term that conveyed the sense of added value and broader scope inherent in their practice.

From these conversations, three interrelated themes emerged: Bridging the Gap, Communication Skills and Clinical Competence, and Caring Behaviours. These themes

will be explored in greater depth in Chapter 8, which turns to the *Fusion of Horizons* across the three participant groups.

In essence, Chapter 8 provides a critical discussion and interpretive analysis of the themes identified in Chapters 5, 6, and 7, synthesising these perspectives to advance a deeper understanding of the APNP role.

CHAPTER 8 - FUSION OF HORIZONS (Discussion chapter)

8.1 Introduction

This chapter brings together the findings presented in Chapters 5, 6, and 7, which explored the perspectives of APNPs, 'Others', and parents. By immersing myself in the text, a new dialogue emerges, and I now move towards a fusion of horizons, as guided by Gadamer's philosophical hermeneutics (Gadamer, 2012) and by using the methodological approach outlined by Fleming *et al.*, (2003). Having established the methodological foundations in Chapter 4, this chapter applies them faithfully to the analysis of the research findings. Therefore, this chapter will discuss my Fusion of Horizons from these three groups of study participants.

In meeting the aim of this study and objectives, the study offers a rare and valuable opportunity to gain understanding and meaning of the APNP role from a whole systems perspective of both service provider and service user perspectives. The conversations revealed complex, multifaceted insights into the APNP role from three distinct perspectives. Although these conversations took place in 2016, many of the themes remain highly relevant today, reflecting ongoing uncertainty and limited literature on the role within NHS Scotland.

What makes this study distinctive is the narrative obtained from all three groups of study participants using a Gadamerian philosophical hermeneutic (Gadamer, 2012) approach which allows for the possibility of understanding and in particular, the inclusion of parents' perspectives alongside those of APNPs and other professionals. This triangulation of voices provides a richer, more nuanced understanding of the APNP role, highlighting both its opportunities and its tensions. The fusion of horizons presented here is therefore not only an interpretive synthesis of the findings but also a demonstration of the value of Gadamerian hermeneutics in illuminating the shared and divergent meanings of the APNP role across different stakeholder groups.

This Chapter will discuss my fusion of horizons from the three groups of study participants, which is a discussion based around key themes that emerged from the subthemes identified in each group and previous chapters.

The next three sections will discuss my fusion of horizon; my new knowledge gained from undertaking this research study.

8.2 APNPs

Three emergent themes developed from my conversations with APNPs in Chapter 5:

8.2.1. Taking a chance

8.2.2 Professional identity

8.2.3 Communication and family centredness

8.2.1 Taking a Chance

Each participant expressed strong motivation and enthusiasm for the opportunity to develop as an APNP. Their accounts revealed excitement about shaping a new role, even while acknowledging the challenges of doing so without established role models. Andi reflected on how little was known about the role and what it would entail, while Lesley emphasised the difficulty of establishing the position in the absence of guidance. Rowan described the transition from staff nurse to APNP as particularly demanding, noting the shift from a nursing-based assessment to a medically oriented approach to patient evaluation as a very different way of learning. One participant likened this process to peeling back the layers of an onion, with consultant paediatricians supporting the deconstruction of prior nursing knowledge to enable the transition into advanced practice. Yet, despite these changes, it became clear that nursing identity remained profoundly important to the APNPs.

By reflecting on my pre-understanding and remaining open to the conversations, subtleties of language and meaning began to emerge. My pre-understanding had not fully accounted for the traditions of nursing that shaped participants' journeys into advanced practice, nor the impact these traditions had on role development (Kuczawski *et al.*, 2024). Prior to this study, my understanding of APNP development was largely informed by the literature (Newhouse *et al.*, 2012; Stasa *et al.*, 2014), and this moment marked my first fusion of horizons. Alex, for example, highlighted the importance of pride and remaining grounded in nursing experience, which ultimately informed their decision to pursue advanced practice. My fusion of horizons was further deepened by reflecting on my pedagogical approach with students and situating these insights within the broader theoretical, policy, and professional dimensions of nursing.

This reflection underscores the importance of engaging in conversations about nursing identity and its meaning during APNP training within higher education programmes. Such dialogue is critical to supporting professional development, ensuring that advanced practice is not seen as a departure from nursing but as an extension of its traditions, values, and expertise.

Through probing discussion and the provocation of my pre-understanding, the significance of role transition began to emerge, as all participants offered narratives of their experiences as the first APNPs appointed within their respective clinical areas. The participants had been qualified paediatric nurses for between 11 and 29 years, and having completed the MSc in Advanced Practice, had been working as APNPs for three to four years. They described the struggle of managing this transition while remaining true to their nursing identity. Alex questioned the uncertainty of the boundary between nursing and "pretending to be mini-doctors," but acknowledged that extensive nursing experience provided a grounding

influence. Implementation of the APNP role was generally ad hoc: while a few units adopted structured approaches, others lacked any formal plan. This variability created a challenging and stressful transition period for many.

Role transition is recognised as a critical stage in preparing practitioners for clinical practice (Hart and Bowen, 2016). Benner's (1982) Novice to Expert model is often used to conceptualise the stages of clinical competence and professional growth. All eight APNPs in this study were senior nurses prior to APNP training and had developed as experts on Benner's continuum. However, upon qualification as APNPs, they were repositioned as novices or advanced beginners, which likely impacted confidence and contributed to anxiety. Andi reflected on the need to construct new knowledge and "peel back the layers" of nursing practice to think differently, a process they found both challenging and stressful.

Barnes (2015), in a survey of 352 nurse practitioners, found that formal orientation was positively associated with a smoother role transition, while prior nursing experience was not significantly associated. Similarly, Hart and Bowen (2016), in a large-scale study of 698 newly graduated nurse practitioners, reported that while most felt prepared for core clinical practice, they were less confident in leadership and other aspects of the role. Challenges at the point of transition were linked to limited orientation and the need for supervision, often provided by medical staff. Officer and McBride-Henry (2021) further highlighted structural barriers arising from differences between nursing and medical education, which can lead to professional misunderstandings and hinder attainment of full scope of practice, an issue also evident in this study.

For the APNPs in this study, transition was further compromised by the lack of structured training once in post. Most training was delivered informally by senior medical staff, and participants reported poor understanding of the role and responsibilities among colleagues and parents. Recent studies confirm that these conditions persist: Kuczawski et al. (2024) and Britton and Blackwood (2024) both identified inconsistent and unstructured role development, difficulties with role identity, and limited public and professional understanding, all of which can hamper transition. Evidence demonstrates that structured transition programmes are beneficial, providing consistent support and reducing stress (Kenny *et al.*, 2021). I had not previously considered transition as a distinct phenomenon within my pre-understanding, and this recognition represents a significant hermeneutic shift for me. Currently, MSc programmes in Scotland do not formally address transition support, despite the substantial shift in responsibility APNPs face across the pillars of practice. On reflection, this gap warrants further research, with greater collaboration between practice providers and higher education institutions to ensure structured, supportive transition processes for APNPs.

The concept of 'Bridging the gap' was highlighted in the narratives, particularly in relation to the APNP role's positioning within the clinical team. From the conversations, it became

evident that the remit of APNPs was to address service needs by improving access to healthcare more efficiently and effectively (Scottish Government, 2017; Scottish Government, 2021). APNPs worked collaboratively with colleagues to ensure that children and families received timely and appropriate treatment, a contribution especially valued in rural areas where resources were limited and workload pressures were acute. Beyond direct clinical care, APNPs provided specialist knowledge, managed complex patient conditions, and demonstrated wider competencies across the four pillars of practice (Barnes, 2015; Kerr and Macaskill, 2020). Their involvement in leadership roles enabled them to advocate for changes to systemic issues, thereby bridging the gap between policy and practice.

Participants' narratives illustrated both the opportunities and challenges inherent in this positioning. Jo described APNPs as occupying an "in-between" space, simultaneously grounded in nursing yet able to navigate the medical domain. This dual identity was a source of satisfaction but also provoked anxiety and, at times, feelings of isolation. Jordan emphasised the tensions that arose when APNPs no longer worked on the nursing rota, noting that nursing colleagues did not always appreciate or understand this shift. At the same time, junior doctors struggled with the authority conferred upon APNPs, which could generate discomfort within team dynamics.

These findings resonate with Britton and Blackwood (2024), who identified similar challenges and argued for the necessity of a more clearly defined role. They further observed that medical hierarchies often reinforced APNPs' professional identity as nurses, thereby maintaining medical primacy and complicating the negotiation of boundaries between professions.

Ruiz (2020) examined multidisciplinary team attitudes towards APNs in UK hospitals and found that advanced practitioners were a key factor in fostering collaborative teamworking. Physicians regarded advanced practitioners as efficient, cost-effective, and capable of appropriate decision-making, and the role was highly valued. However, team members who had not previously worked with advanced practitioners expressed more negative views, raising concerns about potential risks to patient safety. Despite these reservations, the role was predominantly seen as beneficial to patient care and was not perceived as a threat to the medical profession.

A report on professional identity (Academy of Medical Royal Colleges, 2020) highlighted that expanding roles and responsibilities within interprofessional teams can generate resentment or hostility as boundaries begin to overlap. The report outlined a range of teamworking models that have evolved between professions and emphasised the importance of interprofessional education in addressing these challenges. Such education fosters a culture of acceptance, learning, and understanding, ultimately enhancing patient care. Goldsberry (2018) similarly argued that AP nurses are well positioned to lead interprofessional

collaboration, given the nature of their role, and can play a transformative part in reducing barriers within teams.

Within this study, bridging the gap was perceived as a positive addition to clinical teams, as APNPs developed their skills to support children, families, and colleagues. Yet my hermeneutic reflection revealed that while bridging was often celebrated, it also left APNPs exposed and vulnerable, particularly in contexts where support structures were limited. My fusion of horizons occurred as I reflected on my pre-understandings and recognised that APNP narratives and experiences illuminated both the opportunities and risks inherent in 'bridging the gap'. Educationally, interprofessional learning could be further developed to strengthen clinical skill acquisition and decision-making, thereby fostering greater appreciation and understanding between nurses and doctors. Considering these dimensions allowed me to integrate APNP experiences with my pre-understanding, yielding a more informed perspective on the complexities of bridging the gap.

8.2.2 Professional Identity

Professional identity was highlighted as an area of concern by some of the APNPs as the wearing of a national uniform was introduced in 2012 (Scottish Government, 2010, CEL 42), which made some of them feel undermined where previously they had not been expected to wear a nursing uniform in their role. When the new uniform policy was introduced (Scottish Government, 2010, CEL 42) this role was not identified separately, and APNPs had to wear the uniform recognised as worn by registered nurses. Only senior charge nurses wear a different colour uniform at present to denote they are in charge of the clinical area. However, this was problematic for most of the APNPs, as they took a leadership role with patient care, and felt that they should be in a different uniform so that parents could differentiate them from general roles. Interestingly, some of the consultants in their conversations, felt the same, as APNPs were fulfilling a medical as well as nursing role, and felt that they should not be distinguished from junior doctors, as this sometimes created a barrier to parents accepting the level of care APNPs could provide.

Uniforms do play a key role in professional identity and provide clear definition between different occupations. Uniforms help enact occupational boundaries at work, and are symbolic making it easy to delineate between professions. There are very few studies that have looked at uniforms as its main focus, and none can be found looking specifically at the APNP or AP roles. Timmons and East (2011) noted that uniforms did relate to status and professional boundaries and conducted a study examining the boundaries between similar status professions (nursing, physiotherapy, and occupational therapy). Only two previous studies were noted between medicine and nursing (Stein, 1967; Wicks, 1998), in which historical workforce hierarchies are maintained and doctors are not expected to wear a uniform, reinforcing the image that doctors have higher status than other professions.

Professional tribalism is often linked to professional identity and the wearing of uniforms, as practitioners become protective of their perceived core skills to maintain their professional goals (Timmons and East, 2011). A study by Braithwaite *et al.*, (2016) found that professional tribalism existed within multi-professional teams only within the confines of the clinical environment and was largely attributable to traditional workplace hierarchy, the wearing of uniforms, and structures and expectations. However, given that several of the APNPs were concerned about the wearing of a national uniform, and Jo (chapter 5) gave a compelling story for taking the lead in a resuscitation situation where she was questioned in front of the child's family by doctors about her authority to lead the situation because of the uniform she was wearing. One of Jo's remits within the hospital was to be the lead in this situation, but this was challenged due to the uniform she was wearing, the same one that staff nurses wore. Therefore, doctors arriving at the scene assumed they would be in charge of the resuscitation. With the introduction of the national uniform in 2012 (CEL 42), some professional groups feel they may have lost their identity, or when forming new roles, may not think that the uniform they are given gives them the status they require.

A recent development in Scotland has been noted in the SAPEN May newsletter (2024) where the Advanced academies (NES, no date) have carried out one study, and are planning a second study on ANP uniforms. The first was a mixed-methods scoping review of 46 studies examining perceptions of health professionals' uniforms, especially regarding roles that are less understood, such as advanced practitioners. (Cooper *et al.*, 2024), and the second, a Scotland-wide survey is planned to examine patients, visitors, and colleagues' perceptions of ANPs in different coloured uniform tunics. I came to realise that professional identity and the wearing of a uniform are significant topics when I challenged my preunderstandings and listened to the APNPs' perspectives on how they perceive their professional identity. There remains an inconsistency in the approach to uniform-wearing currently, as evidenced by the ongoing work of the Advanced academies and this insight can offer valuable understanding for future research in this area.

In terms of professional identity for the APNP, professional identity is also closely associated with regulation that promotes safe, effective and high standards of practice that improve people's health and wellbeing. Nurses are regulated through the NMC (2018) currently with professional standards articulated that become core values and beliefs for nurses to adhere to. The RCN recently updated their definition of nursing (RCN 2023) to reflect a more contemporary practitioner, whose core graduate and critical thinking skills within increasingly complex clinical environments are acknowledged at undergraduate level. MSc level study is a requirement for working at advanced practice level within the UK, but the exit award requirement at MSc level is dependent on role requirements. Credentialing has also been introduced by the RCN (2020) for APs and is referred to by some as 'semi-regulation' (Oxtoby, 2020) and is acquired through a competency-based assessment process. The process is not without criticism due to its voluntary nature, so unless you apply to go through the process,

you cannot achieve accreditation and it is further criticised as it has a cost associated over and above the NMC annual fees.

At its core, nursing regulation ensures that core knowledge, values and beliefs are embedded for all practitioners (NMC 2018). Separate regulation from the general register held for nurses has long been a contentious subject for advanced practitioners. As identified within Chapter 1, the NMC and CHRE (2010) considered separate regulation for advanced practitioners in 2010, but it was rejected on the basis that AP was regarded as an extension to practice and did not require separate regulatory powers. However, debate continued over expanding roles and public safety, and Brooke and Rushforth (2011) highlighted the need still for separate regulation despite the NMC decision. King *et al.*, (2017) discussed regulation in a doctoral thesis and concluded that, due to the rapid expansion of advanced roles, there should be structured processes in place at both the local and national levels to ensure public protection and suitable preparation for practice for trainees. Recently, due to these ongoing concerns expressed about protecting the public, continuing lack of clarity around the scope of practice in AP roles, and with limited public understanding of the role, an independent report published by the Nuffield Trust (2023) supported the notion of separate regulation. The NMC (2023) also commenced a review on regulation of advanced practice, issuing a recent statement that a variety of options are being considered and that regulation in some format will be introduced in some format. Further public consultation will occur before 2029, to help inform how people think regulation can support both the profession and the public, but may be further complicated with the development of advanced practice across the allied health professions, and the implications of governance and regulation practices between different professions.

Reflecting on the narratives gathered, APNPs in this study supported separate regulation for advanced practice roles, believing it would be beneficial and provide greater clarity for their roles. In my initial pre-understanding, I had not considered the impact of wearing a uniform or the close link between professional identity and regulation. By listening to these narratives and moving from the whole to the part and back to the whole, I was able to understand the importance of professional identity. My new horizon allows me to consider the impact of professional identity on APNPs as they develop, and how organisational and educational support, informed by this information, can be used to feed forward into academic programmes.

8.2.3 Communication and family centredness

Communication skills were identified as central to the development of the APNP role. Advanced communication enables the delivery of high-quality, family-centred services that are both effective and ethically grounded, fostering trusting therapeutic relationships with children, their families, and colleagues (Institute for Healthcare Communication, 2011; Stein

et al., 2022). Yet, within the scope of this role, specific challenges were acknowledged. These often arose in intrateam dynamics, partly due to lack of role clarity, and, as Paton *et al.*, (2013) suggested, because advanced practitioners were sometimes perceived as occupying a “middleman” position within healthcare teams (Stein *et al.*, 2022).

Jordan reflected on the distinction between APNPs and junior doctors, noting: “junior doctors ... just approach things medically ... they have got a list in their head of things that they want to know, whereas I think as a nurse with over twenty years nursing ... as an APNP you approach it differently to a doctor, you just do.” This narrative highlights how APNPs draw on extensive nursing experience to adopt a more holistic, relational approach to communication. A reflective account by King *et al.* (2025) explores the importance of providing family-centred care, requiring the fundamental development of the therapeutic relationship with families and the use of extensive communication skills, especially with parents of acutely unwell children. Gaining parents’ trust and engaging them in their child’s care involves optimal use of both verbal and non-verbal communication techniques. While communication is vital across all healthcare roles, APNPs’ engagement with families introduces an additional dynamic that is integral to paediatric care. Effective communication supports improved health outcomes by providing individualised care, building family-centred relationships, collaborating within teams, and respecting cultural knowledge and traditions (Ridgway *et al.*, 2021). Paediatric nursing is inherently complex, requiring practitioners to facilitate care for both the child and their family (Yehene *et al.*, 2022). APNPs emphasised that their years of nursing experience had honed communication skills they perceived as superior to those of junior doctors. Jordan underscored this distinction, observing that while junior doctors often adopt a task-oriented medical approach, APNPs provide a more comprehensive package of care, taking time to listen, explain, and engage with children and families, thereby approaching healthcare needs in a fundamentally different way.

Across APNPs’ accounts, three key themes consistently emerged: Taking a chance, where APNPs described stepping into new roles that lacked clarity, emphasising the importance of risk-taking and adaptability in advanced practice: Professional identity, the APNPs’ reflections highlighted the continuous negotiation of role boundaries, expertise, recognition, and shaping their integration within multidisciplinary teams: Finally, communication and family-centredness, where a strong emphasis was placed on building trust through clear communication and prioritising the needs of families, ensuring care remained holistic, and family-focused. These themes illustrate how APNPs navigate complex professional landscapes while maintaining a commitment to patient and family wellbeing.

Having outlined the perspectives of APNPs and the three key themes that shaped their experiences, attention now turns to the emergent themes identified among ‘Others’, offering a broad view of how these dynamics resonate across different roles and contexts.

8.3 Others

Three emergent themes developed from my conversations with 'Others' in Chapter 6:

- 8.3.1 Professional identity
- 8.3.2 Bridging the Gap
- 8.3.3. Inconsistency

8.3.1 Professional identity

Although professional identity was discussed previously by the APNPs themselves, the group of 'others' also engaged with this theme, albeit from a different vantage point. The majority regarded the APNP role as that of a highly respected member of the clinical team, uniquely positioned to move fluidly between nursing and medicine. This dual orientation was seen as a clinical strength, complementing existing services and enhancing care provision. Jackie, a consultant paediatrician, captured this sentiment when she observed: "They have got something ... which takes into consideration the medical need as well as the nursing need for the child and family, ... bringing two elements together."

All four consultants expressed support for the role, with three articulating a clear sense of its identity and sustainability, and emphasising their desire to see it continue to develop. However, one consultant framed the APNP position as a temporary solution to medical workforce shortages, specifically gaps in the middle-grade rota. Once recruitment improved, this consultant was explicit that there was no perceived need to train further APNPs, reflecting a more limited and instrumental view of the role. This stance resonates with Britton and Blackwood's (2024) discussion of resistance within the medical community, suggesting that professional identity can be contested and shaped by workforce dynamics as much as by clinical need.

Evidence of interprofessional rivalry also emerged, particularly in rural contexts where opportunities to gain clinical experience were fewer. Junior doctors and APNPs sometimes competed for the same cases, raising tensions around skill acquisition. Stevens *et al.*, (2021), in their systematic review of power and team performance, highlight how such dynamics can undermine communication, decision-making, and collaboration, with potential consequences for patient outcomes. Some junior doctors struggled with the idea of being trained by "a nurse," reflecting entrenched occupational boundaries (Academy of Medical Royal Colleges, 2020). Ainsley, another consultant paediatrician, acknowledged the responsibility of senior medical staff to ensure junior doctors understood the remit of the APNP role and worked in partnership with them. Yet this was framed in a medically driven way, shaped by the limited number of APNPs available at the time to act as mentors.

Chris, a consultant, offered a contrasting perspective, emphasising how APNPs could actively dismantle professional tribalism. He described how some doctors in training arrived with an attitude of superiority, but noted that the APNP's collaborative style quickly broke down barriers: "Doctors in training who still think they are above other people ... [APNP] will very quickly, because of how she works, be able to break down those barriers." Professional tribalism, where occupational groups pursue divergent goals and fail to recognise each other's contributions, has long been recognised as a risk to effective care. Historical failures, such as those identified in the Bristol Royal Infirmary inquiry (Kennedy, 2001), demonstrate the dangers of poor communication and fractured teamwork across professional boundaries. Braithwaite *et al.*, (2016) examined how tribalism and hierarchy manifest in healthcare teams, influencing collaboration and teamwork stereotyping.

Reflecting on these accounts through Gadamer's hermeneutic lens, I came to appreciate the balance required in practice. The APNP role embodies professionalism rooted in nursing expertise, yet extended through advanced training to support junior doctors and strengthen interprofessional collaboration. In this way, APNPs not only contribute to clinical care but also act as mediators across occupational boundaries, fostering dialogue and shared understanding. This interpretation is supported by wider literature (Evans *et al.*, 2020; Kuczawski *et al.*, 2024), which highlights the role of advanced practitioners in bridging divides and enhancing team functioning. As an educationalist, my own horizon was expanded by these insights, prompting me to consider how interprofessional education might further support the development of teamwork and professional identity across disciplines.

Issues of role identity also emerged from nursing staff. Lindsay (2024) discussed tribal tendencies within nursing, particularly around workforce issues and professional boundaries. Lindsay (2024) observed that people tend to develop strong professional identities and alliances within their specialties. While this can foster collaboration and be professionally rewarding, it may also pose challenges as healthcare needs evolve. In this study, one nurse manager raised concerns about the grading of APNPs, noting that their salaries could exceed those of ward managers even though they do not carry equivalent management responsibilities. Entering the hermeneutic circle, I reflected on my own pre-understanding, where I had not initially recognised this as a potential source of tension. This encounter opened a new horizon for me, revealing an unexpected dimension of rivalry between senior nursing roles. It became clear that this reflected a lack of clarity about the distinctions between advanced clinical practice and managerial responsibilities. It underscored the broader challenges in workforce planning and role development highlighted in the literature.

Uniforms were another topic of discussion. All of the nurses, including the director of nursing and nurse managers, felt it was appropriate for APNPs to wear a nursing uniform, believing this reinforced their identity as part of the nursing community (Timmons and East, 2011). Within nursing's hierarchical structures, this was not perceived as problematic. However, APNPs themselves expressed dissatisfaction with wearing the same uniform as other qualified

staff nurses, suggesting it diminished their distinctiveness. Consultants, who did not wear uniforms, also struggled to understand why APNPs were required to do so. Several argued that uniforms created barriers to care, stigmatising APNPs by reinforcing their identification solely as nurses rather than as advanced practitioners. Since these conversations were conducted, the inconsistency regarding the attire of advanced practitioners persists. Although a new uniform for nurse leaders and nurse managers was introduced in 2018, there is still no designated uniform for Advanced Nurse Practitioners (Scottish Government, 2017). Consequently, some continue to wear the cornflower blue uniform traditionally associated with staff nurses, thereby blurring distinctions between advanced and registered nursing roles.

Cooper *et al.*, (2024), in a scoping mixed-methods review of 46 studies, identified diverse perspectives on uniforms across doctors, nurses, and other health professionals. Their findings reinforce earlier arguments that distinct uniforms for advanced roles can be of value (Bryson, 2016). Similarly, Timmons and East (2011) demonstrated that clinical nurse specialists expressed a preference not to wear the same attire as staff nurses, recognising uniforms as symbolic markers of role differentiation. Uniforms, therefore, function as visible signifiers of occupational boundaries and hierarchical position, and their significance becomes particularly salient when considering the distinctions between registered nurses and advanced clinical practice roles.

Within NHS Scotland, ongoing work at the National Academies seeks to address this issue, with some health boards trialling a maroon uniform for advanced practitioners. Whether this initiative will alter perceptions among staff and the public remains uncertain, as the outcomes of these trials have not yet been reported. A further future consideration relates to regulation: with statutory regulation of advanced practice anticipated across the UK nations in 2029 (NMC, 2024), questions arise regarding how uniform policy will align with regulatory frameworks and how this may shape public perceptions of advanced practice.

My fusion of horizons in this context was informed by the strength of nurses' disappointment, who felt undermined by the requirement to wear uniforms indistinguishable from those of staff nurses, and by the recognition that stigmatisation was experienced at times. This tension between professional identity and external markers of status highlights the interpretive complexity of role recognition and warrants further investigation. It is encouraging that this issue is currently under review within the Scottish academies, yet the hermeneutic insight here underscores the need for ongoing dialogue about how symbolic markers such as uniforms intersect with evolving professional identities.

Taken together, the perspectives of nursing staff, consultants, and managers reveal the complexity of professional identity for APNPs. From nursing, tensions emerged around grading and remuneration, reflecting uncertainties in workforce planning and the differentiation of senior roles. Symbolic markers such as uniforms further complicated

identity, situating APNPs within nursing hierarchies while simultaneously stigmatising them in the eyes of medical colleagues. From medicine, critiques centred on educational pathways and perceived reliance on protocols, highlighting structural differences in training and the longer transition required for APNPs to achieve autonomy in clinical decision-making. Entering the hermeneutic circle, my own horizon was expanded by these insights: what initially appeared as isolated concerns became interconnected expressions of how professional identity is negotiated across boundaries of role, hierarchy, and education. In Gadamerian terms, the fusion of horizons here demonstrates that the APNP role is not simply defined by its clinical function, but by the ongoing dialogue between professions, traditions, and expectations.

Finally, doctors reflected on the development and education of APNPs, identifying barriers they perceived as rooted in the traditional undergraduate nursing curriculum. This pathway was characterised, in their view, by an overreliance on protocols and guidelines, which they felt constrained independent problem-solving and clinical reasoning (Martinez-Gonzalez *et al.*, 2014). In contrast, medical education was described as cultivating freedom of thought and diagnostic reasoning from the outset, thereby fostering autonomy earlier in professional formation (Crosskerry and Nimmo, 2011). As a result, doctors argued that APNPs required a longer transition period to retrain in assessment, diagnosis, and treatment in order to achieve the same level of independent decision-making, which reflected similar outcomes in a study by Thompson *et al.*, (2016).

As a nurse, I had not anticipated this for APNPs within my pre-understanding. However, through hermeneutic reflection, I came to recognise that my own horizon was shaped by nursing's hierarchical traditions, which had obscured this perspective. This prompted me to consider more deeply the structural differences between medical and nursing education, both at undergraduate and postgraduate levels, and how these differences influence the trajectory of advanced practice. Notably, I found no comparative studies that systematically examined these educational pathways side by side, highlighting a significant gap in the literature and an important area for future research.

8.3.2 Bridging the Gap

The notion of 'Bridging the gap' emerged as a recurring theme, resonating with insights previously gained from the APNPs' own narratives. The group of 'others' consistently emphasised the value of APNPs' prior nursing experience, which they felt enabled them to deliver what was described as a 'higher level of service.' Central to this appreciation was recognition of the APNPs' ability to move fluidly between nursing and medicine in ways that junior doctors could not. Unlike doctors who rotate every few months, APNPs possess sustained familiarity with clinical areas, allowing them to provide continuity of care.

This higher level of service was articulated through discussions of the APNPs' clinical capabilities: caring for a child from admission through to discharge, undertaking comprehensive assessments, formulating diagnoses, and prescribing pharmacological interventions where appropriate. These skills were complemented by strong communication and partnership working with children and their families, capacities that junior doctors were perceived as lacking. I came to understand that this collection of skills and attributes embodied the idea of 'Bridging the gap,' creating a seamless service for children and families. As Ainsley observed, "It's hard to replicate that! ... junior medical staff just haven't got that yet ..."

Kuczawski *et al.*, (2024) examined how nursing roles, including advanced practice roles, can help 'bridge the gap' in healthcare and improve access to treatments and diagnostics, and, in doing so, described how nurses and advanced practitioners mediate between different professional groups and patient services. My interpretation here suggests that 'bridging the gap' in this study is similar, and captures the unique positioning of APNPs at the intersection of nursing and medicine, and the continuity they provide across professional boundaries. Further research would be valuable to explore the meaning and implications of 'Bridging the gap,' particularly in relation to organisational practice and educational programmes, where the development of advanced roles continues to evolve.

8.3.3 Inconsistency

Clinical supervision provides essential support and opportunities for advanced practitioners at all stages of their development. It enables reflection on practice, discussion of clinical cases, recognition of good practice, and identification of areas where change may be required (Lee *et al.*, 2022). Given the relatively new and evolving nature of the APNP role, all participants in this study had initially been mentored by senior medical staff, predominantly consultants, to facilitate the acquisition of advanced clinical skills. As APNPs became embedded within their clinical areas, however, supervision structures shifted. In some contexts, supervision was provided by clinical managers or other nurses, reflecting variability in how the role was integrated (Lee *et al.*, 2022).

Two key concerns emerged from these conversations. The first relates to the differing approaches to supervision and role modelling across clinical areas, particularly the contrast between medical and nursing supervision models. Consultants expressed frustration that nurse leaders often lacked a clear understanding of the APNP role and did not engage with them, which created divisions and, at times, resentment. This lack of alignment meant that APNPs could be disadvantaged, as they did not fit neatly into either nursing or medical teams. Such ambiguity highlights the need for careful consideration of supervision structures in future role development. This is another approach that the Scottish academies are currently reviewing, and recommending a consistent approach throughout Scotland, as previously

identified however, this may take time to filter down to all areas, and should be reviewed regularly.

The second concern centred on inconsistencies in service provision. In some areas, APNPs were deployed to provide 24-hour cover, ensuring sustainable and equitable services. In contrast, other units had only a single APNP, limiting service availability to the shifts they worked. Larger units with multiple APNPs were able to provide continuous cover and were actively planning for sustainability by training additional APNPs. These disparities illustrate how local workforce planning significantly shapes the scope and impact of the role.

Despite all APNPs receiving core training across different institutions, role clarity and function remains inconsistent (Nuffield Trust, 2023). The direction of the role is heavily influenced by local context and reporting structures (Thompson *et al.*, 2025). Larger health boards tend to have more organised service provision, while smaller or rural areas demonstrate greater variability. While some APNPs were working in community settings, this is not yet universally available. Current work within the Scottish academies seeks to map services across Scotland and inform future workforce planning. Nevertheless, role clarity and scope of practice remain uneven.

My pre-understanding, shaped by prior exposure to the literature, had already sensitised me to issues of role ambiguity. However, my fusion of horizons through these conversations confirmed that, despite progress in advancing the advanced practice agenda within Scotland and the wider UK, significant inconsistencies persist. The findings underscore the ongoing need for dialogue, structural support, and policy development to ensure that the APNP role is both clearly defined and sustainably embedded across diverse clinical contexts.

In summary, within the perspectives of 'Others', three key themes emerged: First, professional identity, where participants reflected on how APNPs roles were shaped and sometimes challenged by evolving expectations, highlighting tensions in recognition and legitimacy; Secondly, Bridging the gap, where 'Others' accounts revealed efforts to connect across professional boundaries and service structures, underscoring the importance of collaboration in meeting complex needs; Finally, Inconsistency, where experiences pointed to variability in provision and demand, exposing gaps in continuity of care.

Viewed through my Fusion of Horizons, these themes illustrate how understanding and meaning develop through the hermeneutic circle, and my perspective on 'Others' highlighted similarities with APNPs, introduced new insights, and raised tensions around identity and service delivery.

This interpretive synthesis prepares the reader for the next section, where the main themes from parents' conversations are examined. Their voices contribute a new perspective to the

dialogue, enriching the understanding of family experiences and their interaction with professional practice.

8.4 Parents

In continuing this Fusion of Horizons, the perspectives of parents are brought into dialogue, extending the interpretive process by revealing how parental experiences and meaning contribute to and develop the key themes identified. There is currently no research demonstrating parental understanding of the APNP role utilising a Gadamerian hermeneutic approach.

Three emergent themes developed from my conversations with parents in Chapter 7, specifically the parents of a child who had been cared for by an APNP in the three months before the conversations, so that they have fresh memories of their experiences:

- 8.4.1 Bridging the gap
- 8.4.2 Communication skills and clinical competence
- 8.4.3 Caring Behaviour

8.4.1 Bridging the gap

When children are unwell, the experience is recognised as a profoundly complex and emotionally charged time for families (Jackson *et al.*, 2008). While such circumstances may be routine for healthcare professionals, they are often marked by stress, uncertainty, and vulnerability for parents (Wray *et al.*, 2011). It is therefore essential to explore how parents perceive and understand the role of the APNP during these periods of heightened emotional intensity.

In engaging with parents, I was compelled to question my own pre-understandings, particularly the assumption that parents would recognise and value the advanced clinical skills that distinguish APNPs from other nurses or junior doctors. Despite my attempts to elicit such distinctions, parents were unable to articulate differences in clinical competence. Similarly, Cescutti-Butler and Gavin (2003) found that parents in a neonatal intensive care unit did not primarily recognise technical or advanced skills. Instead, they valued behaviours that offered emotional reassurance and support. Kinder and Allen (2014) used a validated tool to measure parental satisfaction with paediatric nurse practitioners and discovered that parents consistently prioritised relational aspects of care over technical skills. Likewise, Egerton (2012) examined the role of the APNP in emergency care settings and found that families often perceived the role primarily in terms of accessibility and relational support, rather than

technical expertise. These studies align closely with my findings, underscoring that parental understanding of professional competence is relational and experiential rather than technical. Through hermeneutic reflection, my horizon was reshaped. I came to understand that parents do not require detailed knowledge of the APNP role or its clinical competencies; rather, what matters is the demonstration of competence, fairness, kindness, and responsiveness to family needs. This realisation constituted a significant fusion of horizons, as I came to recognise that my professional emphasis on advanced clinical skillsets was shaped by educational frameworks (NES, 2008; RCN 2018) and was not mirrored in parental perspectives. For parents, the essence of the APNP role was not defined by technical expertise but by relational qualities: providing peace of mind, alleviating isolation, and cultivating confidence and trust.

Narratives from families vividly illustrated this. As an example, Lorna and Adam described how their experience with an APNP enabled them to manage their daughter's complex health needs at home during times of crisis, avoiding the difficulties of accessing GP services or hospital care. Aitchison *et al.*, (2020) examined systemic barriers in child health services for families with children who have complex healthcare needs, finding that these families often face difficulties in accessing timely and coordinated care. The Scottish Government (2023) provided guidance for families concerning disabled children, once again highlighting the stresses faced by families caring for children at home and emphasising the importance of early, accessible support to reduce the vulnerability of the entire family and enhance their wellbeing. The ability of the parents from this research study to contact their APNP for treatment or advice provided them with reassurance and security. Similarly, Margaret emphasised the accessibility and attentiveness of her APNP, whose advocacy and support reduced hospital admissions and allowed her child to remain in the home environment often, an outcome that mitigated feelings of isolation and reinforced parental confidence. Collectively, these accounts demonstrate how APNPs 'Bridge a gap' in care provision, offering a form of support previously unavailable to families.

Other studies have tended to focus on parental satisfaction rather than understanding of the APNP role (Kinder and Allen, 2014; Kinder, 2016; Loureiro and Antunes, 2022). For example, Thibodeau *et al.*, (2022) reported high levels of satisfaction among Canadian parents whose children were cared for by APNPs, with positive evaluations linked to communication, clinical competence, caring behaviours, and shared decision-making. However, such studies are often reliant on quantitative measures (Kinder and Allen, 2014) and lack the narrative depth that characterises my hermeneutic approach. By prioritising parental narratives, this study offers a richer account of understanding and meaning, situating parental perspectives within their lived realities of care.

The broader literature on nurse practitioners has largely emphasised effectiveness, efficiency, and cost-effectiveness in service delivery (Newhouse *et al.*, 2011; Aitchison *et al.*, 2020;

Martin-Misener *et al.*, 2015). Yet there remains a notable absence of research exploring parental understanding of the APNP role, from the perspective of parents whose child has been cared for by an APNP within NHS Scotland. This study, therefore, contributes uniquely to the discourse by illuminating how APNPs are experienced as relational figures who bridge the gap between professional expertise and parental need, thereby embodying the essence of care as families understand it.

In this way, my engagement with parental narratives, alongside reflection on my own pre-understandings, exemplifies Gadamer's (2012) iterative process of understanding, in which horizons are continually reshaped through dialogue with the participant's text and the evolving literature. This hermeneutic movement not only enriched my analysis but also illuminated how the essence of APNP care is revealed in the lived experiences of families, thereby preparing the ground for the subsequent discussion.

8.4.2 Communication skills and clinical competence

Within the narratives, parents consistently emphasised the centrality of communication in shaping their understanding of the APNP role. Trust was cultivated through personal and effective communication, which parents described as more relational and family-centred than their experiences with other professionals. For example, Lisa, whose child was an inpatient, highlighted the value of the APNP's ability to explain clinical processes in language accessible to both parent and child, thereby reducing uncertainty and fostering reassurance. Similarly, Wendy described the importance of being listened to in the busy ward environment, where the APNP's attentiveness provided a sense of recognition and support often absent in interactions with other staff. Cusson *et al.*, (2021) highlight from a systematic review evaluating communication with parents in paediatric patient settings, the critical role of communication in supporting parents during stressful situations. Cusson *et al.*'s., (2021) study determines that effective communication is central to parental understanding, trust, and satisfaction in child healthcare.

All parents identified the APNP as demonstrating excellent communication skills, consistently keeping them informed and engaged in care decisions. The importance of this cannot be ignored, and this contrasts with their experiences of other nurses, who frequently deferred to colleagues for information, which they found frustrating, and junior doctors, whose inexperience limited their communicative competence (Jacobs *et al.*, 2023; Nagra *et al.*, 2024). Through these accounts, I came to appreciate that communication and rapport were not ancillary but integral to parental perceptions of competence. For example, Lorna and Adam articulated this by describing the APNP as offering something "deeper... more personal... understood us more as a family," which illuminated the holistic, family-centred nature of APNP practice. This relational approach, grounded in prior nursing experience and professional development (Scottish Government, 2017b) enabled parents to participate

meaningfully in shared decision-making, thereby reinforcing confidence in care and, in many cases, preventing hospital readmission.

Parents also observed that APNPs were respected by other professionals, particularly doctors, and that their attentiveness to APNP contributions enhanced parental confidence in the care process. This is supported by several studies that found medical colleagues often valued and expressed confidence in advanced practitioner roles, particularly in their ability to deliver safe, effective care, enhance service efficiency, and increase patient satisfaction (Fothergill *et al.*, 2022; Scott, 2024). This respect was not only symbolic but also functional, as it positioned APNPs as advocates for children and families. In addition, Hanks *et al.*, (2019) conducted a pilot study on patient advocacy by advanced practice registered nurses in the United States. The study explored how these nurses experience and practice advocacy, revealing that advocacy is primarily a learned skill, developed through experience. Experienced nurses have improved medical knowledge, thus enhancing their ability to advocate for patients. Indeed, Choi (2015) describes advocacy as a means of ensuring that parental voices are heard and acted upon. This directly relates to the parental experiences of the APNPs in the study, who were often described as acting as advocates in clinical settings. For example, Margaret recounted how her APNP attended meetings with her to speak on her behalf. At the same time, Wendy noted that the APNP stood up for parents who often felt marginalised by medical hierarchies. Such advocacy extended beyond clinical competence to encompass relational and ethical dimensions of practice, reinforcing the APNP's role as a bridge between families and the wider healthcare system.

In this study, advocacy was closely linked to shared decision-making, as parents reported feeling more in control when APNPs supported them in navigating complex care decisions. This aligns with Jackson *et al.*, (2008), whose systematic review identified parental need for control in child health decision-making, and with subsequent studies (Lindberg *et al.*, 2012; Bradshaw, 2013) that emphasised the importance of relational communication in enabling parental participation. Conversely, the loss of control was associated with anxiety, despair, and isolation, experiences echoed by some parents in this study.

Through hermeneutic reflection, my horizon was reshaped, and the narratives revealed that communication skills and clinical competence were understood relationally, through communication, advocacy, and trust. This fusion of horizons illuminated that the essence of APNP practice, as perceived by parents, lies not in technical differentiation but in the relational and dialogical qualities that enable families to feel safe, supported, and empowered.

8.4.3 Caring Behaviour

Parents described a range of situations in our conversations that related to differences in the care approach by APNPs compared to other staff, particularly junior doctors, and how this care demonstrated a higher level of care to them. Their narratives revealed that APNPs offered what was described as “more”, a higher level of care that encompassed not only technical competence but also relational attentiveness and holistic concern. This sense of “more” was expressed through feelings of safety for parents, reassurance, and satisfaction that their child’s care was delivered in a manner attentive to both clinical and emotional needs. Other studies demonstrate the importance of providing holistic and family-centred care for families in hospital (Lindberg *et al.*, 2007; Coyne *et al.*, 2016).

In entering the hermeneutic circle, my pre-understanding was challenged by the parents’ emphasis on caring behaviours. As an example, Wendy’s account exemplifies this: she described her distress when junior doctors repeatedly attempted intravenous cannulation without attending to her child’s suffering, remarking, “He’s not a guinea pig!” In contrast, the APNP then performed the procedure swiftly and calmly, reassuring the child throughout, which demonstrated a holistic approach to care. For Wendy, trust was established not simply through technical success but through the APNP’s ability to integrate clinical skill with relational care.

Pete similarly described “more” as the APNP being hands-on, confident, and comfortable in both clinical and interpersonal domains. He observed the ease with which the APNP communicated with his child, himself, and other staff, contrasting this with the task-oriented and less assured approach of junior doctors as well. For Pete, this demonstrated qualities of caring behaviour, a trait consistently echoed across parental accounts.

These narratives resonate with wider evidence. Systematic reviews and meta-analyses (Newhouse *et al.*, 2011; Martínez-González *et al.*, 2014) have demonstrated that advanced practitioners achieve positive outcomes, including higher patient satisfaction, reduced hospital admissions, and improved mortality. Within the hermeneutic dialogue of this study, however, the meaning of such outcomes was illuminated through parental voices: APNPs were valued not only for the visual effectiveness of care provided, but also for the relational essence of their practice, which made families feel safe and recognised.

Through Gadamer’s philosophical hermeneutics (Gadamer, 2012) and following Fleming *et al.*, (2003) methodological approach, my horizon of understanding was reshaped within this emergent theme. What parents considered important was the demonstration of caring behaviour that was “more”, more holistic, more personal, and more attuned to the child and family.

8.5 Summary statement

In synthesising the emergent themes across APNPs, 'others' and parents, a complex picture of advanced paediatric practice emerges. For APNPs, the themes of taking a chance, professional identity, communication, and family-centredness highlight the evolving nature of their role as both clinically autonomous and relationally grounded. For 'others', the themes of professional identity, bridging the gap, *and* inconsistency in the service context *reflect* both recognition of APNPs' value and the ongoing challenges of role definition and integration within wider healthcare systems. For parents, the emphasis on bridging the gap, communication skills and clinical competence, and caring behaviour underscores that the essence of APNP practice is experienced through trust, advocacy, and holistic care.

This hermeneutic dialogue, situated within Gadamer's philosophical hermeneutic framework (Gadamer, 2012) and interpreted through Fleming *et al's.*, (2003) methodological lens, demonstrates how horizons of understanding are reshaped through engagement with parental narratives, professional perspectives, and policy discourse. This Fusion of Horizons illuminates the APNP role as one that bridges systemic gaps, offering continuity and reassurance in contexts often marked by inconsistency.

These findings must be understood within the wider UK landscape of advanced practice. Since 2016, policy initiatives across the devolved nations (Department of Health, 2016; Scottish Government, 2017; Health Education England, 2017; Welsh Government, 2020; Scottish Government, 2021) have sought to establish multidisciplinary pathways. Despite these developments, advanced practice remains inconsistently defined, with enduring challenges relating to regulation, governance, and the standardisation of training (Brookes and Rushforth, 2011; King *et al.*, 2017; Nadaf, 2018; Mackavey, 2024). The creation of the Scottish Advanced Practice Academies (NES, no date) and the NES NMAHP Post-registration Development Framework (NES, 2023) represent important steps towards greater clarity and sustainability. Nevertheless, the diversity of roles and differences in clinical boards approaches across NHS Scotland continues to complicate professional identity and scope. With regulation for advanced practice now emerging on the horizon, further challenges are anticipated, and it is unlikely that these issues will be resolved swiftly (NMC, 2024).

Thus, the hermeneutic insights from this study contribute to an understanding and meaning of the APNP role from a whole system perspective of service providers and service users, and add to the broader discourse on advanced practice in the UK. By highlighting and discussing the emergent themes found through my conversations with both service providers and service users, this chapter demonstrates that the sustainability of APNP roles depends as much on APNPs' relational essence as on their advanced clinical competence. In particular, the parent narrative adds another dimension to the analysis of role development for APNPs. In this way, the valued experiences of these different groups of people provide a vital narrative evidence base for shaping future role development, ensuring that advanced practice

in Scotland and beyond remains both clinically effective and holistically attuned to the needs of children and their families.

Final note:

In accordance with Gadamer's philosophical hermeneutics (Gadamer, 2012), I acknowledge that understanding is never fixed or definitive. Understanding emerges through the *fusion of horizons*, shaped by the interpreter's historical and cultural context, language, and dialogue. Thus, the interpretations presented here reflect my horizon of understanding, developed through engagement with service providers (APNPs and 'Others') and service users' (parents') narratives, perspectives, and policy discourse. Others, approaching the same texts from different horizons, may arrive at alternative interpretations. This plurality does not undermine the validity of my analysis; rather, it reflects Gadamer's conviction that understanding is dialogical, open-ended, and always subject to further questioning (Gadamer, 2012).

Chapter 9 will now provide concluding remarks and discuss why this study is significant.

CHAPTER NINE – CONCLUDING REMARKS - MAKING A DIFFERENCE

9.1 Contribution to new knowledge

The APNP role has become a central component of workforce strategy and healthcare role development across NHS Scotland and the wider UK, and continues to evolve in response to service demands (Scottish Government, 2017; Scottish Government, 2021). Yet, despite its growing prominence, there remains a notable paucity of evidence addressing many aspects of the role, particularly from the perspective of patient experience and understanding. Much of the existing literature is dominated by value-based research, focusing on efficiency and effectiveness of roles and services (Jones, 2005; Newhouse et al., 2011; Kilpatrick et al., 2024), reflecting the pressures of financial constraint and the imperative to demonstrate value for money.

This thesis represents the first study in Scotland, and indeed the UK, to explore the Advanced Paediatric Nurse Practitioner (APNP) role through three distinct perspectives: APNPs themselves, professional colleagues, and parents. By adopting this triangulated lens, the research advances understanding of role development beyond the traditional focus on clinical competence alone.

- Relational essence as a core dimension: The findings demonstrate that relational qualities—such as communication, empathy, and trust-building—are as critical as clinical expertise in shaping the APNP role. This challenges prevailing assumptions that competence is primarily technical, and instead positions relational practice as integral to professional identity and effectiveness.
- Narrative evidence from multiple stakeholders: The study foregrounds the valued experiences of APNPs, colleagues, and parents, providing rich narrative evidence that supports the ongoing refinement and future development of the role. This multi-perspective approach offers a more holistic understanding of how APNPs are perceived and how their contributions are enacted in practice.
- Illumination of the parent voice: Crucially, this thesis is the first to systematically capture and analyse parent narratives regarding the APNP role. Parents articulate the unique value of APNPs in bridging the gap between nursing and medicine, highlighting their appreciation for excellent communication skills, clinical competence, and caring behaviours rooted in prior nursing experience. This perspective has not previously been illuminated in the literature and provides vital insights into family-centred care and role legitimacy.

Significance:

By integrating professional and parental perspectives, this thesis contributes new knowledge that:

- Reframes APNP role development as a balance of relational and clinical dimensions.
- Establishes narrative evidence as a powerful tool for shaping policy, education, and practice.
- Positions parent perspectives as essential in evaluating and legitimising advanced nursing roles.

This work therefore extends the conceptualisation of the APNP role, offering a foundation for future scholarship, workforce planning, and practice development in paediatric advanced nursing.

9.2 My influence on the hermeneutic process

Tranøy (1986) suggests that research affords the opportunity to distinguish between the significant and the insignificant, granting freedom to challenge assumptions and to form logical-deductive conclusions. This principle resonates strongly with the hermeneutic process, which is grounded in a philosophy of understanding and the art of interpretation (Gadamer, 2012). As a novice researcher, I deliberately chose Gadamer's philosophical hermeneutics to uncover the nature of human understanding by continually questioning how understanding is possible.

Through engagement with the hermeneutic circle, I found that meaning could be achieved by moving iteratively between parts and the whole, guided by Gadamer's key concepts and supported by the methodological framework of Fleming *et al.*, (2003). This process enabled me to enter the hermeneutic circle and gain a deeper understanding and meaning, though inevitably bounded by the time and resource limitations of doctoral study. These constraints required me to formulate an acceptable endpoint, while recognising that hermeneutic understanding is always provisional and open to further development.

Using a Gadamerian approach provided the conditions to facilitate understanding as the APNP role continues to evolve. Given the emergent and widespread development of advanced practice both nationally and internationally, this study holds relevance across professions, contributing to healthcare research knowledge and transformation by illuminating the scope and challenges of the APNP role from the perspectives of both service users and service providers.

A consistent limitation across existing studies of advanced practice roles, including large scale surveys such as Fothergill *et al.*, (2020) and qualitative case studies like Walker and Hooks

(2020), is the absence of service user perspectives. While these studies offer valuable insights into role development, governance, and professional satisfaction, they remain incomplete without the voices of those who directly experience care. The omission of parents and service users risks reducing advanced practice evaluation to a professional exercise, overlooking the human dimension of healthcare delivery.

This study addresses that gap by explicitly including parents' perspectives alongside those of APNPs and colleagues. In doing so, it demonstrates how service providers' and service users' voices reshape and extend understanding of the emergent themes in this study and the APNP role. Gadamer's hermeneutic philosophy emphasises that meaning emerges through dialogue and the fusion of horizons. By bringing parents into this dialogue alongside the APNP and 'others', the research achieves a richer interpretive synthesis that situates the APNP's role not only within professional and organisational frameworks but also with Dasein, 'being-in-the-world' of families.

9.3 Implications for advanced practice

There is no doubt that the role of the APNP is vital to the ongoing development of the healthcare workforce to meet the needs of NHS Scotland (Scottish Government, 2021). The implications of this study are considered in relation to practice, policy, and education, while also identifying areas for future research.

Practice

- Current evidence primarily supports the efficiency and effectiveness of APNP roles, though this remains limited in scope.
- Service user perspectives highlight relational and communicative dimensions of care that efficiency metrics alone cannot capture.
- This study is the first hermeneutic inquiry to give voice to three distinct groups: APNPs, 'Others' working alongside them, and parents experiencing the role. This triangulation of perspectives highlights the need for further follow-up studies to deepen understanding of the role's impact on patient and family care.
- Advanced practitioners must continue to develop the knowledge and skills required to evidence the impact of their practice. Insights from this research have potential applicability across other advanced roles within the NHS. Advanced practice academies should support research across all specialisms to support ongoing development of roles.

Policy

- Managers, educationalists, policy makers, and workforce planners should collaborate more closely to ensure APNPs are supported to utilise their skills fully, with consistent mechanisms for evidencing value.
- Incorporating parent voices ensures that workforce planning and role development remain grounded in patient-centred values rather than solely in financial imperatives.
- While advanced academies in Scotland have begun this work, it must be embedded and expanded to provide a clear strategic direction. This includes the development of standardised educational programmes aligned with clinical practice specialisms.
- The ongoing blurring of professional boundaries, consistently noted in the literature, and demonstrated through conversations in this study, requires further exploration as roles are embedded. The lack of standardisation across Scotland and the UK continues to challenge role development, raising questions about professional identity.
- With the introduction of regulation on advanced practice on the horizon (2029), the impact of this on role clarity and standardisation should be followed up.

Education

- Regulation could play a key role in supporting the development of APNP education, providing a framework for standardised course content and ensuring consistency across programmes. This should be closely monitored.
- Embedding service user narratives into training can foster empathy, strengthen family-centred practice, and prepare APNPs for the complexities of real-world care, and therefore should be integrated into all programmes. Programmes could also invite service users to discuss their experiences in person.
- Interprofessional training should be prioritised to foster greater appreciation of different roles, strengthen communication, and enhance collaborative teamworking.

Future Research Opportunities

- As the APNP role continues to evolve, further research is required to clarify the scope of practice and explore its impact on patient and family care within NHS Scotland.
- Future studies must systematically include service users to generate evidence that is both credible and meaningful, ensuring advanced practice roles evolve in ways that genuinely meet patient and family needs.
- Studies should investigate the implications of boundary blurring and role variation across the UK, with particular attention to professional identity and regulation.
- Crucially, future research must include both service users and service providers. Incorporating these perspectives will generate more comprehensive evidence to inform role development, policy, and practice.

9.4 Limitations to the study

While undertaking this study as a novice researcher, several limitations became apparent, which, as Thomas (2013) recommends, should be acknowledged.

- **Geographic Representation:** The study was conducted across eight health boards within NHS Scotland, encompassing both rural and urban contexts. However, this does not equate to equal representation of all areas. One APNP and one 'other' participant were recruited from each of these boards, while parent participation was more limited, only five parents (including one couple) from four health boards. Given that Scotland comprises 14 regional NHS boards, seven special boards, and one public health body, the findings cannot be assumed to be representative of the whole of Scotland or transferable elsewhere.
- **Parent Participant Bias:** Four of the five parents had children with chronic conditions, which may have influenced both their willingness to participate and their perceptions of the APNP role, particularly if they had longer-term relationships with APNPs. Although these participants met the study criteria, this introduces potential bias. Future research should seek to include a wider variety of parents, particularly those whose children have experienced only acute episodes of illness, to broaden the scope of perspectives.
- **Researcher Positionality:** Demographic data were collected from all participant groups (age, employment, educational background, qualifications, and relationship with the APNP). While useful for grouping within the study, I acknowledge that my own professional role, as an educator and collaborator with clinical practice staff in the HEI sector, may have unconsciously influenced the interpretation of the findings.
- **Hermeneutic Process:** Gadamer (2012) emphasises that proper understanding requires moving within the hermeneutic circle, oscillating between the parts and the whole. There is an inherent risk that the researcher may leave the dialogue too quickly, resulting in interpretations that could be considered arbitrary. This limitation is particularly relevant in doctoral research, where time and resource constraints necessitate an endpoint that may not capture the full depth of possible understanding.
- **Sample Size and Diversity:** The sample size within each group was small and restricted to English-speaking participants. Consequently, the findings cannot be assumed to represent the experiences of service providers and service users from different cultural or linguistic backgrounds.

Despite these limitations, the study makes a significant and original contribution. By adopting Gadamerian hermeneutics and incorporating the perspectives of APNPs, colleagues, and parents, it offers a richer, more holistic understanding of the APNP role than has previously been achieved. While the sample size and scope were necessarily constrained, the insights

generated provide a strong foundation for future research and highlight the importance of including service user voices in evaluating the APNP role and advanced practice.

9.5 Doing Things Differently in Future Research (Recommendations)

While this study has provided valuable insights into the evolving role of the APNP within NHS Scotland, several methodological and strategic refinements could strengthen future research.

First, the scope of stakeholder perspectives could be broadened. This hermeneutic inquiry incorporated the voices of APNPs, 'others', and parents, but subsequent studies should systematically include patients (parents/children), policymakers, and educators. Such expansion would generate a more comprehensive understanding of the role's impact across healthcare. Comparative studies across different NHS Scotland regions, and indeed across the wider UK, would also illuminate variations in practice and professional identity, particularly in light of ongoing boundary blurring.

Second, methodological diversification is recommended. While qualitative inquiry remains essential for capturing relational and communicative dimensions of care, mixed-methods designs that integrate quantitative outcome measures, such as patient satisfaction, workforce efficiency, and clinical effectiveness, would enhance generalisability and provide a stronger evidence base for policy and workforce planning. Longitudinal designs could further capture how APNP roles and family experiences evolve, offering insights into sustained impact rather than snapshot perspectives.

Third, service user integration must be embedded as a central feature of future research. Co-production approaches, in which parents and/or children act as research partners, would ensure that findings remain grounded in patient-centred values rather than financial imperatives. Additional interpretative methods, such as diaries or repeated/ongoing interviews, could provide richer accounts of family experiences and strengthen the credibility of evidence used to inform role development.

Fourth, future studies should explicitly address policy and educational implications. With the regulation of advanced practice anticipated in 2029, longitudinal research should track how role clarity, boundaries, and professional identity shift before and after implementation. Similarly, the evaluation of educational programmes, particularly those that embed service-user narratives and interprofessional training, would provide evidence on how best to prepare APNPs for the complexities of clinical care.

In summary, while this study has contributed an important foundation, future research must adopt broader, more inclusive, and methodologically diverse approaches. Doing so will generate evidence that is both credible and meaningful, ensuring that advanced practice roles

evolve in ways that genuinely meet patient and family needs while supporting the long-term sustainability of roles within NHS Scotland.

9.6 Reflection on the study process and revisiting the aim of this study

My intention throughout this research has been to provide an honest, logical, and clear representation of Gadamer's philosophical hermeneutics, which has guided me towards achieving a fusion of horizons. In keeping with the hermeneutic principles outlined in Chapter 3 and the methodological approach outlined in Chapter 4, I have sought to form a new horizon of understanding of the APNP role.

The overarching aim of this study was to gain meaning and understanding of the APNP role from a whole-systems perspective, encompassing both service providers and service users. To achieve this, three objectives were pursued: first, to explore APNPs' perspectives of their role; second, to investigate the views of multidisciplinary colleagues ('others') working alongside APNPs; and third, to examine parent perspectives on APNP service delivery.

These aims and objectives have been realised through the application of Gadamer's philosophical hermeneutic concepts, operationalised via the methodological framework of Fleming *et al.*, (2003). By working methodically within the hermeneutic circle—moving between parts and whole, dialogue and interpretation, I have been able to uncover new insights into the APNP role. This process has not only achieved the study's stated aim but also demonstrated the value of hermeneutic inquiry in capturing the complexity of advanced practice roles as experienced by both service providers and service users of healthcare.

9.7 Theoretical decisions

As a novice researcher, I recognised that Gadamer's philosophical hermeneutics does not prescribe a specific method. However, Gadamer does not dismiss the use of method; rather, he acknowledges the value of a systematised approach as a means of achieving understanding (Gadamer, 2012). In order to reach the fusion of horizons that was central to the study's aim, it was necessary to adopt a methodological framework that could support the interpretive process.

A review of the literature identified several studies that had employed Gadamerian philosophical hermeneutics. Among these, the work of Fleming *et al.*, (2003) stood out as remaining most congruent with Gadamer's principles while offering a systematic and coherent method. Their framework provided a clear pathway for engaging with the hermeneutic circle, enabling the interpretation of conversations while maintaining fidelity to Gadamer's philosophy. This congruence was not evident in other studies reviewed, which reinforced the decision to adopt Fleming *et al's.*, (2003) methodological approach.

9.8 Concluding statement

This thesis has illuminated the evolving role of the APNP within NHS Scotland, situating it within the wider UK and international context of advanced practice development. While existing studies have primarily focused on efficiency, effectiveness, and governance, they have consistently overlooked service users' perspectives. By explicitly including parents alongside APNPs and 'Others' this study addresses that gap, demonstrating how service user voices reshape and extend understanding of the role.

Guided by Gadamer's philosophical hermeneutics and the methodological framework of Fleming *et al.*, (2003), the research process itself became a fusion of horizons. As a novice researcher, I entered the hermeneutic circle to question how understanding is possible, delineating between the significant and the insignificant (Tranøy, 1986). Through this interpretive play, I came to appreciate that meaning is developmental, provisional, and always open to further dialogue. The inclusion of parent perspectives exemplifies this, bringing the Dasein 'being-in-the-world' of families into conversation with professional and organisational frameworks, and thereby achieving a richer synthesis of understanding and meaning.

The implications are clear. For practice, APNPs must continue to evidence the impact of their roles, not only through efficiency metrics but also through narratives of patient and family experience. For policy, closer collaboration between managers, educators, and workforce planners is required to embed consistent frameworks and support role sustainability. For education, regulation, and curricula standardisation, alongside interprofessional training, will strengthen role clarity and teamworking. For research, future studies must systematically include both service users and service providers to ensure that advanced practice evaluation remains holistic, human-centred, and transformative.

This thesis makes a unique contribution to knowledge as the first study in Scotland, and the wider UK, to explore the Advanced Paediatric Nurse Practitioner (APNP) role from three perspectives: APNPs, professional colleagues, and parents. By integrating these voices, the research demonstrates that relational essence embodied in communication, empathy, and caring behaviours is as vital as clinical competence in shaping new role development. The study provides narrative evidence from multiple stakeholders, offering a holistic understanding of how APNPs are perceived and legitimised in practice. Most significantly, it illuminates the parent perspective for the first time, revealing their appreciation of APNPs' ability to bridge the gap between nursing and medicine, their clinical expertise, and the caring behaviours rooted in prior nursing experience. These insights extend existing conceptualisations of the APNP role and provide a foundation for supporting future workforce planning, education, and policy development in advanced paediatric nursing practice.

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APPENDICES

Appendix 1: Table identifying other interpretivist methods considered

Method	Consideration	Rationale for use/not using
Phenomenology	Focus on lived experience of a particular phenomenon	Lived experience is descriptive and can be ambiguous, doesn't require the application of deeper understanding.
Grounded theory	Developing theories from data on a phenomenon or action	Developing a theory is not the aim of this thesis.
Ethnography	Understanding cultures by describing behaviours, beliefs and values – researchers situate themselves within a cultural group to observe its functioning	As there are three different groups under study in this thesis, the aim is not to describe cultural behaviours, beliefs or values.
Narrative Inquiry	Exploring life stories of individuals through complex stories of personal journeys	Exploring life stories and personal journeys explicitly was not the aim of this thesis.
Case study	Involves intensive investigation of a single case to provide contextualised understanding of an issue	A case study methodology does not align to the aims of this thesis.
Discourse analysis	Uses language and communication to understand how identity and roles are constructed and maintained within a specific context	This methodology examines how language is used as a social practice to construct meanings, power dynamics and social reality instead of developing a deeper understanding of text.
IPA	Focuses on how people make sense of personal experience. An account of lived experience but not prescribed by any pre-existing theoretical concepts.	Although IPA uses hermeneutics as a core analytical component, it fails to recognise that the hermeneutic circle starts with one's own pre-conceptions which is part of Gadamer's philosophical hermeneutic framework.

Appendix 2: Use of Gadamer in other studies.

The following studies were therefore critically reviewed because they claimed to use Gadamerian hermeneutic principles and helped inform my decision for using Fleming et al's (2003) methodological approach. Fleming et al (2003) did critique previously written Gadamerian based studies as part of their research, however, I considered the time elapsed since their paper was published in 2003, and in order to further justify my use of it, I have reviewed other research articles published between 2004 to 2015 that either claimed to use the method of Fleming et al (2003) or challenged it by offering an alternative method using Gadamer's hermeneutic philosophical underpinning. The following papers reviewed here are presented chronologically.

Gadamerian based studies:

Howlin's (2008) study aimed to illuminate understanding and interpret the experience of children's nurses' advocacy experience utilising a philosophical hermeneutic approach that had been inspired by Gadamer. Howlin (2008) suggested that this allowed the aims of the study to be achieved through methods of data collection which were congruent with Gadamer's philosophic hermeneutics, and which included identification of the researcher's prejudices, utilising a researcher's reflexive journal and use of hermeneutic interviews. Howlin (2008) claimed to use Fleming et al.'s (2003) method to identify, transcribe and record her pre-understandings within a reflexive journal before commencing the study to allow her to move beyond her preunderstandings and gain a fresher, deeper understanding of the phenomenon. Other than Howlin (2008) identifying that she had experience 'of both being and witnessing advocacy' (p. 122) within children's nursing, no other information is given as to how her pre-understandings had influenced the development of her understanding within the research process, and neither is there any other reflection on the reflexive journal previously mentioned. To undertake analysis, Howlin (2008) identified that she had used Benner's narrative method of data analysis which allowed her to identify and produce paradigm cases and exemplars which then produced themes. This is a deviation from Fleming et al (2003) and Gadamer (2012), as Benner's (1985) methodology is based on understanding

taken from Heidegger's philosophy which, as identified in the previous chapter, and is based on 'being' in the world rather than considering how understanding is possible.

Other methodological inconsistencies are noted within the research. Howlin (2008) re-interviewed participants to ensure her understanding of their accounts, rather than looking at the development of her understanding which would have enabled her to achieve a 'fusion of horizons'. There was not any demonstration throughout the research article of applying the principles of Gadamer's hermeneutic to her data analysis or findings, and neither did Howlin (2008) reflect upon the application of Gadamer's hermeneutics within her discussion or limitations section. Howlin's (2008) research would have been more robust had Howlin considered in more depth the relevance and application of Gadamer's hermeneutic and of Fleming et al.'s (2003) methodological approach throughout the research article. A reflective discussion surrounding the difficulties of interpretation and reflection on the relevance of the Gadamer's concepts Howlin had identified and which should have been central to the study would have been beneficial, but it is perhaps not surprising as this seems to reflect the common confusion present during the research process for many researchers between the phenomenological and hermeneutic philosophers. My intentions for my study, are to be open and honest in the method used and to demonstrate clearly how each step of the process has been applied throughout.

A study by Ryde, Strang and Friedrichsen (2008) aimed to explore and develop a deeper understanding of family members' experience of crying within two hospital-based home care palliative care units in Sweden. Ryde et al (2008) claimed to utilise a qualitative hermeneutic approach according to Gadamer and similarly to Howlin's (2008) study identified their intention to identify and use their pre-understandings, the hermeneutic circle and fusion of horizons. Their pre-understanding was identified but only considered through the literature read prior to the start of the study and their clinical experience of palliative care, but there was no specific reflection on the researchers' historical background. However, the authors acknowledged that their pre-understanding and the way it had influenced their study design and analysis was a potential limitation as this had previously been criticised in seminar presentations. The authors' recognised that this was open to judgement by other researchers when considering their methodological approach.

Ryde et al (2008) identified that the data was collected over a two year period until data saturation was reached. This conflicts with Gadamer's philosophical hermeneutics (2012) where the intention is to develop understanding so that a fusion of horizon is achieved for the researcher, rather than achieving data saturation. Indeed, Gadamer considers that understanding is not finite and can never be achieved totally (Gadamer 2012). Data saturation is often associated to grounded theory approaches (Strauss and Corbin 1998) where emerging concepts have been fully explored and no new insights are being generated.

Ryde et al (2008) additionally did provide details of their six step approach to data analysis which would enable another researcher to replicate this method. They did describe how they developed their understanding and interpreted the data from their own the participant's viewpoints to develop a new horizon. However, this differs from Gadamer's intention of achieving a fusion of horizons through co-creating the meaning of experience between people using language (Gadamer 2012, Gaenellos 1999). Additionally, as part of the analysis, the authors attempted to consolidate their study by using dialogical intersubjectivity. This involved the author's splitting up the categorisation of the data analysis with one author coding and developing categories, another author reading all the condensed meaning units and questioning the preliminary analysis and another author discussing the findings with the other authors by 'supplementing and contesting each statement' (p. 348). This helped to develop their fusion of horizons together as a team but is in direct contrast to Gadamer's philosophical hermeneutics who views the development of understanding as occurring when the individual is present to the text (Gadamer 2012) and whereby this guides them to arrive at a new viewpoint. Thus, a team approach to interpretation may lead to biases of each interpreter being introduced in order to achieve a united understanding, rather than each interpreter being able to recognise and consider their own historical awareness and its effects on the research process (Fleming et al 2003). This leads to confusion, the fusion of horizons was not evident within the research process, but some passages were identified which demonstrated new understanding through the whole and parts of the text. This approach could be considered useful as the authors represented the main and subcategories of knowledge developed but did not represent a shared understanding. This paper therefore offers a methodological departure from Gadamer's fusion of horizons and is therefore not

considered a substitute for the method offered by Fleming et al (2003). As I am an individual researcher, I will not be choosing to adopt this method.

Grassley and Nelms (2008) utilised a Gadamerian hermeneutic framework to gain an understanding of maternal breast-feeding confidence and its meaning (Grassley & Nelms 2008). The authors stated that they used Fleming et al.'s (2003) method to guide their analysis through use of open dialogue and application of the hermeneutic circle. The author's description of Fleming et al.'s method is adequate but could have been expanded upon further to aid the novice researcher if looking to replicate this study.

One particular weakness of Grassley and Nelms (2008) study was that the author's did not identify any preunderstandings. Gadamer (2012) regards the provocation of preunderstanding to be a requirement to the process of understanding via the hermeneutic circle. Neither did the authors identify if they achieved a fusion of horizons which would be difficult to achieve if one's pre-understandings have not been identified. This study therefore demonstrates some differences in the philosophical approach to using Gadamer's' philosophical hermeneutics. However, there was sufficient detail in the presentation of Fleming et al.'s (2003) method which supported the use of this method in their study. Within my study, I will be identifying and using my preunderstanding of the APNP role clearly to enable me to enter the hermeneutic circle and develop a fusion of horizon where it occurs, within the three groups of people that I had conversations with.

Another study by Wiriya, Hatthakid, Wiroonpanich and Smith-Battle (2009) aimed to explore what suffering means to Buddhist mothers who had experienced an accidental death of a child using a Gadamerian hermeneutic phenomenological approach (Wiriya et al 2009). As with other studies, this study demonstrates inconsistencies and misconceptions between the delineation of phenomenology and hermeneutics (Fleming et al 2003, Bradshaw 2009). The authors do not seek to clarify, justify or in fact determine what this methodological approach means or the commonalities and differences between these approaches. Gadamer's key philosophical concepts including the hermeneutic circle, dialogue, fusion of horizons and prejudice (preunderstanding) were introduced in that order, but none were discussed and there was no further examination or application to practice within the paper to identify how

the author's utilised these concepts to develop their understanding. Preunderstandings were not discussed and the authors' made no attempt to identify their historical background in relation to this study and how it may have influenced achieving their fusion of horizon with the participants of the study. Therefore, this does not reflect truly Gadamer's philosophical hermeneutics who considers that our preunderstanding is a starting point from which to begin the process of achieving understanding (Gadamer 2012).

Wiriya et al (2009) stated that they utilised Fleming et al.'s (2003) approach to underpin their study. They identified a seven step approach so that this could be replicable by other researchers. It is very similar to the method of Fleming et al (2003) although it is not clearly described in the final steps if the researchers, after generating themes, then related the meaning of these again back to the whole text so that a sense of the text as a whole was expanded (Fleming et al 2003). It is important to do this as other methods of analysis do not consider the movement back to the whole (Van Manen 1997). Additionally, a few other methodological inconsistencies were identified within the paper and were not commented on by the authors. Firstly, it was not clearly articulated how they had followed all the steps identified and how they had used Gadamer's concepts to develop their understanding within the data analysis section, which creates a limitation to the study. Additionally, the authors' stated that their inclusion criteria included the loss of a child between the ages of 16 to 18 years, but within the study the authors identified that mothers were interviewed who had lost a child between the ages of 10 to 18, thus presenting the reader with inconsistencies about the study. As with Ryde et al (2008) the authors of this study did attempt to present new knowledge, but it was not clear how this represented a shared understanding of the authors viewpoint or a clear fusion of horizons (Gadamer 2012). There was no further discussion regarding the methodological implications alongside the use of Gadamer's philosophical hermeneutics or how this was achieved by using Fleming et al's (2003) data analysis methodology. This paper offers limited insight into utilising Gadamer's hermeneutical concepts for any novice researcher looking to replicate this type of study and therefore, I have not chosen to follow this example.

Skar's (2009) study aimed to illuminate the meaning of nurses' experiences of autonomy within work situations. Skar used a hermeneutic approach inspired by Gadamer by using a

combination of in-depth interviews followed by focus group interviews to form the basis for meaning interpretations. Skar then adopted and used the methodological approach suggested by Fleming et al (2003) for the analysis.

Skar (2009) identified three Gadamerian concepts: preunderstanding, the hermeneutic circle, and fusion of horizon and faithfully described these according to Gadamer's hermeneutic (Fleming et al 2003, Gadamer 2012). The five step method of Fleming et al (2003) is demonstrated clearly and would make this replicable for other researchers but there was a lack of application noted between the concepts and method. The in-depth interviews reflecting Gadamer's' hermeneutic to gain understanding, were analysed first using Fleming et al.'s (2003) method, and this then allowed the researchers to expand their understanding of statement's made through two focus groups.

Focus groups can be a good source of gaining information from a larger group of people (Bryman 2004, Clough and Nuthouse 2012) on a specified subject but the researcher has to consider how group dynamics may impact upon focus group dialogue (Bryman 2004) and may be in contrast to Gadamer's philosophical hermeneutics who views understanding as achievable when the individual is present to the text – a focus group may lead to group bias and difficulty with applying preunderstanding to the situation, and thus being open to entering the hermeneutic circle may be difficult to achieve.

Skar (2009) did not reflect upon this but instead presented themes and passages which they claimed represented the whole and the parts of the text and thereby demonstrated new understanding of the phenomenon. Whilst interesting, this focus highlighted the themes and subthemes developed rather than necessarily the shared understanding or a fusion of horizons.

Skar (2009) also suggested that the 'rather small sample and various representations of nurses from different workplaces (Skar 2009, p. 2232) were a limitation to the study. This conflicts with Gadamer's hermeneutics and qualitative research principles (Bryman 2004) where gaining an understanding of social and historical context are the general aim, rather than numbers and size being of concern which can provide generalisation of results for populations more commonly seen within quantitative studies (Bryman 2004, Parahoo, 2014).

Thus, this paper failed to clearly articulate the relationship between the utilisation of the concepts identified, and the work of Gadamer, and as such I would not choose to undertake my study in this way.

Lindberg, Persson and Bondas (2012) aimed to develop an understanding of collaboration between a hospital and university regarding the integration of caring science in practice using a hermeneutical interpretative approach within their analysis inspired by Fleming et al (2003). The major flaw to this study is that the authors did not in fact discuss which elements of hermeneutics underpinned their study and only reviewed the article by Fleming et al (2003), thus this does not give the reader any insight into which hermeneutic concepts were being applied, and therefore it was impossible to see how these influenced and developed their understanding of the phenomenon (Gadamer 2012). While the motivation of the research was in keeping with hermeneutics, and the authors did identify that their preconceptions, meaning preunderstanding, evolved from difference experiences as nurses and teachers (Lindberg et al 2012), there was no further reflection on this statement which could be considered as a methodological weakness and how preunderstandings if provoked are central to the process of developing understanding via the hermeneutic circle (Gadamer 2012, Fleming et al 2003).

Focus group interviews were undertaken which is a commonly used approach with phenomenological research where several participants have experience of and can discuss a given topic (Bryan 2004). This has rarely been seen in relation to data collection in philosophical hermeneutic papers but was seen in the study by Skar (2009). As previously discussed, this is in potentially in conflict with Gadamer's hermeneutic (2012) where the process of data analysis involves the co-construction of the researchers' horizon with that of each individual participant which then enables the researcher to engage with the hermeneutic circle and develop an understanding of the phenomenon to achieve a fusion of horizons (Laverty 2003). Focus groups can be a useful method for collecting qualitative research data but there are limitations in the employment of this method, such as meaning is jointly constructed, introducing bias between the group and often rendering the development of a strategy of analysis which incorporates both themes and patterns of interaction more challenging (Bryman 2004, Clough & Nutbrown 2012). Additionally, the researcher should

consider group interview subtleties where there may be a variety of participants with differing opinions. Group dynamics may include more restrained participants and more vocal participants which can make the group difficult to manage to allow each participant a viewpoint. It is also acknowledged that focus groups can lead to participants being more prone to express culturally expected views rather than their own individual viewpoint (Bryman 2004). Overall, Lindberg, Persson and Bondas's (2012) study presented a very limited insight into the application of Fleming et al.'s (2003) method because of its lack of discussion and application to any underpinning philosophical hermeneutics, and I will not be reproducing this study methods within my own research.

Soderhamn, Dale and Soderhamn (2013) aimed to re-analyse narratives using a Gadamerian-based research method based on Fleming et al (2003). The narratives re-analysed had previously been examined using a descriptive phenomenological research method (Giorgi 2009) to describe self-care activities of older people. The re-analysis was undertaken to develop an understanding of why self-care activities were actualised. The research method utilised is clearly articulated and follows Fleming et al's (2003) framework, making this replicable to other researchers. One weakness of this study, however, is that the central concepts of Gadamer which should have been intrinsically identified within the study were not discussed within this paper, except for the concept of preunderstanding, therefore this would be a limitation for the novice researcher who wishes to achieve understanding through the hermeneutic process.

While Soderhamn, Dale and Soderhamn (2013) did acknowledge that the key concept of pre-understanding was integral to Gadamer's philosophical hermeneutics, where 'understanding is only possible through one's pre-understanding' (Soderhamn et al 2013, p. 20592/2) this was not discussed until the limitation section of the study which made it difficult to appreciate how their pre-understanding had influenced the whole study and their resulting fusion of horizons.

Furthermore, this paper was based on a re-analysis of narratives which can be seen as another possible weakness. According to Gadamer, it is essential to gain understanding through texts gained from participants, where that understanding may only be possible through dialogue. The notion of dialogue here does not only mean through a conversation between two people,

but also the reader and text (Fleming et al 2003). However, only the previous narrative was available to the authors, and they acknowledged that this was a limitation to the study, although one of the authors had performed the interviews for the initial study thereby having some first-hand knowledge from the study participants. The authors reflected that the text therefore was the starting point for the interpretation of this study, which is supported by Austgard (2013) who considers that when using a Gadamerian-based hermeneutic research method it is most important to understand text. Overall, the study provided an interesting insight into the application of Fleming et al.'s (2003) methodological approach but a discussion surrounding the Gadamerian based concepts and the complexities of interpretation would have proven beneficial. My study is open and transparent and has discussed the central concepts which are important within the study and demonstrates how they are applied throughout.

In a further study, Weiland (2013) aimed to understand the meaning of autonomy to nurse practitioners underpinned by Gadamerian hermeneutics with Fleming et al.'s (2003) method being employed. Within this paper, the author discusses hermeneutics as a framework, but no central Gadamerian concepts are identified or discussed within the study. While the aims of the research were in keeping with hermeneutics, and the author did briefly discuss that they were a nurse practitioner which had influenced the study, there was no further reflection on the concepts of preunderstanding or other influences from a hermeneutical stance which would allow the reader to comprehend the development of understanding through text. The author considered within the limitation section that as a nurse practitioner this could be seen as a weakness 'which may have caused findings to be overlooked' (pg. 103). This however conflicts with Gadamer's hermeneutic where researchers are required to identify their preunderstandings of the topic, in this case according to Gadamer, the nurse practitioner by acknowledging her tradition, language and culture as a nurse practitioner could have strengthened her understanding of autonomy with other nurse practitioners enabling her to be able to move beyond her horizon and achieve a fusion of horizons (Fleming et al 2003, Gadamer 2012). A discussion on how the author's preunderstandings if provoked were central to the process of understanding via the hermeneutic circle (Gadamer 2012, Fleming et al 2003) would have been beneficial and would have demonstrated a deeper understanding

of hermeneutic tradition, rather than identifying her role as a nurse practitioner as being considered a weakness.

Within Weiland's (2013) analysis and interpretation of data, the author suggests that data analysis followed the method explicated by Gadamer (2006) and further clarified by Fleming et al (2003). This suggests that the author has not remained faithful to Gadamer's philosophical writings and has not recognised that Gadamer does not offer a methodology to develop understanding (Gadamer 2012).

Weiland (2013), similarly to Ryde et al (2008) who suggested that data saturation was reached within their study, also considers that data saturation was achieved after seven interviews. This as suggested before is in contrast to Gadamer's philosophical hermeneutics (Gadamer 2012) where the intention is to develop understanding so that a fusion of horizons is achieved for the researcher (Gadamer 2012) rather than reaching for a point of data saturation that is often referred to in phenomenological and qualitative studies.

This paper offers very limited insight into Gadamer's hermeneutics but does offer some detail of the method used by Fleming et al (2003) for any novice researcher looking to replicate this type of study. However, it has too many limitations from my perspective and will not be used within my study.

Finally, since the publication of Fleming et al (2003) method for undertaking Gadamerian hermeneutic research, one other method has been identified within the literature, as being useful for use with Gadamerian hermeneutic research, and is critically discussed here in order to illuminate and support further my decision to use Fleming et al.'s method for this study.

Austgard (2013) developed a Gadamerian philosophical hermeneutic methodological approach for researchers to consider using which Austgard suggests helps researchers to operationalise their thinking into practical use. Austgard (2012) considers Gadamer's hermeneutics through the key concept of understanding, interpretation and application which he considers allows the analysis to be inherent within the interpretation. Austgard uses a four step approach inspired by other Norwegian research scholars. These steps appear consistent with the work of Gadamer, but one major difference is noted. Austgard (2013)

considers the identification of 'fore-understanding' which emerges from the different opinions of other researchers gained from an overview of existing research and the literature available within the topic area. Austgard suggests that this 'hermeneutic preparation' allows the researcher to enter the hermeneutic circle and to be conscious of the 'hermeneutic situation' (Austgard 2013, p. 832). This differs from Fleming et al.'s (2003) method who consider Gadamer's concept of preunderstanding. Gadamer considers that pre-understanding gives one an historical awareness which is considered as a positive stance for knowledge and understanding to develop (Gadamer 2012, Fleming et al 2003). I believe that as a nurse educator and an experienced paediatric nurse that my pre-understandings allow me to consider the development of my understanding of the APNP role from three different perspectives from a deeper stance rather than just through 'fore-understanding' suggested by Austgard (2013). My historical tradition and culture of being a paediatric nurse, working with colleagues and alongside parents whose child was being looked after in the past has impacted on my awareness of nursing and advanced practice and not just through the literature which I have read as a nurse educator.

In addition to this, Austgard does not speak German and therefore developed his work from the English Translation of Truth and Method and developed much of his knowledge and interpretation of Gadamer's hermeneutic from two other modern philosophers in Norway (Martinsen, and Nissen p.829). Austgard acknowledges that this therefore may limit the scope of his work because some of the key concepts are difficult to translate into other languages and other philosophers may interpret things differently. Gadamer himself states that every translator is an interpreter (Gadamer 2012), therefore this does not detract from Austgard's work. For these reasons, this paper further helped support my decision regarding the appropriateness of using Fleming et al's (2003) method of study. Fleming et al (2003) does indeed speak German and found this useful in order to look at original German text, however, many other researchers have now studied and written about Gadamer's philosophical hermeneutics who are not native German speakers, and I therefore consider that this is not a disadvantage.

Appendix 3: IRAS Ethics form

Health Research Authority

NRES Committee East of England - Hatfield

Room 002, TEDCO Business Centre
Rolling Mill Road
Jarrow
Tyne and Wear
NE32 3DT

Telephone: 0191 428 3387

12 November 2013

Mrs Mandy J Allen
Lecturer Child Health
University of the West of Scotland
UWS, Hamilton Campus
Almada Street
Hamilton
Lanarkshire
ML3 0JB

Dear Mrs Allen

Study title: An exploration of how the Advanced Paediatric Practitioner is perceived from the perspective of service users and service providers in NHS Scotland.

REC reference: 13/EE/0399

Protocol number: N/A

IRAS project ID: 133967

Thank you for your email of 07 November 2013. I can confirm the REC has received the documents listed below and that these comply with the approval conditions detailed in our letter dated 31 October 2013

Documents received

The documents received were as follows:

Document	Version	Date
Participant Consent Form	3	06 November 2013
Participant Information Sheet: Service Providers	3	06 November 2013
Participant Information Sheet: Parents	3	06 November 2013

Approved documents

The final list of approved documentation for the study is therefore as follows:

Document	Version	Date
Covering Letter	Mandy Allen	01 October 2013
Interview Schedules/Topic Guides	2	28 October 2013
Investigator CV	Mandy Allen	01 October 2013
Investigator CV	Marion Welsh	04 September 2013
Investigator CV	Yvonne Robb	01 October 2013
Letter from Sponsor	Paul Flowers & Yvonne Robb	25 September 2013

A Research Ethics Committee established by the Health Research Authority

Letter of invitation to participant	2	28 October 2013
Other: Letter for Insurance Arrangements	Mandy Allen	01 October 2013
Other: Manager Letter	2	28 October 2013
Other: Reply Paid Slip for Service Providers	2	28 October 2013
Other: Reply Paid Slip for Parents	2	28 October 2013
Participant Consent Form	3	06 November 2013
Participant Information Sheet: Service Providers	3	06 November 2013
Participant Information Sheet: Parents	3	06 November 2013
Protocol	2	28 October 2013
REC application	IRAS Version 3.5, 133967/516338/1/728	22 October 2013

You should ensure that the sponsor has a copy of the final documentation for the study. It is the sponsor's responsibility to ensure that the documentation is made available to R&D offices at all participating sites.

13/EE/0399 **Please quote this number on all correspondence**

Yours sincerely

Miss Sarah Grimshaw
REC Manager

E-mail: nrescommittee.eastofengland-hatfield@nhs.net

Copy to: *Dr Yvonne Robb, Glasgow Caledonian University*
Mr Raymond Hamill, NHS Lanarkshire

Information Sheet for Parents.

1. Study Title

An exploration of how the Advanced Paediatric Nurse Practitioner is perceived from the perspective of service users and service providers in NHS Scotland.

2. Invitation Paragraph.

You are being invited to take part in a research study. Before you decide on participating, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Your participation in this study is entirely voluntary. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss with others if you wish. Please do not hesitate to contact me if I can supply any further information. Contact details are at the end of this sheet.

Thank-you for reading this.

3. What is the purpose of this study?

I am currently a post-graduate student studying for a Professional Doctorate in Health and Social Care degree at Glasgow Caledonian University. I am also a University Lecturer in child health at the University of the West of Scotland and have an interest in Advanced Paediatric Practice.

To date the advanced paediatric nurse practitioner role is still relatively new within NHS Scotland and there is very little research available about this area of clinical practice. I am therefore looking to explore this area of practice and gain people's perspectives on the role within NHS Scotland.

As you have been identified as being a parent whose child has been seen by an advanced paediatric nurse practitioner within the last 3 months (termed as a service user), I am inviting you to take part in this study.

This research will be carried out through the use of one to one audio recorded interviews which may last up to 60 minutes. There may be a follow-up interview with each participant when all of the first interviews have taken place (in person or by phone) arranged at a mutually agreed time.

I hope to have completed the analysis of this study by May 2015.

4. Why have I been invited to take part?

You have been invited to take part in this study as you have been recognised as someone who is:

A parent whose child has recently been seen and treated within the last 3 months by an advanced paediatric nurse practitioner.

5. Do I have to take part?

No, it is up to you to decide whether or not to take part. Your decision to take part is entirely voluntary. If you do decide to take part you will be asked to keep this information sheet and you are asked to send back a reply paid envelope to me. When I have received replies, I will contact you directly to arrange a mutually agreed date, time and venue for the interview to take place. If you decide to take part you are still free to withdraw at any time, and without giving a reason.

6. What will I have to do?

You will be invited to take part in a one to one audio recorded discussion focusing in on your recent experience of the care and treatment provided to your child by an advanced paediatric nurse practitioner. I will not ask you to discuss any personal or clinical information about your child but will focus only on your perception of the role of the Advanced Paediatric Nurse Practitioner.

The discussion will be audio taped with your consent, and notes which are pertinent to the discussion may be made to help the researcher in the writing up of these discussions. Another person may be present with the researcher to help with the management of the interview. The discussion about your experience of this role will be anonymised completely for the purpose of analysis for the final report. Audio taped discussions will be deleted at an appropriate time once transcription of the interview has taken place and accuracy confirmed. Some direct quotes from the discussions may be used within the final report, but these will be anonymised so that you are not personally identifiable.

7. What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

This research does not pose any risk or disadvantage to any subject participating in the study. If as a participant, you feel strongly about any discussion evolving, you have the right not to participate in that discussion.

If you feel that you would like to discuss anything sensitive about the advanced paediatric practitioner role that falls out with the remit of this research project, the researcher will give you details of how to contact the appropriate service manager or Appropriate information that will allow you to access the NHS complaints procedure through the Patient Advice and Support Service (PASS, NHS Scotland) if required.

Participants' involvement is treated as strictly confidential. However, confidentiality may be breached if a participant discloses evidence of poor practice that may be

harmful to patients. This would only take place after the researcher has taken guidance from her supervisor.

8. What are the possible benefits of the study?

The information collated from this study will help identify a variety of experiences and perspectives on the evolving advanced paediatric nurse practitioner role within NHS Scotland. This information will be disseminated through publications and conference presentations to highlight the findings and understanding gained about this role.

9. Will my taking part in this study be kept confidential?

Absolutely. All information/discussion that takes place within the interview will be anonymised, so that individuals cannot be identified in any manner.

The interview/discussions will be recorded digitally (with consent) and then transcribed. All participants will be sent a copy of the transcript for checking to ensure accuracy of the discussion. All data at this stage will be anonymised. Once the content of the discussion has been verified by the participant, the researcher will contact the participant for a follow-up interview after the first interviews are completed. The further discussion that evolves from this will then be analysed and will inform and help the researcher in developing a mutual understanding about your experience and perspective on the advanced paediatric nurse practitioner role.

All information will be treated in the strictest of confidence and handled only by the researcher. All information gathered will be kept locked in a lockable cabinet in a secure environment by the researcher, and in computers that are password protected and can only be accessed by the researcher.

Anonymised information for my study can also be accessed by, should they require it, by my: University Supervisor
However, they are also bound by rules of confidentiality.

10. What will happen to the results of the research study?

When all the research has been analysed, a report will be generated. This report may be published within a journal at a later date. Your name or any identifying information will not appear on any publication or in any presentation relating to this study. All participants will be sent a copy of the research results at the end of the study. Further copies of this will be available by contacting the researcher directly – as per contact details below.

11. Who has reviewed the study?

NRES Committee East of England – Hatfield (NHS research ethics committee) and Glasgow Caledonian University Higher Degree Ethics Committee have all reviewed the proposal for this study, and given approval for it to be conducted.

12. Contact for further information.

You may ask any questions at any time about your rights as a participant in this study, or the research study itself. Should you wish to discuss taking part in this study directly, or require any further details, you can contact me as follows:

Mandy Allen, Lecturer in child health, University of the West of Scotland, Hamilton.

Telephone: [REDACTED] Ext 8478 Email: [REDACTED].

13. Complaints procedure.

If you have a concern about any aspect of this study, you should ask to speak to the researcher who will do the best to answer your questions (01698 283100 ext 8478). If you remain unhappy and wish to complain formally, you can do this by contacting the Director of Studies at Glasgow Caledonian University (Yvonne Robb on [REDACTED] or [REDACTED]).

Your contribution to this study is greatly appreciated. Please complete and send back the reply paid slip enclose

Information Sheet for Service Providers.

1. Study Title

An exploration of how the Advanced Paediatric Nurse Practitioner is perceived from the perspective of service users and service providers in NHS Scotland.

2. Invitation Paragraph.

You are being invited to take part in a research study. Before you decide on participating, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Your participation in this study is entirely voluntary. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss with others if you wish. Please do not hesitate to contact me if I can supply any further information. Contact details are at the end of this sheet.

Thank-you for reading this.

3. What is the purpose of this study?

I am currently a post-graduate student studying for a Professional Doctorate in Health and Social Care degree at Glasgow Caledonian University. I am also a University Lecturer in child health at the University of the West of Scotland and have an interest in Advanced Paediatric Practice.

To date the advanced paediatric nurse practitioner role is still relatively new within NHS Scotland and there is very little research available about this area of clinical practice. I am therefore looking to explore this area of practice and gain people's perspectives on the role within NHS Scotland.

As you have been identified as being a service provider who has experience of either being an advanced paediatric nurse practitioner or has close contact with an advanced paediatric nurse practitioner, I am inviting you to take part in this study.

This research will be carried out through the use of one to one audio recorded interviews which may last up to 60 minutes. There may be a follow-up interview with each participant when all of the first interviews have taken place (in person or by phone) arranged at a mutually agreed time.

I hope to have completed the analysis of this study by May 2015.

4. Why have I been invited to take part?

You have been invited to participate in this study as you have been recognised as someone who either:

Works currently in an advanced paediatric nurse role or

Works closely with an advanced paediatric nurse practitioner (service provider)

5. Do I have to take part?

No, it is up to you to decide whether or not to take part. Your decision to take part is entirely voluntary. If you do decide to take part you will be asked to keep this information sheet and you are asked to send back a reply paid envelope to me. When I have received replies, I will contact you directly to arrange a mutually agreed date, time and venue for the interview to take place. If you decide to take part you are still free to withdraw at any time, and without giving a reason.

6. What will I have to do?

You will be invited to take part in a one to one audio recorded interview (discussion) focusing in on your experience and perspectives of the advanced paediatric nurse practitioner role.

The discussion will be audio taped with your consent, and notes which are pertinent to the discussion may be made to help the researcher in the writing up of these discussions. Another person may be present with the researcher to help with the management of the interview. The discussion about your experience and perspective of this role will be anonymised completely for the purpose of analysis for the final report. Audio taped discussions will be deleted at an appropriate time once transcription of the interview has taken place and accuracy confirmed. Some direct quotes from the discussions may be used within the final report, but these will be anonymised so that you are not personally identifiable.

7. What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

This research does not pose any risk or disadvantage to any subject participating in the study. If as a participant, you feel strongly about any discussion evolving, you have the right not to participate in that discussion.

If you feel that you would like to discuss anything sensitive about the advanced paediatric practitioner role that falls out with the remit of this research project, the researcher will give you details of how to contact the appropriate service manager or appropriate information that will allow you to access the NHS complaints procedure.

Participants' involvement is treated as strictly confidential. However, confidentiality may be breached if a participant discloses evidence of poor practice that may be harmful to patients. This would only take place after the researcher has taken guidance from her supervisor.

8. What are the possible benefits of the study?

The information collated from this study will help identify a variety of experiences and perspectives on the evolving advanced paediatric nurse practitioner role within NHS Scotland. This information will be disseminated through publications and conference presentations to highlight the findings and understanding gained about this role.

9. Will my taking part in this study be kept confidential?

Absolutely. All information/discussion that takes place within the interview will be anonymised, so that individuals cannot be identified in any manner.

The interview/discussions will be recorded digitally (with consent) and then transcribed. All participants will be sent a copy of the transcript for checking to ensure accuracy of the discussion. All data at this stage will be anonymised. Once the content of the discussion has been verified by the participant, the researcher will contact the participant for a follow-up interview after the first interviews are completed. The further discussion that evolves from this will then be analysed and will inform and help the researcher in developing a mutual understanding about your experience and perspective on the advanced paediatric practitioner role.

All information will be treated in the strictest of confidence and handled only by the researcher. All information gathered will be kept locked in a lockable cabinet in a secure environment by the researcher, and in computers that are password protected and can only be accessed by the researcher.

Anonymised information for my study can also be accessed by, should they require it my: University Research Supervisor

However, they are also bound by rules of confidentiality.

10. What will happen to the results of the research study?

When all the research has been analysed, a report will be generated. This report may be published within a journal at a later date. Your name or any identifying information will not appear on any publication or in any presentation relating to this study.

All participants will be sent a copy of the research results at the end of the study. Further copies of this will be available by contacting the researcher directly – as per contact details below.

11. Who has reviewed the study?

NRES Committee East of England – Hatfield (NHS research ethics committee) and Glasgow Caledonian University Higher Degree Ethics Committee have all reviewed the proposal for this study, and given approval for it to be conducted.

12. Contact for further information.

You may ask any questions at any time about your rights as a participant in this study, or the research study itself. Should you wish to discuss taking part in this study directly, or require any further details, you can contact me as follows:

Mandy Allen, Lecturer in child health, University of the West of Scotland, Hamilton.

Telephone: [REDACTED] Ext 8478 Email: [REDACTED]

13. Complaints procedure.

If you have a concern about any aspect of this study, you should ask to speak to the researcher who will do the best to answer your questions (01698 283100 ext 8478). If you remain unhappy and wish to complain formally, you can do this by contacting the Director of Studies at Glasgow Caledonian University (Yvonne Robb on [REDACTED] or [REDACTED]:

Your contribution to this study is greatly appreciated. Please complete and send back the reply paid slip enclosed.

Appendix 5: Consent Form

CONSENT FORM

Title of project: An exploration of how the Advanced Paediatric Nurse Practitioner is perceived from the perspective of service users and service providers in NHS Scotland.

Name of Researcher: Mandy Allen

Please initial box.

1. I confirm that I have read and understood the information sheet dated for the above study and have had the opportunity to ask questions and have them answered satisfactorily.

2. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time, without giving any reason, and without my legal rights being affected.

3. I agree to the use of audio equipment for taping the research interview.

4. I understand that the relevant sections of my data collected during the study, may be looked at by individuals from Glasgow Caledonian University, from regulatory authorities or from the NHS Trust, where it is relevant to my taking part in this research. I give permission for these individuals to have access to my records.

5. I agree to take part in the above study.

----- Name	----- Date	----- Signature
..... Name of researcher Date Signature

1 copy for participant, 1 for researcher

Appendix 6: Initial general pre-understanding of APNP role before starting study

Initial general pre-understanding of APNP role before starting study influencing my ontology and epistemology. Undertaken in 2015 prior to conversations with any groups:

Appendix 7: General overview and influences of pre-understanding of APNP role 2015.

Appendix 8a: Pre-understanding of APNP role

Undertaken prior to conversations with APNPs undertaken in 2015

Appendix 8b: APNPs post conversation subthemes

Undertaken after all 8 conversations with APNPs in 2016

Appendix 8c: Fusion of Horizon for APNPs

3 main themes developed after analysis of conversations with APNPs initially in 2016, then reviewed in 2023

Appendix 9a: Pre-understanding of Parents thoughts about APNPs

Undertaken prior to conversations with parents in 2015

Appendix 9b: Parents post conversations subthemes in 2015

Undertaken after all conversations with Parents

Appendix 9c: Fusion of Horizon for Parents

3 main themes developed after analysis of conversations with parents initially in 2016, then reviewed in 2023/24

Appendix 10: Final Fusion of Horizon for all 3 groups

Overall understanding demonstrated throughout Chapter 9

Appendix 11: Anonymised Demographics of participants

Anonymised Demographic Information of APNPs

Name	Age	Qualified as a nurse in years	Qualified as an APNP in years	Clinical area of practice
Lesley	33	13 years	3 years	General paediatrics (rural DGH)
Andi	35	15 years	3 years	General paediatrics/assessment unit (rural DGH)
Jamie	51	22 years	10 years	Emergency department (City DGH)
Jo	36	15 years	3 years	General paediatrics (City DGH)
Rowan	49	28 years	2 years	General paediatrics (City DGH)
Bobbi	48	24 years	2 years	Community (rural)
Alex	32	12 years	4 years	Emergency department (city DGH)
Jordan	49	24 years	4 years	Assessment unit (rural DGH)

Anonymised Demographic information of 'others'

Name	Age	Post	Length of time in post	Area of practice
Ainsley	40	Consultant paediatrician	2 years (Qualified 1997)	General paediatrics
Chris	47	Consultant paediatrician	7 years (qualified 1990)	General paediatrics
Taylor	45	Consultant paediatrician	11 years (qualified 1994)	General paediatrics
Jackie	62	Clinical nurse manager	14 years (qualified 1984)	General paediatrics
Nikki	52	Consultant paediatrician	8 years (qualified 1994)	General paediatrics
Corey	48	CCN	7 years (qualified 2004)	Community
Sam	53	Lead nurse	11 years (qualified 1981)	General paediatrics
Lindsay	55	Chief nurse/clinical director of nursing	7 years (qualified 1981)	All paediatric services within a large NHS board

Anonymised Demographic Parent Data:

Parent name	Age range	Where interviewed	Child condition – acute or chronic
Pete	Age range for parents ranged from 28-49 years	Acute paediatric ward	Acute
Lorna and Adam (couple)		Own home	Chronic and acute
Margaret		Own home	Chronic
Lisa		Acute paediatric ward	Acute
Wendy		Acute paediatric ward	Acute